

**The role of English Language teachers at a Chinese university in
developing motivation and intercultural competence in their Chinese
students: the students' perceptions**

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Abstract

English is acknowledged as a global language in China. In order to prepare Chinese students to be globally competitive in the labour market in the future, higher educational institutions in China offer English language courses which are taught by both English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers. In the cross-cultural settings of the English language classroom, the development of intercultural competence and students' motivation in English language classes are considered as important elements of English language education which can develop students' English language skills effectively. However, there is little research on students' perceptions of the development of intercultural competence and their related motivation enabled by both English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers in the Chinese context. This study, therefore aims to explore Chinese university students' perceptions of the role of their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers in developing motivation and intercultural competence in the English language classroom. This study examines two different groups of Chinese students: English major and non-English major students, their perceptions, and whether they differ in their perceptions of how their English teachers develop their motivation and intercultural competence in the classroom. The theoretical framework selected for this study is Byram's (1997) intercultural competence model which provides a clear definition of the intercultural competence theory, which enabled the researcher to form the interview questions for data collection.

This study uses an interpretive, qualitative research approach in analysing the data collected from twenty students at one university in China. The participants include ten English major students and ten non-English major students. The participants were selected for the focus groups interviews, and then in order to gather rich data for this study, some of the participants were then invited to take part in semi-structured in-depth interviews. All the data collected for this study was coded to themes, and was analysed through interpretive phenomenological approach.

This study provided a number of key findings: English and non-English major students' perceptions of their motivation to learn English, and the development of intercultural competence by their English language teachers in the classroom. Additionally, English

major and non-English major students at the Chinese university are found to differ in their preferences for English language courses taught by English 'native' or 'non-native' teachers.

The researcher intends that this current study will help the readers and the English language educational departments in China to consider the importance of intercultural competence in foreign language teaching, and to consider students' voices in relation to English language learning.

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Author's Declaration

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, this thesis is the result of the researcher's own work and has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institutions.

Printed name Yueying Zheng

Signature

List of Abbreviations

ELF: English as a lingua franca

L1: first language

L2: second language

FL: foreign language

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

This chapter provides a brief introduction to the study, presents and discusses the rationale for this study. It then introduces the aims of this research and research questions, and briefly overviews the research approach the researcher selected for this study. In addition, a discussion of the significance of this study and an outline of this thesis are considered at the end of this chapter.

This study sets out to explore students' perceptions of how their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop motivation and intercultural competence in the classroom at a Chinese university setting. More specifically, investigations focused on both student groups, which are English major and non-English major students, to discover whether there is any difference in their motivation to learn English. According to the courses they have selected, these student groups are taught English language by both English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers in Chinese universities. This study aims to explore whether any differences of their motivations to learn English between English and non-English major students affects their perceptions of how their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom. The skills of developing intercultural competence in the classroom by English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers are then examined and discussed based on students' perceptions, that is, from the data provided by the two groups of students. The associations between language learning motivation and practice and theories of intercultural competence closely relate to the area of this study, and help the researcher to form the research questions, thus informing the discussion around the findings for the study.

1.2 Rationale for the Study

The English language has emerged as a lingua franca within the context of globalization (Crystal, 2003). It is regarded as an essential tool to connect different nations and cultures by communicating through the English language (Steger, 2009). Given this situation, a huge demand for teachers to teach English language to speakers whose first language is not English can be found in different countries, especially for those teachers

whose first language is English (Davies, 2009). In the Chinese context, English is acknowledged as a global language in China, as the Chinese government realized the importance of improving the English proficiency of Chinese learners after China opened up its borders and entered the World Trade Organization (Cai, 2010). In order to develop Chinese learners' English language skills to be competitive for the labour market and for the country to be competitive in, the Chinese government offered opportunities for those teachers whose first language is English to teach in China, in order to develop English communicative skills and knowledge of Western culture of Chinese learners (Wright & Zheng, 2017).

However, the question then arises of whether English 'native' teachers, simply by being speakers of the language, are able to provide the English teaching knowledge and skills to their students which are suitable in the Chinese context. Timmis (2005) indicated that English 'native' speaker teaching models are probably the best starting point for learners to understand a language. However, Alptekin (2002) argued that learners who are taught the language by 'native' speakers within the target language culture in the UK or US, would appear to have difficulties using and understanding an international language in a cross-cultural setting. These related issues, around whether or not 'native' or 'non-native' English-speaking teachers have better English teaching skills to teach Chinese students in the Chinese context are discussed later in this thesis.

In the Chinese context, Jin (2005) noted that Chinese teachers would be better able to teach English language in the Chinese culture setting than English 'native' teachers, as 'China English' used by Chinese teachers is acknowledged as a potential standard variety alongside the standard varieties of British and American English. 'China English' refers to the English language which is based on a standard English format, but with cross-linguistic influences from Chinese culture (Li, 2007). However, being taught by the 'China English' model, Chinese learners appear to have difficulties accomplishing English writing and speaking in the same standard format as 'native' speakers (Jiang, 2014). The result is that, Chinese learners of English may face challenges when they study or work abroad. Both English 'native' and 'non-native' teaching models appear to have limitations, and thus the accommodation of the case of English as a tool of international and intercultural communication is urgently required in English language education in China (Alptekin, 2002). In other words, intercultural competence is

considered as an important skill for English language teachers and learners in China. Thus, this context is one of the impetuses of this study which aims to discover students' perceptions of how their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom, in order to make recommendations and support English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers and English departments at Chinese universities to improve intercultural teaching in English language education.

In light of the discussions above, this study has been undertaken in order to investigate English major and non-English major students' perceptions and suggestions as to help English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers to develop cultural understandings of other cultures, and skills of practising intercultural competence in the classroom. Kramersch (2005) considered that for language teachers who have limited understanding and experience of other cultures, specific intercultural training should be offered. However, teacher education programmes and training in general appear to fail to prepare teachers for delivering their knowledge in the classroom (Crandall, 2000). Therefore, in order to provide recommendations to support English language teachers to improve their skills of intercultural competence beyond any training they might already have had, as it is suggested by Kramersch (2005) that language teachers should be offered specific intercultural training. This study aims to explore the development of intercultural competence between English language teachers and students in the classroom which will help the English language departments in China to understand teachers' skills of delivering intercultural competence in the classroom, and to develop their skills of intercultural competence. The related findings around this issue will be discussed in Chapter 6.

The researcher considers the related issues around English learners' motivation to learn English as an important issue in the Chinese context. Chinese university students are acknowledged as those students who are mainly instrumentally motivated to learn English, as they use English as a tool to pass exams, and to gain more opportunities in the labour market after they graduate from the universities (Dornyei & You, 2014; Liu, 2007). However, there is a large number of Chinese learners who appear to lose their motivation to learn English currently. One of the reasons is that students find they lose concentration easily when their Chinese teachers use teacher-centred methods in the English language classes, so they start to lose the motivation to acquire English

knowledge. This is caused by authentic interactions, in the English language with their English teachers and peers in the classroom (Wright & Zheng, 2017); in addition, some Chinese students seem to lack the understanding of how to practise English language in their daily lives. Their limited contact with the target language (Liu, 2007) leads to the result that they do not foresee the need to contact people who are from English-speaking countries (Pan, 2014). This situation results in Chinese students being demotivated to continue learning the English language, as well as engaging in learning in English classes.

Thus, the researcher perceives that Chinese students' motivations to learn English might be affected by teachers' teaching methods, students' understanding of English culture, and their lack of experience of practising the English language with English 'native' speakers. Therefore, this study aims to understand what Chinese learners require to develop their understanding of intercultural competence and to motivate them to learn English, thus to assist English departments in China to find ways to support Chinese learners to learn English effectively. The recommendations to the English departments based on the findings of this study will be discussed in Chapter 7.

This research is designed to support English departments and English language teachers in Chinese universities to revisit the ways intercultural competence is, whether delivered effectively by English language teachers in classes or not. Sercu (2005) pointed out the importance of intercultural competence in foreign language education, as teaching a foreign language is not merely teaching language skills, but more importantly, teaching the students to understand the culture of the target language, and developing their ability to interact with people from different cultures which is necessary in an increasingly globalised world. Therefore, in order to add to the literature and the discussion around improving intercultural competence in English language education in China, this study will look into students' perceptions of intercultural competence developed by their English language teachers, and make recommendations to English language departments and English language teachers in Chinese universities. In order to enable English language teachers to support their students' development of their English language skills effectively, the resulting good practice as well as the positive impact of this study, should have on students' language

and ability to communicate, and thus to build relationships, whether business or personal, in another language.

1.3 Research Questions

- In what ways do University students perceive intercultural competence and the role of their University teachers in contributing to its development in English classes at Chinese universities?
- To what extent is intercultural competence developed between English teachers (both 'native' and non 'native') and Chinese university students?
- In what ways do students think intercultural competence could be developed more effectively in English departments at Chinese universities?
- To what extent do English major and non-English major students differ in their motivation to learn English and in their perceptions of how their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom of their Chinese university?

1.4 Research Aims

The aim of this study is to reveal students' perceptions of the factors that influence intercultural teaching in English classes, and to discover whether English 'native' teachers or 'non-native' teachers have better skills of developing intercultural competence in the classroom according to students' perceptions. To address this research aim, a qualitative research approach will be utilised to collect in-depth information based on students' perceptions, which will enable the researcher to analyse the data thoroughly. The following research aims to support the research questions are advanced:

- To examine and discover Chinese university students' perceptions of intercultural competence of 'native' English-speaking teachers and 'non-native' English teachers in the Chinese university .
- To identify and explore how both 'native' and 'non-native' English teachers develop intercultural competence in English classes based on students' perceptions in the Chinese university.

- To explore in what ways students will be able to develop their understanding of intercultural competence based on students' perceptions in the Chinese university.
- To compare and discuss the difference in students' motivation to learn English and their perceptions of how their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom of their Chinese university.

1.5 Research Approach

This research is designed within a qualitative paradigm. The researcher aims to conduct a small scale piece of research to collect in-depth information instead of seeking determination and generalisation from findings, as it would not align with the focus of this study which analyses the data emerging from the students' perceptions. Therefore, the researcher selected a qualitative paradigm for this study, in order to gather in-depth data from the students, and to analyse students' perceptions of their motivation and the development of intercultural competence by their English language teachers, as developed and discussed in Chapter 5.

1.6 Significance of the Study

There are many models of intercultural competence, such as those situated in international business (Lloyd & Hartel, 2010), and international communication (Lustig & Koester, 2010), but this study focuses on international education (Cushner & Mahon, 2009). This research investigates students' perceptions of intercultural effectiveness in academics, the importance of intercultural competence and makes recommendations to support English language departments at Chinese universities to develop their English language education and English teachers' intercultural competence (Molinsky, 2013).

Current intercultural competence models aim to predict intercultural effectiveness by evaluating three types of outcomes: psychological (cultural adjustment), behavioural (intercultural cooperation) and performance (job performance) (Bhaskar-Shrinivas et al., 2005). Relevant empirical research has focused primarily on psychological and behavioural outcomes to examine the individual's skills of intercultural competence

(Leung et al., 2014). However, there are few studies which have examined the underlying processes of intercultural competence and effects of cultural influence on others' behaviours (Van Dyne et al., 2012). Therefore, to fill the gap in examining the development of intercultural competence and its cultural influence on others, this study will examine five aspects of the intercultural competence theory of English language teachers based on Byram's (1997) model. In addition, to shed light on the influence of the development of the teaching of intercultural competence by English language teachers on students, this research will investigate students' perceptions to explore how their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom at a Chinese university.

Moreover, there are few studies investigating Chinese students' motivations to learn English by distinguishing English major (advanced English class) students and non-English major (ordinary English class) students (Pan et al., 2010). Therefore, this study considers two different paths of English education taken by students in Chinese universities, and considers their English learning motivation and their related perceptions of intercultural competence as taught by their English language teachers. This study will thereby contribute to the relevant research areas by considering different English proficiencies of these students as an important factor in the resulting discussion.

1.7 Outline of the Study

This study comprises six chapters. Following this introductory chapter, Chapter 2 will introduce the context of this study through discussing the challenges and improvements of English language education in China, and will overview the policies which have influenced the teaching methods of English language teachers in China, and which have brought opportunities for Chinese students to be taught by English 'native' teachers. In addition, being affected by these policies, English learners' perceptions of both English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers' abilities to deliver intercultural competence will be discussed, and the related issues around 'native-speakerism' will be introduced in Chapter 3.

Chapter 3 will present the literature which is related to and underpins this study. The central concepts of this study, intercultural competence and second language learning

motivation will be discussed in detail. In addition, this chapter will introduce the related theoretical lenses employed in this study which specifically includes 'native-speakerism' and language identity. A critical review of the related literature will be discussed throughout in this chapter.

Chapter 4 will present and discuss the research methodology used for this study, a discussion of the research methods, tools for data collection, data analysis, and the ontological and epistemological stances of interpretive paradigm selected for this study. Moreover, this chapter will discuss the theoretical framework the researcher selected for data analysis, and the process of data analysis. Issues of ethical considerations, reliability, transferability and the researcher's position in this study will be presented in this chapter.

Chapter 5 will discuss the findings of this research which arise from the research aims and questions designed for this study. The discussion and analysis arising from the examination of the data focuses on the following themes: students' motivation to learn English, students' perceptions of the development of intercultural competence by their English language teachers in English classes and students' suggestions for English departments to help future students' understanding of intercultural competence.

Chapter 6 will be the conclusion of this study. The findings from Chapter 5 will be discussed and evaluated in relation to the research aims and questions. It will set out a summary of the research and consider the implications of the study and recommendations for English language educators in the Chinese context. In addition, the researcher will discuss the limitations of the current study and suggestions for future research.

1.8 Conclusion

This study is designed to investigate and examine the perceptions around how English language teachers deliver intercultural competence in English language classes of two different groups of English language students in Chinese universities. To fill in the gaps in the previous research field, the researcher distinguishes Chinese English language students in two different groups, in order to provide a comprehensive understanding of Chinese university student groups and their experience of and motivations to learn

English. In addition, the researcher will explore their perceptions of how their English teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom by a qualitative interpretive approach, in order to discover how students perceive their English teachers' development of intercultural competence in English classes, and therefore how Chinese students perceive cultural knowledge from their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers and develop their ability of intercultural competence in the classroom.

The detailed discussion of the Chinese context which underpins this study will be presented in the next chapter.

Chapter 2: English Language Context in China

2.1. Introduction

For any discussion of students' perceptions of how their 'native' and 'non-native' English teachers develop their motivation and intercultural competence in the classroom at a Chinese university, it is essential to discuss the context of English language education in China. The reason for this is that the English language education in China has been changing over the years. The crucial shift in English language education took place after China hosted the 2008 Summer Olympics and entered the World Trade Organization. The government realized the importance of improving the English language proficiency of Chinese learners in both oral and literacy skills of the English language in order to enable the Chinese learners to be competitive for the contemporary labour market (Cai, 2010). Therefore, the Ministry of Education in China started to hire more English 'native' teachers from English-speaking countries to help develop communicative skills of Chinese learners (Wright & Zheng, 2017).

2.1.1 Development of English language education in China

However, this was not the first attempt for the Chinese government to develop English language education in China. Since the late 1950s, China has made significant efforts to improve English as a foreign language education throughout China in order to promote economic, social development as well as to secure rights to education of Chinese citizens Rong (2001). In the early 1980s, in order to meet the increasing demand for the English language education of Chinese students, a wide variety of schools were established including kindergartens, primary schools, senior secondary schools and higher educational institutions (Ngok, 2007). These were established to cater for the greater numbers of students throughout each education sector, however, the expansion of English language education failed, because English learning resources which were designed to improve the quality of English language education were limited to the rising numbers of Chinese learners (Hu, 2004).

In order to transform China into a modern socialist country, Deng as the Chinese leader at the time initiated a fundamental reform: to develop a centrally planned economy to a market-oriented economic system (Lewin, 1994). However, in response to the increasing demand for the growing economic situation in China, a reform of the educational system was announced in 1985 to prepare for more well-educated workers (Richard et.al, 1979). This educational reform was launched by the Ministry of Education, which had drafted guidelines and provided a framework for separating students of higher education institutions into two groups: English majors and non-English majors. This was the beginning of a process which lasted until modern times (Pepper, 1990). When students pass the entrance examinations to higher education institutions, both groups of students, that is, English major and non-English major students, are required to enrol in a four-year programme. The students themselves select the programme, therefore they select to study English major or non-English majors at Chinese universities. In the first two years, all students are offered basic courses in the English language, and in the third and fourth year, specific plans for the objectives and curricular content of their particular English Language major classes are developed by the lecturers in the English language departments in order to meet the needs of English major students (Xu,2009).

However, the goals of these two-year basic courses for English major students and non-English major students are different. For English major students, the objectives of the basic courses in the first two years of the degree are to build a solid foundation of English language knowledge to improve their language skills to an advanced level, and these refer to the four language skills: listening, speaking, reading and writing (Xu,2009). For non-English major students, only a 320-hour English course is offered for the total two-year basic programme, nearly four hours a week, unlike English major students, where fourteen hours of English courses per week is offered. The general objective of basic English language courses for non-English major students is to develop the reading skills as well as oral skills which is in contrast with English major students where the intention is to develop the whole range of four English language skills. However, some institutions such as The Medical College in Guangzhou complained that the 320-hour English course was not sufficient in length to support the rising demand

of developing oral English skills for students in China as identified by the government's documents referred above (He, 2011).

The reason why some higher educational institutions complained about the insufficiency of the English language education in China, as well as the challenges of developing the English language education in Chinese universities or colleges will be discussed in the next section.

2.2. Challenges for the English Language Education in China

At the beginning of the twentieth century, China had gone through reforms of its economic, social, cultural and educational domains (Hu, 2004). With the increasing growth of Chinese economic development, there were more changes in relation to the global economy and the integration of China with other countries. This brought challenges and pressures for the Chinese government in developing technological advances and a knowledge-driven economy (Hu, 2004). In addition, the Chinese education system faced a challenge to teach millions of pupils and students the English language. As the Chinese government at that time closed borders to avoid having interaction with the rest of world, only a few Chinese people had the opportunity to acquire English or practise speaking English outside the classroom (Lu, 2012). Thus, one of the reasons why China opened up its borders for trade and exchange with other countries in the 1990s was because there was an urgent need to increase foreign language skills among the population in order to develop international trade in China (Wright & Zheng, 2017). The selection of the English language as a foreign language for secondary school and higher education had been made in 1982, as the Chinese government realised that English was the language used most widely in foreign markets, and this would give China the opportunity and skills to engage with other English language speakers for commercial purposes (Zhang, 2015). At that time, Chinese students in higher education institutions were encouraged to access scientific literature which was published in English, as well as to participate in transnational, scholarly interactions in English (Xu & Yang, 2015).

However, for English language teachers at higher education institutions at that time, teaching English to Chinese students seemed like a challenge because many English language teachers had never had the opportunity to acquire English to a high degree of

fluency which made it difficult for them to deliver advanced English language to Chinese students at higher education level (Wright & Zheng, 2017). In addition, for older teachers who were born in the Maoist era and experienced the Cultural Revolution, it was complicated for them to ensure they acquired and developed the English language to the required standard, because during the Cultural Revolution, learning a foreign language was viewed as an anti-state activity. However, after the Cultural Revolution was softened by the state, the English language was chosen to be taught in schools for the sake of modernisation, as it was no longer considered as a conduit for the 'spiritual pollution' from the capitalist world (Pan,2014). The purpose of learning English was considered by English language teachers in China to be 'to learn a foreign language, not to learn to be a foreigner' (Pan 2014:72). It seemed like a difficult task for those teachers to teach English language skills, while trying not to promote and explain the cultural knowledge of its background and native speakers.

Another challenge around that period was students' motivation to learn the English language. Some learners in China did not understand the attraction of acquiring English knowledge, as they still held the opinion that the language was from people with whom they had no contact and with whom they did not foresee contact (Pan, 2014). Another issue affecting students' motivation was the large class sizes which were normal in China. Students found that they lost concentration easily when teachers used teacher-centred methodologies to deliver knowledge to oversized classes because the classes were so big, and the lesson demanded no personal interaction from the students (Wright & Zheng, 2017). Therefore, English language teachers were forced to teach an advanced level of English to students at a higher educational level when they had not acquired themselves the required level of English language skills and cultural knowledge of English. For students, they did not have the motivation to study a foreign language in oversized classes. Both of these issues made the development of English language education in China quite challenging at that period.

In the 21st century, even though most English language teachers in Chinese universities had studied English Literature and Linguistics in their first degree, only a small amount of them had ever studied in an English-speaking country or used the English language regularly in an authentic context outside the classroom which led to the fact that English language teachers in Chinese universities had limited understanding and

knowledge of the cultural background of the language (Zhao, 2012). Moreover, the rapid rise in student numbers in higher educational institutions in China, had brought pressure on the recruitment of English language teachers. A large number of trainee English language teachers were brought into the higher educational system, only basic teacher training was offered to these trainee teachers by the English departments at universities (Rao & Lei, 2014). It caused a number of serious problems: a large number of young and inexperienced English language teachers had no pedagogic research experience which made it difficult for them to monitor and analyse their own teaching practice; they had low levels of motivation and commitment to improve their English teaching skills; they had poor management of students in large-size classes (Lian & Wang, 2011). As Borg and Liu (2013) noted, classes of more than fifty students were the norm in the foreign language departments at Chinese universities. However, it was difficult for teachers to teach the English language effectively to a large group of students if they themselves had no experience of managing a large number of students before (Liang, 2009; Qi & Wang, 2009).

Moreover, the traditional pedagogic approaches adopted in the English language classroom in China were appropriate to the assessments, since these assessments were mainly written examinations (Wright & Zheng, 2017). As English language teachers in Chinese higher educational institutions had acquired English language from text-focused programmes, they were only able to offer English language courses by presenting texts for comprehension exercises, and by explaining grammar rules (Cai, 2010). This English teaching approach led to very limited opportunities for Chinese students to practise English oral skills (Gao, 2009). Furthermore, this English teaching method of emphasizing the written English affected students' motivation to learn the English language, as their prime motivation was to gain the qualifications to progress through the educational system rather than to use the language as a tool to interact with either 'native speakers' or with those using English as a lingua franca (Wright & Zheng, 2017). In fact, this was in contrast to what the government wanted, as the Chinese government encouraged people to have English language ability in using English orally and engaging with other English language speakers. However, the English language teachers in China were not trained properly for it, and so this was not possible in the Chinese context.

Therefore, limited training of English language teachers, outdated pedagogic approaches, as well as large class sizes made the development of English language education in China challenging. These problems were widely recognised by the political elite in China, so as a result, English language learning was claimed to be highly 'ineffective' at that time (Cai, 2011). In the next section, the changes to government policies and efforts to improve English language education in China will be discussed.

2.3 Amendments to improve the English Language Education Policy in China

In 2004, with the government aware of the problems regarding English language education, the Ministry of Education issued the College English Course Teaching Requirements which focused on improving professional skills of English language teachers (Gao, 2013). Moreover, English language teachers in higher educational institutions were encouraged to use oral methods and student-centred learning methods (Wright & Zheng, 2017). Although in secondary schools, the training of English grammar, reading comprehension, vocabulary and translation were still emphasized in English language classes due to the pressure of passing the entrance examination. The newer textbooks at this level adopted communicative principles which emphasized oral skills and English language culture. In addition, Chinese students were required to spend long hours focusing on their English language homework, reviewing vocabulary and grammar notes, and going over model examination exercises after school (Jin, 2002). In other words, they were still focusing on text-based English language learning methods, rather than practising oral English.

Along with promoting student-centred language learning, the College English Course Teaching Requirements (Gao, 2013) promoted the communicative language teaching approach with its interactive strategies and individualised learning methods. Apart from improving students' communicative competence, developing their cultural knowledge and intercultural communication skills were required as the objectives by the Ministry of Education in China (Liu & Zhang & Yin, 2014). To increase interaction with other countries, a large number of Chinese cooperation programmes with foreign universities were registered with the Ministry of Education (Wright & Zheng, 2017). In this context, English 'native-speaker' teachers from English-speaking countries were offered more opportunities to visit China and to work at Chinese universities.

In addition, as the number of 'native-speaking' English teachers in universities increased, it became difficult for Chinese employers to monitor their quality because English 'native-speaking' teachers varied in their capabilities and experience with regard to teaching English language in China. Therefore, more efforts were still needed to create more opportunities for qualified and experienced English 'native-speaking' teachers, as well as to standardize a recruitment requirement which included a qualification in teaching English language, and graduate certifications from official universities in Western countries (Li, 2020).

Gradually, the level of English language proficiency had improved substantially in China (ibid). In December 2019, in order to develop English testing systems, Chinese policymakers took measures to link China's Standards of English Language Ability (2019) successfully to the TOEFL IBT Test (Test of English as a Foreign Language: a standardized test to measure the English language ability of 'non-native' speakers who plan to enrol in universities in English-speaking countries). This improvement in policy indicated China's ambition to innovate the English education system to a more globalised and advanced level (ibid).

For Chinese students at higher educational institutions, even though passing exams and gaining educational qualifications were still major factors in keeping them focused on English language education, students' motivation to learn English was not only driven by gaining qualifications to progress through higher levels of education. Chinese students who had merely seen English competence as a necessary tool to gain qualifications discovered the motivation to study and develop a thorough understanding of the English language because they discovered an interest in exploring the Western culture; those students who were ambitious about their further study or future career abroad improved their English competence as a necessary skill to help them to engage with people from different countries by speaking English (Cai, 2012). Among those, students who desired to study abroad or see themselves in a foreign travel situation were strongly motivated to improve their proficiency (Shao & Gao, 2016). However, there was still a large number of Chinese students whose English language skills remained at a basic level, who did not have clear reasons for developing their English language skills because they were more comfortable with only speaking their first language (Wei & Su, 2012).

2.4 Students' perceptions of English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers in China

2.4.1 Native-speakerism in China

Traditionally, English is believed by many as the property of its 'native' speakers, therefore, the 'native' norm of English language is considered as the only standard to evaluate the success of English language learning (Fang, 2018). With the development of English as a global language, the number of 'non-native' speakers of English has surpassed the number of 'native' speakers of English. However, in the EFL setting, 'native' speakers of English are considered to no longer have any privilege for intercultural communication, as the English language goes further to legitimate all users of English, and the individual's mutual intelligibility and negotiation skills in intercultural communication are more important than the 'native' standard of English language (Cogo & Dewey, 2012).

In the Chinese context, the current English language policy in China is still largely 'native-oriented' in English language education (Houghton & Rivers, 2013). 'Non-native' teachers of English language at Chinese universities believe that they lack support from the government to empower them to change the 'native-oriented' English language teaching ideology in China, as these teachers believe that professional identities as qualified English language teachers and the need to address language learners' needs are more important in English language education (Fang, 2015). In addition, students and 'non-native' English teachers at Chinese universities believe that they support standard Western English language teaching methods used in China; while the Chinese government should consider publishing multicultural English language textbooks which promote Chinese culture and the reality of cultural globalisation to support English language education in the Chinese context (Liu, 2018).

In China, English language education is still focusing on the 'native' norm of the English language. English 'native' teachers are hired to teach the English language along with 'non-native' teachers at Chinese universities (Wright & Zheng, 2017). Therefore, as the focus of this study, it is important to discuss Chinese university students' perceptions of both English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers because these have not been previously considered within the Chinese context. In the next sections, previous studies and

literature which are related to this issue in the Chinese context will be considered to inform the discussion.

2.4.2 Students' perceptions of English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers in China

In this section, the researcher discusses previous studies which are related to students' perceptions of English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers in the Chinese context. Students' perceptions and preference for both English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers relate to the focus and impetus of this study, which aims to explore students' perceptions of, specifically, the development of intercultural competence of their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers. Chinese students' preference between English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers will also be discussed in the Findings chapter in this study.

2.4.2.1 Chinese students' preference for English 'native' teachers

According to Peng (2006), in Chinese universities, compared to non-English major students, English major students seem to be more satisfied with the English language classes taught by their English 'native' teachers, as the English language proficiency of students is found to be a significant factor that will affect the development of effective intercultural communication between English 'native' teachers and students. In addition, English major students believe that their English 'native' teachers understand the English language better than their 'non-native' teachers, as English 'native' teachers are perceived to be professional in teaching the English language as it is believed by many perhaps they are trained and qualified to teach their first language.

2.4.2.2 Chinese students' preference for English 'non-native' teachers

However, in other previous studies, English 'non-native' teachers with a high proficiency of English language skills are considered to have better language teaching strategies than English 'native' teachers (Siegel, 2003; Cook, 1999; Kasztelanic 2011).

According to Liang (2002) who conducted a survey of 20 English language learners' perceptions of their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers in China, the findings

show that Chinese students believe the precise English accent of their English language teachers plays an important role in their English learning experience, however, students are still found to have positive attitudes towards their English 'non-native' teachers even though they have not acquired the same precise English accent as their English 'native' teachers. These students believe that professional features such as 'being interesting' , 'being prepared' and 'being qualified' in teachers are more necessary than a precise English accent.

Ling and Braine (2007) researched 420 students' perceptions of their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers in Hong Kong universities. The findings show that these students prefer to be taught by 'non-native' teachers than English 'native' teachers as the students believe that 'non-native' teachers of English are able to teach as effectively as English 'native' teachers. In addition, their 'non-native' teachers appear to make more effort to communicate with these students, because these teachers share the same cultural background with the students and they are able to understand the challenges in learning English faced by these local students. However, these students consider that they are not encouraged to develop the skills of critical thinking by their English 'non-native' teachers, and that their 'non-native' teachers seem to over-emphasise the importance of passing exams and over-correct their grammar mistakes. Instead, students believe that their English 'native' teachers are able to develop their skills of critical thinking and understanding of English language in the classroom.

All above is central to the focus of this study. Clearly, there is a gap in the literature; this study aims to fill it by discussing the issues around two different groups of Chinese university students: English major and non-English major students, and providing a comparison of their perceptions of English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers. The researcher will develop these conclusions from previous studies.

2.5 Intercultural Language Teaching in Chinese Colleges and Universities

Since the publication of the Requirements by the Ministry of Education (2003) to develop intercultural English teaching in China, more teachers from English-speaking countries were employed at Colleges and Universities with the purpose of strengthening intercultural education. In addition, textbooks for communicative learning were updated to focus on culture; course equipment and facilities were

provided to play English film clips and videos to students as examples of cultural input (Liu & Zhang & Yin, 2014).

However, from the perspective of intercultural language education, it seems that it was challenging to achieve this in practice in the Chinese context as some teachers had no clear understanding of what intercultural competence was and may have misinterpreted the meaning of it to their students. Therefore, problems occurred during the process of integrating culture into English language teaching and these needed to be recognised and overcome (Li, 2016).

English language teachers at Chinese universities were qualified in English language teaching which focuses on linguistic knowledge. However, most teachers did not develop cultural awareness as they had not received cultural training or education. Intercultural teaching for those teachers was teaching through the textbooks, and when there were notes about cultural knowledge in the textbook, they would refer students to that to encourage them to recognise cultural differences. This seems far from the aim of cultivating intercultural education (Zhang, 2007).

In addition, students who had high English proficiency were found to be more willing to communicate with English 'native speakers'. In other words, students' engagement and motivation towards intercultural communicative learning might influence their attitudes towards the English language culture and cooperation with English 'native speaker' teachers (Chen, 2001). Therefore, how to develop the knowledge and an understanding of intercultural competence in English language teachers at Chinese universities, as well as to motivate students to explore cultural differences and knowledge were additional challenges to overcome during the reform of English education in China. It is from this context that this study aims to develop an understanding of the experience of English language learning of these two groups of Chinese university students, as well as their awareness of the importance of the place of intercultural teaching in the English language classes in the Chinese context.

2.6 Conclusion

This chapter has introduced the educational background, challenges and improvements initiated by the process of developing English language education at higher educational

levels in China, and discussed the Chinese students' perceptions of both English 'native' and 'non-native teachers, and the situation of intercultural teaching in Chinese University context. This study notes that English major and non-English major students receive different levels of English education after entering Chinese universities. A discussion of previous studies focusing on the motivation of English learning of English major and non-English major students in China will be introduced in the next chapter. In addition, in relation to the development of intercultural communicative skills of Chinese students, more teachers from English-speaking countries were employed in Chinese universities. However, students who had high English proficiency were more willing to communicate with English 'native-speaker' teachers, while, students who had lower English proficiency appeared not to engage actively in classroom activities or to have an interest in exploring cultural differences and knowledge. Moreover, most English language teachers at Chinese universities merely had cultural awareness and training about intercultural teaching. They still needed training to integrate culture into language teaching. Therefore, in order to illustrate the main focus of this study, the circumstances of intercultural competence teaching in English classes in the Chinese context, and Chinese university students' perceptions of how their English teachers develop their motivation and intercultural competence in the classroom will be discussed in the literature review chapter.

Chapter 3: Literature Review

3.1 Introduction

The topic of this thesis is English major and non-English major students' perceptions of the development of their motivation and intercultural competence of their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers in the classroom at a Chinese university. This study is related to the following scope of literature: Native Speakerism, English as a global language, Language Identity, Language learning motivation, Intercultural Competence, Culture and teaching cultural knowledge which will be discussed in this chapter.

The general findings of this literature review are listed as follows: the English language is used in various areas as a global language in China, especially in high school and university curriculums (Crystal, 1997; Kachru, 1992; Quirk, 1985; Harumi, 2002; Taylor 2002). Supported by Chinese national foreign language policy (Chang, 2006), English departments at Chinese universities were set up for English major students to learn the English language to support the development of international economy and trade in China which has caused the increasing requirement for English 'native' teachers at higher education institutions (Zhang, 2008). However, in China, people's general perceptions of 'native speaker' teachers are limited to teachers who are white and from inner-circle English-speaking countries (Fairclough, 1993). This will be discussed fully within this chapter. However, In the Chinese context of this study, students have begun to understand the value of a variety of the English language and the state of English as a global language, and have displayed willingness to be taught via Chinese English from their English language teachers rather than just the English language from its 'native' speakers (He & Zhang, 2010).

However, there is a continuing debate in the research field around English 'native' teachers who were welcomed to China and who were considered better to teach the English language by the government than 'non-native' teachers. Previous research shows that 'non-native' teachers received more positive comments than English 'native' teachers from Chinese students (Liang, 2002; Mahboob, 2004; Ling & Braine, 2007). Therefore, as a result of the discussion in this study around the influence of English as a global language in China, as well as the discussion around what English 'native' and

'non-native' teachers bring to the English language classrooms and their students, the researcher aims to explore Chinese university students' perceptions of their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers and how their teachers develop their motivation to learn the English language and intercultural competence in the classroom to support them to develop their skills and understanding of the English language.

In addition, L2 motivation, which is central to the learning process of Chinese university students connected with this study, is divided into two main types for the purposes of this study: instrumental motivation and integrative motivation (Gardner, 1985 & 2007). These frameworks of motivation were selected for this study because their theories are directly related to students' motivation to learn the English language in the Chinese context, as instrumental motivation usually reflects Chinese cultural and educational traditions (Zhang et al., 2013). Gao et al. (2007) and Taguchi et al. (2009) have noted that Chinese students are found to have a high level of instrumental motivation to learn the English language for a dominant exam-oriented purpose, or to reach their parents', and the Chinese society's expectations. Kim (2009) stated that L2 motivation considers the outcome of learning in relation to the target language. In addition, Dornyei (2011) asserted that integrative motivation has played a rapidly diminishing role in the L2 motivation research field. One interpretation of this might be that teachers are now more cautious when they encourage students from another culture to 'integrate to' the target language culture, as this expectation might be considered as a 'racist' manner to their students. Currently, even though students might wish to accept and integrate to parts of the target language culture while maintaining their own culture, it is suggested that language teachers should not assume language learners should have to integrate to the target language culture. In fact, that might be the reason why there are less studies focusing on integrative motivation (Dornyei, 2011). In the Chinese context, university students are found to be more instrumentally motivated rather than integratively motivated to learn English as they desire to find a better job with high English competency rather than exploring their understanding of the culture behind the English language (Murph, 2007; Liu, 2007; Dornyei & You, 2014).

In addition, there is limited research around the separate but related issue of 'identity change' within many Chinese people when they become English language learners in the Chinese context. The reason might be that English language learners in China are

less motivated to develop their understanding of the target language culture, as most of them are learning English to pass the exams and to gain qualifications rather than being aware of 'identity change' in themselves as they become English language learners at Chinese universities. This study aims to explore Chinese university students' motivation to learn English, in order to examine whether the participants more instrumentally motivated to learn English, as well as to find out whether and in what ways English major and non-English major students are differ in their motivation to learn English at a Chinese university.

The related theory underpinning this thesis is intercultural competence theory, which is defined as the ability of the individual to adapt knowledge, attitudes and behaviours in order to be open and flexible to other cultures (Byram, 2002). In the Chinese context, intercultural competence is found to be hardly addressed in English classes as some Chinese teachers seem not to have a clear understanding of the importance of acquiring intercultural skills, and awareness to develop their understanding of the target language culture (Song, 2008; Han, 2011). However, second language learning motivation is found to be related to the intercultural competence developed in the classroom (Alred, 2003), as language learning motivation is considered as one of the psychological factors which serves as a reference for understanding an individual's intercultural development. Therefore, in order to understand the development of intercultural competence by English language teachers in Chinese universities, and its relation to students' motivation to learn English, this study aims to discover students' perceptions of how their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom, and whether it will affect motivation to learn the English language.

3.2 Native-Speakerism

It is interesting to discover how Chinese students perceive the English language education as delivered by both English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers as there are, currently, increasing number of English 'native' teachers teaching English in China (Wright & Zheng, 2017). However, in the Chinese context, the definition of English 'native' speakers is found to be those who are white and from inner-circle countries (Ruecker & Ives, 2015). Therefore, 'native-speakerism' is addressed in this study in

order to expand the readers' understanding of who are considered to be English 'native' speakers in China, as the term 'native-speaker' is discussed and referred to within this context in this study.

3.2.1 'Native' Speakers

In the Chinese context, most Chinese students believe that English 'native' teachers are able to teach English language better than 'non-native teachers as they expect to be taught 'standard' English in their English classes. In other words, 'standard' English here can be considered to be American or British English, and students assume that English 'native' teachers who are born in what are perceived as 'leading English-speaking countries' have the best abilities to teach English (Quirk, 1990 & Medgyes, 1994). This is the fact that this study explores English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers instead of English language teachers in general in the Chinese context. However, some students have found that they may feel uneasiness and lack confidence when they are taught by their English 'native' teachers in English classes, because the teaching methods of 'native' teachers are different from what they have experienced by local teachers, even though they believe that English 'native' teachers hold the power of 'standard English' (Wu & Ke, 2009). In addition, as Chinese students have started to understand the nature of globalisation in relation to the English language teaching, they realised and understood the variety within the English language: that is, rather than only American and British English, they started to display more willingness to accept Chinese English rather than 'native' English as a viable form of the English language in the university classroom (He & Zhang, 2010). This is related to one of the aims of this study, as the researcher aims to explore whether Chinese university students prefer the English language education delivered by English 'non-native' teachers rather than English 'native' teachers.

The term 'native' speaker was defined by Kachru and Nelson (1996) as someone who has learned English in a natural setting as a first language since he or she was born as an English 'native' speaker. In addition, Holliday (2006:385) stated that 'English 'native' teachers represent a 'Western culture' from which spring the ideals both of the English language and of English language teaching methodology'. However, in the East-Asian context, people's perceptions of English 'native speakers' seem quite narrow and

conservative (Kusaka, 2013). In Japan, the majority of people recognise and accept the term 'native speaker' as a white person whose first language is English from the US or UK. In addition, in English language education settings in Japan, a 'native speaker' teacher is regarded as a linguistic icon who is available to serve the goal and means of English language teaching (Kusaka, 2013). In China, Wu (2009) conducted a survey about how Taiwanese students and parents define the English 'native speaker' and found that Taiwanese students and parents used to define and recognize English 'native' speakers to be someone who is white and from the US or UK. China is now more engaged with the rest of the world by the process of globalisation, so that people in China are changing their impression and widening their acceptance of English 'native speakers' rather than just recognising white American or British people as 'native speakers' (Jin, 2005).

3.2.2 The Debate around 'native' and 'non-native' teachers

However, there is a debate about whether 'native' speakers are ideal teachers for English language teaching. The belief that a 'native' speaker is the ideal English language teacher resulted in the widely held assumption that English 'native-speaking' teachers are better than 'non-native' teachers in teaching English language (Braine, 2005). Mahboob (2010:2) defined a 'non-native' teacher as someone who 'takes language as a functional entity where successful use of language in context determines the proficiency of the speaker and where the English language reflects and construes different cultural perspectives and realities in different settings'. In other words, a 'non-native' teacher's language proficiency appears to be bound by the context in which they learnt and developed the language. Therefore, within this context they develop their understanding of the target language with their own cultural perspectives, and develop their awareness and understanding of the target language as used in educational settings. Braine (1998) pointed out that in a job market, the qualifications, ability and experience of 'non-native' English language teachers seem to be considered invisible as many English-language teaching departments do not hire 'non-native' English teachers. 'Non-native' English language teachers who obtained high degrees and teaching qualifications in English-speaking countries still find it difficult to find a proper job or position after they have returned to their own countries (Braine, 2005). At the same

time, some English language departments appear to prefer unqualified 'native-speaker' teachers rather than qualified 'non-native' English teachers for teaching positions (ibid).

In Chinese and Korean recruitment websites, the definition of English 'native' speakers is limited to those who are white and from English-speaking countries. In addition, the recruitment websites require 'native speaker' teachers to produce passports from a list of predominantly White, so-called 'inner-circle' countries (Ruecker & Ives, 2015). Due to the high demand for English 'native speaker' teachers, recruitment websites work hard to catch prospective teachers' attention with clever slogans and images, and light-hearted videos that promise an exciting adventure for any English 'native' speaker to start a new journey instead of listing requirements of teaching qualifications (Fairclough, 1993). The employers appear to concentrate on expanding their business through recruiting and attracting people who appear to be not fully committed 'native' speakers rather than encouraging interest in their profession for its academic value.

Indeed, the item 'native-speakerism' can be considered neo-racist. First, race is implicit in the cultural othering of 'non-native' speakers; apart from Western cultures, any description and definition of 'other cultures' and assumptions of people whose first language is not English, and this is in fact done in a racist manner (Holliday, 2017). In addition, the discriminatory employment between English 'native' and 'non-native' speakers exists at nearly all types of language teaching institutions, and their 'customers' and students commonly show a mistaken preference for 'native speaker' based on their race and colour of skin (Lengeling & Mora Pablo, 2012). At the same time, English teachers whose colour of skin is not white but have spoken English from birth are categorized as 'non-native speakers' (Holliday, 2017). In the Chinese context, the situation is similar. Sung (2011) analyzed advertisements for recruiting English 'native' teachers, and found that white 'native' speakers of English are considered preferable for the job of English language teachers. In other words, not only is a 'native' background considered as a necessary criterion, but also race is more implicated in what makes an ideal English language teacher in Chinese employers' minds. Even though the candidates are born in what are considered to be 'leading' English-speaking countries, if their race is not white, they might not be fairly considered for the required job position as white 'native' speakers.

However, as Rampton (1990) argued, how you use one language is totally different from how you teach it, and English proficiency should depend on 'what you know' instead of 'who you are'. That is, English language teachers should be valued by their language proficiency, their ability and their knowledge of teaching methodology rather than the colour of their skin. As Nunan (2003:610) asserted, 'If English is a necessity, steps should be taken to ensure that teachers are adequately trained in language teaching methodology appropriate to a range of learner ages and stages, that teachers' own language skills are significantly enhanced, that classroom realities meet curricular rhetoric, and that students have sufficient exposure to English in instructional context'. In other words, a teacher's ability should be much more important than the colour of his or her skin. This is clear from Briane & Cheung's (2007) research, in which the teaching skills of English 'non-native' teachers are endorsed by Chinese university students as they think 'non-native' teachers do not only have the ability to use students' first language in teaching, but also have effective pedagogical skills to prepare teaching materials according to students' need.

The issue of 'native-speakerism' has resulted in 'low confidence and self-perceived challenges to professional competence' and 'self-perceived prejudice based on ethnicity or non-native status' for 'non-native' English teachers (Kamhi-Stein, 2000). Kim's (2011) interviews revealed that English 'non-native' graduate students from American universities believe they were not able to acquire perfect professional English, and their accented English might not be accepted as standard English as English is now a global language. However, the low confidence of 'non-native' teachers does not equal low teaching abilities and methodology. As Medgyes (2001) stated, 'non-native' English teachers are able to provide better learner models, and easily anticipate their students' difficulties during language learning. In addition, they have the ability to be more sensitive to understand students' needs by using the same first language as them. In the Chinese context of this study, China has proposed 'Chinese English' as a potential variety of English alongside British and American English. It follows that Chinese local teachers would have better abilities to teach 'Chinese English' based on their needs than English 'native speaker' teachers (Jin, 2005). In this study, Chinese university students' own perceptions of the development of intercultural competence of their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers as a direct outcome of the developing global status of

English language in China will be explored and discussed in order to add to the literature on this subject.

3.3 English as a Global Language

While English has been recognized as a global language in different contexts in the world (Crystal, 1997), it is important to explore how English language learners perceive the status of English in the field of education within which they are learning. In the context of globalization of English in China, which has the largest English learning population in the world, the emphasis on learning English continues at present (Taylor, 2002). Therefore, an investigation into Chinese learners' motivation to learn the English language, and their perceptions of how their English teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom to prepare them for interacting with people from different parts of the world through English in the global marketplace, seems to be of the utmost importance in the area of English language education in China.

3.3.1 English as a Global Language

According to Crystal (1997), when a language develops a special role in every country being recognised as an official language or a foreign language, then this language can be regarded as a global language. In addition, Quirk et al. (1985) claimed four criteria for assessing the globalisation of a language which are: The number of speakers: English is in the second position of globally the amount of speakers as there are more people in the world speak Chinese; Geographical dispersal: over one third of population in the world live in countries where English is regarded as native language or official language; The range of purposes for which the language is used: English is the dominant language of the science and technology area in the world. In addition, in terms of Economic and political power held by 'native' speakers of the language: English has the dominant position of the world as the language of the United States. As the English language has occupied three out of the four criteria stated by Quirk et al (1985), and the English language enables people to connect with others from different linguistic communities (Behera & Panda, 2012), English can be, therefore regarded as a global language.

English has been spreading fast all over the world (Hasman, 2000). While Navarro (1997) stated that the usage of the English language exceeded other languages such as Dutch, Japanese and Hindi, by 2009, Guilherme (2009) carried out a study for the British Council in his research about the amount of people who speak English in 28 different countries including the countries whose national language is not English; the result showed that nearly 90 percent of participants speak the English language; among people from Japan and Bangladesh who did not speak English, the level of English was still well developed. In addition, Crystal (1997) stated that there were one in three of the population in the world who are capable of communicating English at a useful level. Moreover, according to Kingsley (2008), nearly 20 percent of people from the countries where English is not regarded as the first language can speak English fluently. With the increasing number of 'non-native' speakers of English in the world, the ownership of English has shifted and new World English such as 'China English' has emerged (Caine, 2008).

Crystal (1997) stated that English plays a special role not only in English-speaking countries such as the USA, Britain, Canada and Australia, but also in the countries where English is regarded as an official language or the primary medium of communication such as Nigeria, Singapore and India. There are over 100 countries that consider English as a chief foreign language such as Europe, Asia and North Africa.

Kachru (1992) explained that there are three concentric circles in the English-speaking world: the Inner Circle contains the countries where English language is regarded as first language such as USA, UK, Canada and Australia; the Outer Circle contains the communities where English is regarded officially as an additional language such as India, Malaysia, Philippines and Sri Lanka; in addition, the Expanding Circle includes the countries where English is considered as a primary foreign language such as China, Korea, Indonesia and Nepal. This accords with Qu (2005) and Gao et al (2007) who note that, in the current Chinese context, English is considered as a foreign language rather than a second language.

For the countries where English is not considered as first language, Quirk et al. (1985) distinguished five types of functions to define the second language position of the English language: Instrumental- for formal education; Regulative- for government

administration and the law courts; Communicative- for interpersonal communication between individuals whose local languages are different; Occupational- for commerce, science and technology internationally; Creative- for nontechnical writing such as fiction, novels. In the Chinese context, the English language is commonly used in international business, developing science and technology with other countries; in addition, it is taught from primary school to higher education in China. In this way, the English language is widely used in China, however, it seems not to be able to concentrate on all the five functions to confirm its second language position discussed by Quirk et al. (1985). No doubt, this discussion of whether the use of English language in China is regarded as a foreign language or a second language will continue to be discussed as China develops, and the use of English language in context also develops in China.

Previously, according to Harumi (2002), 'Today's English is no longer an inviolable property of English-speaking people. It is becoming a common property of different people around the world'; and Harumi (2002) predicted that the population of people whose second language is English will be 1.5 times larger than the population of English 'native' speakers. In addition, the increase in the number of 'non-native' speakers of the English language has not only prompted communication and interaction between people from different linguistic communities, but also developed education in the ELF setting (Graddol, 2005). Moreover, Smith (1981) earlier considered that there is no need for people who desire to improve their English proficiency level to be more like 'native' speakers because there will be various types of English in the future. In other words, 'non-native' speakers of the English language tend to focus more on the efficiency of their language learning process rather than the acquisition of 'nativelike' correctness (Jenkins, 2007). Crystal (1997) noted that a language cannot be given a global status only if it is spoken by its 'native' speakers. However, English in the 21st century is no longer the language of few English-speaking countries which is limited to standard American or British accents; it is regarded as a global language spoken in other non-English speaking countries (Hung, 2002). Therefore, in the next section, this study will discuss how the global status of the English language affects English language education in the Chinese context.

Toolan (1997) predicted that what will happen to English in the future as a global language is that there will be multiple dialects and accents of spoken English as the wider spread of English; this language will be indigenized in different areas with specific vocabulary, and pronunciation. In addition, English speakers from all over the world will be constantly in contact with each other by modern media and international tourism because of the globalisation of the English language (Hung, 2002). However, Pennycook (1995) considered that the wide spread of global English might bring colonialism and cultural control to some countries, for example, young people from non-English speaking countries might be enthusiastic to learn Western cultures and speak English instead of developing their own cultural identity. Previously, according to Le Page and Tabouret-Keller (1985), the usage of global English should not lead to the loss of identities of English speakers whose first language is not English as they use English as a fundamental instrument to communicate with others to introduce their own culture. In other words, the existence of languages is bound up with identity.

However, Graddol (2006) considered that what will happen to global English in the future is outlined in the following three main points: first, the standard English accent is no longer needed as English is widely used as a global language by speakers who are able to signal their nationality and other aspects of their identity through English; the English language is used as a basic skill for 'non-native' English speakers which in turn can lead to the result that failure to master English means failure in other disciplines, because English language as a 'lingua franca' is used in many textbooks and classroom discussions; in addition, there might be a growing demand for English 'non-native' speakers to learn other foreign languages as they have developed their English language proficiency, and English language would no longer be a 'foreign language' to them. Graddol (2006) noted that English language teachers with sufficient English proficiency will be needed in the field of English language education, for example, English 'native-speaker' teachers with mature teaching skills and teaching experience, and bilingual teachers who can offer specific skills such as translation and interpreting to English 'non-native' students. It is interesting that this earlier discussion around English 'native' and 'non-native' speakers in language educational settings continues to be discussed today.

3.3.2 English as a Global Language in China

The globalisation of English language has connected different cultures in the world, as the English language no longer only belongs to their 'native' speakers, it is used as a tool for English language speakers all over the world to communicate and share information (Warschauer, 2000). In addition, the globalisation of the English language also has a deep influence in China, where English as a foreign language is not only widely taught in higher education, but also in secondary and elementary schools (Du, 2001). In terms of the number of learners of foreign languages in China, the English language is the most popular foreign language among Chinese learners, and it is set to remain the first foreign language in China in the foreseeable future (Wen, Su & Jian, 2011).

In the Chinese context, the spread of English has reached over 200 million students learning English in school and nearly 13 million young people at university in China (Taylor, 2002). Pan (2011) conducted research about Chinese teachers' and students' beliefs of English as a global language at Chinese universities through 48 questionnaires and interviews; the results showed that there were over 60 percent of Chinese students and teachers who recognized the global state of the English language as they considered English language is more 'global' than other languages in China; in addition, English can be used as a necessary instrument to develop international business and economy in China. Moreover, Nunan (2003) researched the status of English language education in China and found that the medium of English has been used as the main language for Chinese teachers to teach many courses in more and more Chinese universities such as information technology, finance, economics and law; in addition, with the increasing demand of learning English language in China, English language education is not only offered in schools and universities, but also is emerging as a private business in some large cities in China. The high demand for English 'native teachers' in private institutions has provided more job opportunities for those English language teachers from English-speaking countries to teach in China.

However, even though English is considered as the most popular foreign language which is taught across the sectors of education in China, Chinese learners still have a low frequency of usage of English language. In other words, they seem not to have opportunities to use the English language in authentic contexts. The reason might be that English has no official status in Mainland China, and English language is hardly used in Chinese learners' daily lives (Wei & Su, 2012). The main domain of the use of

English language is education (Bolton & Graddol, 2012). In other words, English is still a foreign language for most Chinese learners, as the use of English language is restricted to a small scale in other aspects of their daily lives apart from English language education. Therefore, this study aims to explore Chinese English learners, their perceived motivation to learn English language at a Chinese university, and whether they require more practice and support in developing English language outside their classrooms. In addition, the researcher aims to explore, influenced by the globalisation of English, how the related area of these Chinese students' perceptions of their English language teachers' development of intercultural competence in the classroom to help them improve their understanding of the English language in the Chinese context.

In the last two decades, influenced by global and national changes, Chinese students from higher educational institutions, especially English major students, are guaranteed they will be offered English language training by English departments at Chinese universities. The reason is that the Chinese government believes that the education of English major students plays a crucial role for the country as it helps China to maintain its contact with other countries, as well as helping China to prepare for the challenges from globalisation. In addition, supported by national foreign language policy, China has been enjoying a period of development against the background of accelerating globalisation and the rise of English as a global language (Chang, 2006). However, as English-major education is developed in China, the ways in which another group of students, non-English major students at Chinese universities, and their perceptions of their own developing English language related to the development of English as a global language in China should also be explored in this research field hence the impetus for this study.

3.4 Identity

The concept of language identity is explored and discussed in this chapter, as it is considered to be related to language motivation which is one of the main areas for research of this study (Dornyei, 2009). According to Lamb (2004), the motivation to learn the English language is shaped when individuals recognize their identity as English language learners. In the Chinese context, the researcher believes it is necessary to discuss how Chinese learners perceive themselves as English language learners, as it

is relevant to their relationships with the target language, and their perceptions of the motivation to learn the language; hence the impetus for this study.

3.4.1 Identity

According to Danielewics (2001:10), identity refers to 'our understanding of who we are and who we think other people are'. Norton (1997) stated the definition of 'identity', in different pieces of research and sources, refers to how people consider their relationship to the world and their possibilities in the future, and also how people construct the relationship through time and space. In addition, Norton (1997) concluded that identity can be divided into two aspects: 'social identity' which refers to the relationship between the individual and the social world through families, schools and other social institutions; 'cultural identity' refers to the relationship between the individual and a specific group with a common history, language and similar thoughts of the world. Moreover, Block (2007) conceptualised identity as a dynamic process of self-identification on a constant basis in social interactions with other members of a particular community. In other words, individual's self-identity might be changed or expanded when they expose themselves to different social communities or different cultures.

In addition, when the issue of identity has been brought into focus with the development of social approaches in relation to the foreign language learning theory, learning a foreign language is considered to be a social phenomenon, rather than just a cognitive phenomenon (Klimanova & Dembovskaya, 2013). Foreign language learners are motivated by 'the desire and possibility of expanding the range of current identities and reaching for wider worlds' (Kannon & Norton, 2003:242) to learn the target language. In other words, foreign language learners' identities are associated with their motivation to explore different languages and cultures for social as well as educational purposes. In this study, the researcher aims to discover how Chinese university students perceive their motivation to learn the English language, and whether they are motivated by social purposes to use the English language as a tool to explore a wider world or just to pass English exams. Moreover, in the Chinese context, the issue of English language learners' identities as one of the impetus of this study will be considered in this research field.

3.4.2 L2 and FL Identity

In the related context of English language learning, L2 identity refers to the relationship between L2 learners and the world, and how they understand the culture of the target language they are studying, and how they relate themselves to the culture and natives of the target language (Norton, 2000). As Pennycook (2003: 58) stated, 'it is not that people use language varieties because of who they are, but rather that we perform who we are by using varieties of language'. In addition, Norton (2000) summarized that L2 identity is associated with language affiliation, language expertise, language inheritance, and the ability of L2 learners to approach a closer connection with the target language and culture. In this sense, Chinese language learners who are based in the UK might be considered as second language learners, as they appear to approach and have a closer connection with the target language culture because they immerse themselves in the target language culture while they learning the language. However, referring to Wei & Su (2012), in China, English is still a foreign language for most Chinese learners.

As a consequence of the extent of the English language, there is growing interest in considering whether national identities of English learners will be changed in the process of learning the English language (Gu, 2009). According to Joseph (2001)'s study, national or sub-national identities of English learners should not be eroded by the globalisation of English. In addition, Gu (2009) conducted a survey about how Chinese university students thought about their identities in relation to the spread of the English language; the findings showed that the participants appeared to have a strong sense of their national identity as Chinese rather than expanding their identity as English language learners; they regarded English proficiency as a tool to interact with other countries to create a good national image of their own country, instead of having a closer connection with the target language culture.

Qu (2005) considered that it was far-fetched to discuss the issue of 'identity change' in the Chinese context as there is a lack of intercultural communication being taught in the classroom, and most Chinese students were motivated by instrumental purposes (such as passing the exam, graduating from university) to learn the English language. Therefore, at this stage, English was taught as a 'foreign language' instead of a 'second language' in China. However, Gao et al.(2015) stated that in the environment of

globalisation, with the increased intercultural exchange in China, the development of L2 and FL identity of English language learners in EFL and ESL contexts cannot be ignored as the importance of English as a global language has been greatly enriched. Even though the boundary between second language and foreign language contexts is not disappearing, it is diminishing in China. The reason for this might be that Chinese language learners are developing their language not only within or outside the classroom, but also engaging through social media with first and second language speakers. In this way, they are involving themselves more with the language as well as the target language culture.

In addition, Gao et al. (2005) conducted a survey among Chinese university students about their self-identity changes as English language learners, and the findings showed that the self-identity of Chinese university students was scarcely changed because of the limited exposure to the target culture, and English language competence was the factor may affect most to identity change in the Chinese EFL and ESL context. In Chinese universities, English major students found that their self-identity changes through English language learning were higher than non-English major students as learning motivation and basic needs of English language were different from these two groups of students (Gao et al., 2005). Therefore, It relates to the aims of this study to explore the differences in these two groups of students' perceptions of their English language learning motivation, and to further understand to what extent Chinese university students are motivated to develop their foreign language skills as English language learners.

In the research field of foreign or second language learning, bilingualism is related to the issue of identity. Lambert (1975) proposed two types of bilingualism, which are 'subtractive' and 'additive' bilingualism. 'Subtractive' bilingualism refers to the language learners whose 'native' language and 'native' cultural identity are replaced by the target language and target cultural identity; in addition, 'additive' bilingualism refers to the language learners whose 'native' language and 'native' cultural identity are maintained while the target language and target cultural identity are acquired. 'Productive' bilingualism was proposed by Gao (2001) as an alternative term to 'subtractive' and 'addictive' bilingualism which refers to the command of the target language and the command of the 'native' language positively reinforce each other while the deeper

understanding of the target language and culture also brings deeper understanding of the 'native' culture to language learners.

Even though, in the current Chinese context, Chinese students do not consider themselves as bilinguals in both Chinese and English, Chinese university students have found that they have experienced moments or instances of 'productive' bilingualism while learning the English language (Gao et al., 2005). Chinese university students who have been supported to develop their understanding of the English language and culture through their English teachers associating it with a deeper understanding of their own language and culture. In this way, they have reached the state of 'productive' bilingualism as foreign language learners (Gao, 2001). In other words, this means that students are equipped to function not only in Chinese, but also in the English language for social and academic purposes.

Norton (2000) explained further that the identities of the Chinese bilingual participants are complex and always changing. This researcher examines, therefore, the self-awareness of perceived identity and differences between English learners from English major courses and non-English majors in Chinese universities who are the focus of this study.

Moreover, the issue around motivation to learn English is correlated with the individual's global identity or their national identity (Dornyei, 2009). Lamb (2004) explained earlier that changes in the motivation to learn the English language occurred during the process of reconstruction of identities, in other words, the motivation to learn English would be shaped when the individuals recognize their perceptions as English learners in the context of their learning within a Chinese university.

In the current Chinese context, where English is widely taught as a foreign language, students are developing themselves as foreign and second language learners. Therefore, it is essential for English language teachers to motivate their students to learn the English language and to develop their foreign language learner identities as English language learners. In addition, every area of the Chinese society has placed great pressure on the effectiveness of English teaching with the result that Chinese learners' English learning motivation tends to be more instrumental. As Gao (2007) noted, self-

identity change does not seem to be an issue in an English as a foreign language context where research on non-linguistic outcomes is limited. In addition, although English language education is widely promoted in China, there is still emphasis on Chinese language, culture and traditional values (Fang, 2018). The debate on the localised use of English as a second or foreign language in relation to the Chinese language will still continue (Wang, 2015; Yang & Zhang, 2015). In other words, most of the related research into Chinese learners has been at the language level. Thus, one of the reasons that the researcher engaged in this study is to focus on how their development of the target language influences their identities and their awareness of the target language culture.

3.5 L2 and FL Motivation

In the Chinese context, English is a compulsory subject for all university students. This English learning is mainly conducted in the classrooms, so the focus of the learning is not on authentic communication, as the English language is not typically used in students' daily interactions (Zhao, 2011). Hedge (2003) emphasizes that, in general, language learning motivation is related to students' classroom experiences but Chinese students' classroom learning experiences are mainly formal, focused on inauthentic language. However, Crookes & Schmidt (1991) found that English language teachers evaluate their students' motivation based on their engagement with their classroom teachers, instead of focusing on students' own specific motivations for language learning; there has been no previous study exploring Chinese students' motivation and their perceptions of their formal, inauthentic language learning. Therefore, this study aims to explore students' own perceptions of their motivation to learn the English language, and what support they would need to help them develop their English language skills.

According to Gardner (1985:10), L2 and FL motivation is defined as 'the extent to which the individual works or strives to learn the language because of a desire to do so and the satisfaction experienced in this study'. There are two types of motivation discussed in his study which are instrumental motivation and integrative motivation. Instrumental motivation refers to the aim of individuals to gain reward from something such as passing exams and getting a better job; Integrative motivation expresses the desire of

students to learn a foreign language to be more integrated into the target language culture (Gardner, 1985). In addition, Liu (2007) suggests that integrative motivation is the key component of Chinese students' language learning process (Liu, 2007). Therefore, as integrative motivation has played a rapidly diminishing role in L2 and FL motivation research, Dornyei & Ushioda (2011) suggested that researchers on motivation should include the concept of 'integrative motivation' in their research paradigms, even though Dornyei (2011) previously noted that language learners are less interested in integrating to the target language culture.

Kim (2009) further states that L2 and FL motivation is created when L2 and FL learners realize the importance of target language learning, and the outcome of learning this target language would connect with their life conditions; in other words, when they realize that learning a language is not only an exercise, but also it helps them to develop their understanding of other cultures which might connect or resonate with their own cultures. In addition, L2 and FL motivation is the integration of appropriate L2 and FL learning goals, and the participation in actual or imagined target language communities. Accordingly, motivated students would be more eager and enthusiastic to devote their time to language learning. Moreover, having a specific goal and desire to study a foreign language can help students make their best effort and maintain their motivation (Muftah & Rafik-Galea, 2013).

In Gardner's (1985) early research, a model called the Attitude/Motivation Test Battery (AMTB) was designed to measure the key components of motivation to learn a second or foreign language in which the three components of L2 and FL motivation include integrativeness, attitudes toward the learning situation and motivation. Integrativeness refers to the openness of the individuals to identify themselves with another language community which includes three scales: attitudes toward the target language group, integrative orientation and interest in foreign languages. Attitudes toward the learning situation refers to the association of the individuals with the language learning context which includes two scales: evaluation of the course and evaluation of the teacher; the third component Motivation refers to 'goal-directed behavior' (Heckhausen, 1991) which includes three scales: motivational intensity, desire to learn the target language and attitudes toward learning the target language. This can be seen in Chinese learners, and it will be interesting, in this study, to explore their motivation to learn the English

language and the relation between their motivation and their perceptions of their English language teachers. In addition, Gardner (1985) summarized these three components of L2 and FL learning motivation as a new concept: integrative motivation which refers to the individuals' desire to learn the target language, identify themselves openly with the group of another language community and develop favourable attitudes toward the second language learning. Cook (2001:114) reviewed Gardner and Lambert's theory of integrative motivation and stated that: 'integrative motivation reflects how the students identify themselves with the target language culture and people from the target language culture, the students who are more engaged to be involved in the target language culture appear to be more successful in second and foreign language learning'. In other words, the motivation of second and foreign language learning is related to students' attitudes and interest towards the target language culture. In addition, Parker and Riley (2005) argued that integrative motivation seems more important in second and foreign language learning than instrumental motivation as it would cause negative attitudes towards the students' learning process if external pressure such as examinations is the only reason for learning a second or foreign language. This helps to explain the way in which English language learning in China seems to be moving from English as a foreign language to English as a second language where there is much more involvement in the language learning process as English language is not only regarded as a tool for students to pass exams.

In addition, according to Deci & Ryan's (2000) theory, there are two types of motivation which are intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation originates from the enjoyment of achieving difficulties in the process of a particular academic task of individuals who desire the feeling of accomplishment; extrinsic motivation refers to the attitude and pressure of individuals toward the success or failure of an academic task. Students who are extrinsically motivated will perform mainly for the attainment of an external reward or to avoid punishment like passing exams. In foreign language learning settings, Muftah and Rafik-Galea's (2013) study confirmed the belief that students are instrumentally oriented to learn a foreign language when they have specific goals. However, this seems to be related to the discussion around foreign and second language learners who are learning the language not only to pass the exams or

achieve academic tasks, but also to immerse themselves in the target language culture, in order to understand and connect with the social communities behind the target language.

The L2 Motivational Self System was developed by Dornyei (2005) to research L2 learning motivation of foreign and second language learners. There are three principal components of the L2 Motivational Self System which are: the Ideal L2 Self: a self-image of the kind of L2 learners would ideally desire to become in the future; the Ought-to L2 Self: the individuals become an 'imported' self-image by believing themselves ought to possess to meet the expectations of others and to avoid any possible negative learning outcomes; the L2 Learning Experience: executive components of motivation which are related to the immediate learning experience or environment includes the class environments, the teaching quality of teachers or the classmates. The L2 Motivational Self System theory is discussed in order to inform this research because this theory has been used successfully in a piece of research around L2 and FL motivation of Chinese English learners by Taguchi (2009). It relates to the purpose of this study which aims to explore Chinese university students' motivation to learn the English language and its relation to their perceptions of their English teachers and how they integrate culture into their teaching in the classroom.

In addition, Gardner (2007) considered that second and foreign language learning motivation theory was more complex than the theory he discussed in his earlier study (Gardner, 1985). In the foreign and second language learning settings, there were two new types of L2 and FL motivation discussed in Gardner's (2007) study: language learning motivation and classroom learning motivation. Language learning motivation related to the general characteristics of the individuals which applied to any single opportunity to learn the target language; classroom motivation was obviously associated with the classroom context or specific situation; this kind of motivation was influenced by the following key factors: the teacher, the classroom atmosphere, teaching materials and facilities, the content of the language course, as well as the personal characteristics of individuals as students. In other words, the motivation of foreign and second language learners no longer only depends on themselves, it is also associated with language teaching materials and skills of their teachers. Therefore, in this study, the researcher aims to discover how Chinese university students perceive their

motivation to learn English language, and the association between their perceived motivation and their perceptions of how their English language teachers develop their English language skills and abilities of intercultural competence in the classroom.

According to Gao's (2004) large-scale survey about the motivation of learning English language of Chinese university students, the L2 and FL motivation of Chinese university students is classified in seven types: intrinsic interest, immediate achievement, learning situation, going abroad, social responsibility, individual development and information medium. Therefore, Chinese university students were not only driven by instrumental reasons to learn English language, as the participants perceived that they desired to connect with people and communities of the English language, and experience the target language culture (Gao, 2004). The researcher would like to discover in this study how Chinese university students perceive their motivation to learn the English language, and whether their motivation is related to these seven types in Gao's (2004) study. However, the research by Zeng & Murph (2007) showed that English language teachers in China found it was not easy to motivate Chinese students to learn English in the classroom as most of the teachers focus more on grammar teaching and language knowledge instead of developing students' communicative skills which causes a lack of English language communicative practice for Chinese students. Referring to Gardner's (2007) theory, foreign and second language learners' motivation is associated with the classroom atmosphere and teaching skills of their teachers. Therefore, as one of the impetuses of this study, the researcher aims to focus on students' own perceptions, in order to discover how students perceive their motivation to learn English language, and how they perceive the development of English language teaching by their teachers in the classroom.

In addition, Dornyei and You (2014) reviewed the situation of English language learners' motivation in China; the participants were Chinese secondary school and university students, and the sample size was 10413. The findings of their study showed that English language learners in China were primarily instrumentally or extrinsically motivated to learn English aiming to pass the exams, to graduate successfully from the university, and to acquire more opportunities for their future careers. In addition, English language learning motivation of Chinese university students, especially of English major students, was found to be in a direct association with the hopes of their

parents. In other words, these Chinese students learn English language to achieve higher scores in English exams, in order to satisfy their parents. Moreover, the findings also explained that as the globalisation of English language developed in China, English major students in Chinese universities learn English language to acquire more opportunities for their future career, in order to get a well-paid job to take care of their parents. In addition, You et al. (2014) researched English language learning motivation between English major and non-English major students in Chinese universities; findings showed that the English language learning motivation differs between English major students and non-English major students, as English major students acquire a more advanced level of English language education than non-English major students. Therefore, English major students are found to be more motivated to learn English than non-English major students, as they do not only learn English to pass exams, but also to understand the English language thoroughly. Therefore, in this study, the researcher will explore and examine whether English major and non-English major students differ in their motivation to learn the English language, and to what extent English major and non-English major students differ in their perceived motivation to learn English in a Chinese university.

Moreover, Liu (2007) investigated the English language learning motivation of Chinese university students, especially non-English major students in Xiamen University. The results of the research revealed that Chinese university students had positive attitudes towards the English language, and they were motivated to learn English. However, even though Chinese university students are found to be motivated to learn English, Dornyei and You (2014) found that Chinese university students were more instrumentally motivated rather than integratively motivated to learn English as they desired to find a better job with high English competency. Therefore, it seems that non-English major students were more instrumentally motivated because they had limited opportunities to have contact with English 'native' speakers and the target language culture. In addition, Liu (2007) found that the majority of the participants reported that they were demotivated to learn English after passing the CET 4 test, an essential condition for Chinese university students to graduate from their universities, as they had less pressure to learn English and limited contact with the target language. In other words, the majority of Chinese university students are less motivated to learn English language

after they pass the English exam or achieve their academic goals. Therefore, this researcher aims to explore the English language learning motivation of Chinese university students, in order to find out whether they are more instrumentally motivated to learn the English language, and how to support them to develop their English language skills by listening to and analysing students' suggestions.

3.6 Intercultural Competence

As a result of globalisation of the English language in China and in the world today, the increasing communication and interaction among people from different cultural backgrounds makes an awareness and understanding of intercultural competence very important in the field of English language education (Zhou, 2011). It is vital for English teachers to prepare Chinese university students with the skills of intercultural competence for their future careers in the global market. Therefore, this study aims to explore students' perceptions of the development of intercultural competence by their English teachers in the classroom, and the related literature is discussed below.

3.6.1 Intercultural Competence Theory

The English as a foreign language classroom in China has become an important place for the development not only of the English language, but also of the related intercultural competence as it has the possibility to enable English language learners to explore diverse language identities and cultures behind the language itself (Wu, 2019).

However, traditional language acquisition approaches for English language teacher training and education have focused more on linguistic competence such as English speaking, listening, reading and writing skills (Ohta, 2000). Therefore, the lack of ability of English language teachers to capture the complexity of the sociocultural perspectives of language learning has led to the result that intercultural enrichment is hardly addressed in the EFL setting in China (Piller, 2002).

However, the globalisation of the English language has made intercultural competence and intercultural communication increasingly important in English language education. Therefore, English language teacher training and education started to focus on improving English language teachers' cultural knowledge such as English literature,

history or customs (Wu, 2019). However, the generalised cultural knowledge these English language teachers have acquired has failed to enable them to achieve effective communication in real intercultural contexts. Interestingly, previously English language teachers were encouraged to explore cultural aspects in depth such as beliefs and values of the target language to foster intercultural competence in their English classes (Alatis et al., 1996). However, it might be the lack of training to support teachers to teach cultural knowledge in practice which may have resulted in their lack of ability to teach intercultural competence.

According to Taylor (1994), intercultural competence refers to a transformative process through which the individuals develop their adaptive capacity, that is, they adapt their perspectives to effectively understand and the demands of another culture. Byram (2002) also defined intercultural competence as the ability to change the individual's knowledge, attitudes and behaviours in order to be open and flexible to other cultures. In addition, Salo-Lee (2006) described the term 'intercultural competence' to refer to intercultural awareness, knowledge and skills; in other words, both theory and practice are needed for the performance of intercultural competence. In addition, according to Huang, Rayner and Zhang (2003), the individual who has the ability of intercultural competence is able to develop relationships with groups from different cultural backgrounds, and manage to solve complicated conflicts by crossing the barriers which were caused by cultural differences. Moreover, Spitzberg (2009) considered that due to the cultural diversity manifested in the global market, intercultural competence would become an extremely crucial skill in the future. Therefore, this is one of the reasons why this study was initiated as it is important to discover the place of intercultural competence and whether it supports both types of English language learners, that is, English major and non-English major students in the Chinese university.

According to the American Council (1996), a four-developmental-stage theory of global competence process was listed as follows: recognition of global systems and their interconnectedness including openness to other cultures, values and attitudes; intercultural skills and experiences; general knowledge of history and world events; detailed areas studies specialisation such as language learning.

In addition, Stier (2003) divided intercultural competence into two parts: content-competencies and processual competencies. Content-competencies refer to the 'knowing' which means the person has the ability to understand the knowledge of history, language, behaviour and other aspects of both his/her own culture and other cultures. Processual competencies refer to the interactional contexts in the process of intercultural competence which involves intrapersonal and interpersonal competencies. Intrapersonal competencies involve cognitive skills which refer to the ability to place oneself in the position of the other person from a different cultural background, to keep an open mind on cultural peculiarities without valuing another culture automatically. Another aspect of intrapersonal competencies is the development of emotional skills which refers to the ability of the individual to cope with diverse feelings triggered by unfamiliar cultural settings. Intrapersonal competencies refer to interactive skills which means the individuals are able to be aware of different interaction styles in diverse cultural groups and are capable of responding adequately to contextual meanings. This is related to the current context of this study where Chinese English language learners are engaging both in person and through social media with both first and second English language speakers, and this is one of the reasons why this study was conducted: to explore the students' perceptions of the development of intercultural competence by their English teachers in the classroom in the Chinese university, in order to prepare them to take their place in the world where English is regarded as a global language.

The proposed model of intercultural competence by Byram (1997) which underpins this study consists of five components: attitudes, knowledge, skills of discovery and interaction, and skills of interpreting and relating, the fifth component 'critical cultural awareness' is based on an educational setting. As the focus of this study is to explore both types of students, that is, English major and non-English major students, their perceptions of how their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom in the Chinese university. Each component of this model is explained below.

Attitudes are a feature of Intercultural competence, for example they refer to a speaker who is capable of exhibiting a 'readiness to suspend disbelief and judgement with respect to others' meanings, beliefs and behaviours and willingness to suspend belief in one's own meanings and behaviours, and to analyse them from the viewpoint of others

who has a different set of values, beliefs and behaviours' (Byram, 1997:34). The components of attitudes of learners on developing intercultural competence are as follows: a willingness to seek out interaction with the other in a relationship of equality; a genuine interest in the other's point of view on phenomena in one's own culture and in the other's culture; A readiness to interrogate the value systems and assumptions behind one's cultural practices; A readiness to examine one's own affective reactions to experience of otherness and to cope with these reactions; A readiness to engage with culturally appropriate verbal and non-verbal communication in the corresponding contexts (Byram, 1997:51).

The component 'relational knowledge' refers to the intercultural speaker who is not only capable of gathering information from the foreign culture, but also is able to connect this information with another fact from his/her own cultural background; in addition, such 'relational knowledge' entails the ability to provide critical commentaries on intercultural situations (Byram, 1997).

Byram (1997:38) defines the 'skills of discovery' as 'the ability to recognize significant phenomena in a foreign environment and to elicit their meanings and connotations, and their relationship to other phenomena'. In other words, it means the intercultural speakers are capable of coping with the unfamiliar issues occurring in the dialogues with little prior knowledge of other foreign cultures. In addition, the 'skills of interaction' are considered as the ability of intercultural speakers to operate their knowledge, skills and attitudes under the constraints of real time communication (Byram, 1997).

The skills of interpreting and relating are defined as 'the ability to interpret a document or event from another culture, to explain it and relate it to documents from one's own' (Byram, 1997; 52). In other words, the individuals are capable of sourcing documents or knowledge from other cultural backgrounds and relating it to his/her own culture in intercultural communications. Therefore, this theoretical framework is selected for this study as this model provides a clear definition of each component of intercultural competence theory, and it will assist the researcher to underpin and inform the construction of research questions and the participant interview questions.

3.6.2 Research around Intercultural Competence in English Language Education

In the Chinese context, Hao and Zhang (2009) researched the intercultural competence of Chinese college students; the findings revealed the fact that the participants were not capable of cultivating successfully intercultural awareness and they failed to respond appropriately during intercultural communication with English 'native' speakers, even though they had been learning English for more than 12 years. In addition, Griffiths (2011) conducted a survey about Chinese university students' intercultural competence in the university in Beijing: the findings showed that Chinese university students were not able to provide evidence of their skills of intercultural competence successfully, as they lack intercultural knowledge, and they are taught with grammar-focused teaching methods by their English language teachers. Therefore, as the previous studies revealed that Chinese students were not able to prove their skills of intercultural competence, the focus of this study is to examine the development of intercultural competence in the Chinese university. Thus, the researcher designed research methods to explore students' perceptions of how their teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom, in order to discover how students perceive whether and how knowledge of intercultural competence is taught, instead of examining their skills.

The level of ability of foreign language teachers' intercultural competence is regarded as an important role for their professional identities (Sercu, 2005). Foreign language teachers' ability in intercultural competence, and their degree of willingness to interculturalize foreign language teaching, are crucial to achieve successful foreign language teaching, and to promote students' acquisition of intercultural competence in the foreign language classroom (Han, 2011). When the students have acquired the skills of intercultural competence, they can be prepared to enter the global workplace.

Sercu (2005) conducted a research project about foreign language teachers' perceptions of their ability in intercultural competence in foreign language classrooms. It explored their perceptions of how their ability in intercultural competence can be used in their classroom practice to relate themselves to the expectations of foreign language teachers. The findings showed that there was no clear relationship between teachers' beliefs about their perceived ability of intercultural competence and how they shape it in their teaching practice. In addition, Sercu (2005) further suggested that foreign

language teachers are making an effort to become more familiar with intercultural competence, but they still lack the skills to teach it effectively, therefore they fail to meet their own expectations. Even though Sercu's (2005) study did not take place in the Chinese context, it guided this researcher to focus the design of this study to collect data from students' perceptions, rather than teachers' perceptions, as the teachers' perceptions of their own ability in intercultural competence was not relevant to their actual skills in delivering intercultural competence in the classroom (*ibid.*). Therefore, the researcher believes that examining students' perceptions would provide more reliable data for this study.

Aleksandrowicz (2003) interviewed English language teachers for their views of their ability in intercultural competence in English language classrooms in the European context. The findings revealed that only few English language teachers have been trained to deliver intercultural knowledge and develop intercultural competence in their classes in a systemic way; in addition, most of these English language teachers have realized the important role of integrating intercultural competence into their English language education, but they still lacked specific knowledge of intercultural competence and a clear understanding of how to develop intercultural competence in their English language classes.

In the Chinese context, English language teachers in China believe that developing English language learners' intercultural competence as well as their English language skills is important for English language education, but this idea hardly happens in their own teaching practice (Song, 2008). In addition, Song (2008) noted that although teaching intercultural competence is hardly addressed in the Chinese English teaching context, there are two official teaching guidelines for English language teachers in China to support them to develop intercultural competence in English language classrooms, which are The National Curriculum Guide for English Majors (2000), and The National Curriculum Requirements for the Teaching of College English (2004). Both of these official teaching policy guidelines have emphasized the importance of intercultural competence as a part of the foreign language teaching principles and teaching content.

Han (2011) interviewed 30 English language teachers in Chinese universities about how they conceptualize intercultural competence and relate it to their teaching practice. The

findings revealed that although many English language teachers in China could make a distinction between the intercultural approach and the communicative approach to English teaching, their knowledge of intercultural competence and its relevance to English language teaching were ambiguous. In other words, the intercultural dimension in their English language teaching needs to be enhanced. In addition, some English language teachers in China did not have a clear understanding of the importance of acquiring intercultural skills and teaching the target language culture in an integrated way. Moreover, the findings revealed that there was limited knowledge and teaching content related to intercultural issues in English language textbooks, and the English language teachers themselves lacked the knowledge of specific aspects of both the target language and cultural aspects which was reflected in the teaching materials. This awareness of the place of intercultural competence has helped the researcher devise not only the research questions, but also the interview questions for the participants in order to collect and analyse data for the study.

3.7 Culture and teaching cultural knowledge

Steely (1984) believes that the goal of foreign language teaching cannot be separated from the culture of the target language. In addition, relational knowledge of both foreign culture and the individual's own cultural background is considered as an important part of an ability in intercultural competence (Byrum, 1997). Therefore, literature related to the concept of 'culture' is discussed in this section, in order to provide a fuller understanding and discussion to inform this study.

According to Chastain's (1976: 388) 'large C' culture and 'small c' culture theory, 'Large C' culture refers to 'the major products and contributions of a society in general or of outstanding individuals in that society'; and 'small c' culture stands for 'the way people live'. Chastain (1976) considered that 'small c' culture should be emphasised at the early stage of foreign language learning, and 'large C' culture should be tackled when foreign language learners are at an advanced level of target language as the language learners may desire to explore depth of target language society and civilisation. According to Kramsch (1996:2), 'culture' has always referred to two ways of defining a social community: the first definition comes from the humanities which focuses on how a social group represents itself and others through material productions such as art,

literature, social institutions or artefacts; the second definition comes from the social sciences which focuses on the attitudes and beliefs, ways of thinking, behaving and remembering shared by members of that social community. This understanding of experience of culture has shaped this study and has led to the focus on the interview questions related to participants' beliefs, in order to get a clear understanding how they view English language learning and their English teachers' ability to teach intercultural competence.

Teaching knowledge of foreign language culture means not only breaking down stereotypes that lead us to realize people are not the way one thought they were, but also understanding everyone in the social community is unique and different (Kramsch, 1996). This statement is related to the focus of this study, which is an exploration of whether teaching intercultural competence in English language classes can link both home and target culture as well as respecting the differences between both cultures. Therefore, foreign language teachers are required not to deliver stereotyped and unhelpful cultural knowledge to their students in the classroom. According to Harumi (2002), a new framework of cultural teaching methods was developed to support language education which was divided into three key parts: culture around language, culture in language and culture through language. Culture around language emphasised customs and habits of the 'native' speakers of the target language should be discussed in the context of English language teaching; culture in language was regarded as a key component of language teaching which specifically focused on the lexical or grammatical items, and typically thought patterns of speakers of the target language. In other words, it is important for an English language learner to learn how 'native' speakers deliver their information with a close association to their target culture; culture through language refers to the importance of teaching a foreign language through both local cultural background and target cultural knowledge.

Subsequently, Harumi (2002) put forward four corresponding goals of culture teaching which are : culture teaching should be between language and culture; culture teaching should be between language teachers' own culture and foreign language culture; Culture teaching should be between oneself and the world; culture teaching should be between English language and other school subjects. These four goals of culture teaching aim to foster cross-curricular understanding of the target language culture

through local cultural background, the target language society, learners' own beliefs and other aspects of relevant knowledge. Moreover, Maynard (2002:1) stated a similar view that 'in cultural teaching, the focus is on the examination of the local discourse practices, the social ecology of development, and the material aspects of the environment that make cultural learning possible.' The analysis of this particular literature enabled the researcher to realize the importance of culture in foreign language teaching, and informed this study in helping the researcher to devise research and interview questions which will allow the data from the participants to be examined fully in this area.

However, it is interesting to explore the extent which teaching culture became the responsibility of foreign language teachers. As Kramsch (1996:3) noted, culture is always 'linguistically mediated membership into a discourse community which is both real and imagined'. In other words, language is a crucial part not only in the construction of culture, but also in the emergence of cultural change. The 'cultural change' does not mean any direct or immediate change, it can occur quite slowly as when foreign language teachers teach students how to use somebody else's linguistic code, and how to talk and behave in somebody else's cultural context. This is important in understanding how China is undergoing cultural change at the moment, and its impact on Chinese English language learners themselves. In addition, how they develop their understanding of both English and Chinese culture will help them to engage with other speakers of English language. Therefore, this researcher notes that it is important to explore the experience of the participants of this study, and whether they feel anything is missing from their English language education.

In addition, for foreign language learners, being taught the culture of target language is helpful to develop their intercultural (communicative) competence as well as to reach the space between cultures which is called the 'Third Space' (Kramsch, 1993). For example, the foreign language learning classroom can be seen as a 'Third Space' which enables students to discuss the similarities and difference between both cultures, and help the students to respect and understand both cultures by making comparisons and connections between two cultures. In this study, the term 'Third Space' (Kramsch, 1993) could also be regarded as the process of intercultural competence in English language classes. A consideration of how students reach the 'Third Space' will help the

researcher to devise the interview questions in this study to discover whether and how these English language teachers help their students to reach the 'Third Space' in English language learning, in order to analyse students' perceptions of how their English language teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom in the Chinese university.

In the Chinese context, Chen (1990) stated that English language teachers should make efforts to develop students' cultural capacity, not only to gain knowledge about the target language culture, but also to cultivate their English language competence in the interactions between the home culture and target language culture. In addition, Tang (1998) claimed the importance for English language teachers from Western countries of introducing values, beliefs and attitudes of English language cultures to Chinese students in the English language classes; in this way, Chinese students might be able to learn the language more effectively based on understanding of the social contexts for English language.

Moreover, Absalom (1996:6) previously commented on the types of blocks of intercultural communication between English 'native speaker' teachers and Chinese students which might occur, such as 'assumption of similarities, language differences, nonverbal habits and misinterpretations, preconceptions and stereotypes, tendencies to make value judgements and culture shock.' It explains that English 'native' teachers are required to acquire the skills of intercultural competence and understand both Chinese and English language culture, in order to teach English language effectively to Chinese students.

In order to help foreign language teachers to cope better with Chinese students, Tang (1998) suggested that foreign language teachers should attempt to design teaching approaches which would proceed slowly and cause minimal changes to authority structures in China, in order to guide Chinese students to understand the target language culture instead of criticism the students when any difficulties arise in foreign language teaching practice. In addition, foreign language teachers are required to gain knowledge of empathy with their students when they attempt to communicate with them. In the Chinese context, students tend to be polite to teachers which may cause their anxiety about asking questions. Therefore, in this circumstance, foreign language

teachers should understand and be sensitive when they direct questions to particular students while they introducing knowledge to their students on a specific topic which is related to culture. This issue has supported the researcher to understand that, in the Chinese context, it is important for foreign language teachers to develop intercultural competence and be aware of cultural differences, in order to improve the effectiveness of language teaching in the classroom. Therefore, it is interesting for the researcher to explore how Chinese university students perceive the development of intercultural competence by their English language teachers in the classroom in this study.

3.8 Relationship between English learning Motivation and Intercultural Competence

English is used as an international language which enables people in the global society to experience intercultural communication and interaction with English 'native' speakers and the target culture (Tsai, 2012). Intercultural learning can occur naturally in the EFL and ESL contexts, as intercultural competence developed by English language teachers in the classroom can affect students' English language acquisition (Wilkinson, 2002). In addition, motivation is considered as one of the psychological factors which serves as a reference for understanding an individual's intercultural development (Alred, 2003). In other words, English learning motivation is the factor that would reflect the effects of intercultural learning on English acquisition (Tsai, 2012). In previous studies, Gardner and Lambert (1972) argued that second language learners' understanding of other cultures and desire to communicate and interact with the 'native' speakers of the target language, which is defined as 'integrative motivation' in their theory, can be considered as the best basis for achievement in second language learning. In addition, Dornyei and Csizer (1998) further proved that competency in understanding a target language culture is importantly linked to a learner's language learning motivation.

In the EFL and ESL settings, such as in China, the context for this study, learners who are taught by English 'native' teachers have to improve their communicative skills to cope with unavoidable changes in a process of cultural negotiation with their English 'native' teachers (Corbett, 2003). On the other hand, by developing their intercultural communicative skills, learners may be motivated to learn more about the target

language and culture (Paige et al., 1999). In addition, Sia (2015) suggested that it is important to enhance the teaching experience of those English language teachers who are not from the same country as their students, by developing their understanding of local culture and traditions, in order to improve student learning outcomes. In other words, the teachers' skills in intercultural competence and awareness of cultural differences are related to students' learning outcomes and their motivation to learn the language. Byram (2008) considered that the assumption of a causal relationship between language learning motivation and understanding of and attitudes towards target language culture has been sparingly researched in this field. Therefore, in order to explore the relationship between intercultural competence and English learning motivation in the Chinese context, this study aims to discover English major and non-English major students' motivation to learn English, and to what extent they differ in their motivation to learn English and in their perceptions of how English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom.

3.9 Conclusion

To sum up, this chapter has presented a review of the relevant literature that explored a few main areas which are central to this study which are foreign language and second language learning motivation, in the context of English as a foreign language learning in China, intercultural competence and related theories regarding the definition and discussion of 'native' speakers, English as a global language, identity and cultural knowledge. In addition, this chapter explored the related purpose of this thesis to examine students' motivation to learn English and their perceptions' of how their English language teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom at one Chinese university, with the aim of providing a more complex understanding and exploration of the difference between two groups: English major and non-English major, through an examination of students' perceptions of how both their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom at the Chinese university.

This chapter next examines existing models and frameworks of intercultural competence. Specifically, despite its advantages in identifying individual's cognitive skills and emotional skills of intercultural competence, Stier's (2003) theory is

correspondingly weak in specifying the interaction during developing intercultural competence between teachers and students which is not suitable for the aim of this thesis. However, Byram's (1997) model, which contains five aspects: attitudes, knowledge, skills of discovery and interaction, skills of interpreting and relating, and critical cultural awareness, gives clear instructions for students to facilitate the development of intercultural competence during English class by English language teachers. Therefore, this model will be used as a main point for the analysis of this study regarding the participants' perceptions to their English teachers, as well as their understanding of intercultural competence in the university contexts.

With regard to English language education in China, and teaching English language at Chinese universities in particular, there is a lack of research on the difference between English major and non-English major students' perceptions of their English language teachers, and students' perceptions of intercultural competence of both English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers. Moreover, current studies and theories on the content of intercultural competence of English language teachers focus exclusively on how to examine teachers' abilities of intercultural competence, instead of analysing it from the students' perceptions. Thus, the existing literature does not provide a detailed picture of how English major and non-English major students' perceptions of intercultural competence of English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers at Chinese universities. Methodology used to support this study will be discussed in the following chapter.

Chapter 4: Methodology

4.1 Introduction

This chapter lays out the design of this study into English and non-English major students' perceptions of the development of their motivation and intercultural competence by their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers in the classroom in a Chinese university, including how the study was carried out and how to collect the data for this study. This chapter comprises the following sections: the discussion around the theoretical framework selected for this study; the development of the research design, data collection and analysis; the reflection of the whole research design by examining the reliability; transferability of this study and considering ethical issues; and finally, the position of the researcher in this study.

This chapter first will discuss the rationale for selecting Byram's (1997) intercultural competence model as the theoretical framework for this study, and the design of research questions and aims which are in relation to the current Chinese context and relevant literature. Then, the researcher will explain the reason why this study is a qualitative study by discussing and comparing different research paradigms. Moreover, the procedures of this study will be discussed in detail, which include the selection of data collecting tools and samples, and the procedures of participant recruitment. Finally, the ethical considerations and the debate around the researcher's positionality in this study will be discussed.

4.2 Theoretical Framework

4.2.1 Introduction

This section discusses the theoretical framework of this study. The theoretical framework is considered as the foundation for a research study which serves as the grounding for the literature review and research methodology, moreover, it provides the support for the rationale and purpose for the study, and it helps to form the research questions (Grant & Osanloo, 2014). It is suggested by Lederman (2015) that all research studies should have a valid theoretical framework to justify the importance and significance of the work. Thus, a theoretical framework is used to underpin this

study to help the researcher form the research questions which are relevant to the rationale and purpose for this study, and it enables the researcher to gather knowledge from related literature to support her to analyze the data in the findings. This section gives the rationale for selecting the intercultural competence model by Byram (1997) to explore Chinese students' perceptions of the development of intercultural competence by their English language teachers in the classroom. Moreover, two additional theories: Standard Cultural Tests and the intercultural competence theory by Chen and Starosta (1996) were discussed and compared to Byram's (1997) model; the reasons why they are not suitable for this study will also be discussed in this section.

4.2.2 Intercultural competence model by Byram

In order to evaluate an individual's ability of intercultural competence in the educational domain, Byram (1997:33-38) developed a model of intercultural competence which contains five dimensions: 'savoirs', 'savoir apprendre', 'savoir comprendre/faire', 'savoir eˆtre' and 'savoir s'engager'. In English, these five dimensions stand for knowledge, intercultural attitude, skill of discovery and interaction, skills of interpreting and relating, and critical cultural awareness.

Byram defines 'savoirs' as 'knowledge of social groups and their products and practices in one's own and in one's interlocutor's country, and the general processes of societal and individual interaction' (Byram, 1997: 58). Sercu (2004) suggested that 'savoirs' should contain culture-specific and cultural-general knowledge of both the home and foreign cultures, as well as the knowledge which is relevant to the ways how culture influences language and communication. 'Savoir apprendre' is known as 'the ability to interpret a document or event from another culture, to explain it and relate it to documents or events from one's own' (Byram, 1997:61). In addition, 'savoir comprendre/faire' is described as the 'skill of discovery and interaction: the ability to acquire new knowledge of a culture and cultural practices and the ability to operate knowledge, attitudes, and skills under the constraints of real-time communication and interaction' (Byram, 1997: 61). Moreover, 'Savoir s'engager' is defined as 'critical cultural awareness/political education: an ability to evaluate, critically and based on explicit criteria, perspectives, practices, and products in one's own and other cultures and countries' (Byram, 1997:63). Finally, 'savoir-eˆtre' is described as 'curiosity and

openness, readiness to suspend disbelief about other cultures and belief about one's own' (Byram, 1997:57).

4.2.3 Reason for choosing this model

The purpose of this study is to explore English and non-English students' perceptions of the development of intercultural competence by their 'native' and 'non-native' English teachers at one Chinese university, which is related clearly to the intercultural competence theory by Byram (1997). To answer the research questions of this study, a clear definition and understanding of intercultural competence should be related to the purpose of this study. However, according to Dervin (2006), there is no guarantee that the concept of interculturality is understood in the same way by language teachers and learners even though some language departments include teaching intercultural competence in their programmes. In other words, the development of intercultural competence in the foreign language classroom not only depends on how language teachers deliver the relevant knowledge but also depends on how students understand and develop it. Therefore, this study focus on students' perceptions of the development of intercultural competence of their English language teachers instead of examining the ability of intercultural competence of their English language teachers, in order to understand from the language learners' perspectives, how they are helped to develop intercultural competence and English language skills. Byram's (1997) intercultural competence model states a clear definition of his intercultural competence theory, it helps the researcher to form the related research questions for this study. Moreover, these five components of this model can be fully addressed in interviews to ask participants in which specific ways their English language teachers developed intercultural competence in the classroom in relation to 'Savoirs', 'Savoir apprendre', 'Savoir comprendre/faire', 'Savoir être' and 'Savoir s engager' in Byram's (1997) model. For example, in order to understand how students perceive the 'Savoirs' of their English language teachers, the researcher will ask the participants whether they think their English language teachers have knowledge of social groups and practices in their own and another country, and how they develop this in English classes; the researcher will ask the participants how they think their English language teachers have been able to interpret a document or event from Chinese culture and to explain it and relate it to documents or events from their own cultural background during the interviews, in

order to evaluate their English language teachers' 'Savoir apprendre' in Byram's (1997) model; to relate the interview questions to 'Savoir comprendre/faire' in Byram's (1997) model, the researcher will ask how the participants think their English language teachers' have been able to acquire new knowledge of a culture and cultural practices, and how their English language teachers introduce and discuss cultural knowledge in the English classes; to relate the interview questions to 'Savoir e`tre' in Byram's (1997) model, the participants will be asked whether they think their English language teachers are curious about other cultures as well as their own, and how they show their curiosity about Chinese or Western cultures in English classes; finally, to discover how participants perceive 'Savoir s engager' in their English language teachers, they will be asked whether they think their English language teachers are able to evaluate perspectives and practices critically from Chinese and English-speaking cultures, and how this is done in English classes.

Dervin (2006) suggests that the intercultural competence model by Byram (1997) could only be taken into consideration for the following domains: university contexts, contexts of student mobility, and professional contexts. This study took place in a Chinese university context in which five components of Byram's (1997) model can be clearly practised. In the current context, each of the five components is suitable for Chinese university setting: 'savoirs' refers to the English teachers' ability in expressing the national memory of their own country and explaining how its events are related to and seen from the perspective of other countries in English classes (Byram, 1997:59); 'savoir apprendre' refers to English teachers' ability to elicit from an interlocutor the concepts and values of documents or events and explain to students, as well as identifying contemporary and past relationships between one's own and the other culture and society (Byram, 1997:63); 'savoir comprendre/faire' refers to English teachers' ability to identify ethnocentric perspectives in the textbook or event and explain their origins to students, as well as identifying areas of misunderstanding and dysfunction in the interaction with students and explain to them in terms of both cultural systems (Byram, 1997:61); 'savoir e`tre' refers to English teachers' willingness to discover and discuss with students other perspectives on interpretation of familiar and unfamiliar phenomena in both cultures (Byram, 1997 :58); 'savoir s engager' refers to English teachers' ability to use a range of analytical approaches to

place a document or event in context while being aware of their own ideological perspectives and values (Byram, 1997:64).

To conclude, the intercultural competence model by Byram (1997) offers a clear explanation of how the intercultural competence theory can be related and practised in a university context. In addition, based on Risager's (2009:27) statement, this intercultural competence model by Byram (1997) covers three important aspects: knowledge, skills and attitudes. This model helps the researcher to analyse the finding from multiple angles; Byram's (1997) model emphasises the interpretation of texts and events as a crucial part of intercultural competence according to one of the components which is defined as 'savoir comprendre/faire', skills of interpreting and relating. In the Chinese university context, students receive knowledge of intercultural competence based on oral and textual information, via their English language teachers and textbooks in the classroom, as well as cultural events which are studied and discussed in the classroom as set out in the syllabus of the English language departments. In addition, cultural teaching in Chinese universities is often conducted in classrooms instead of offering students opportunities to make contact with people from English-speaking countries and their community which can result in limited opportunity for Chinese students to experience the cultural difference in a more informal, outside of a classroom intercultural context (Zhou, 2011). Byram's (1997) intercultural competence model not only provides a clear understanding of intercultural competence to participants for the purposes of the interviews for this study who might not be aware of intercultural knowledge within English classes, but it also proposes some teaching strategies for English language teachers to achieve intercultural competence in classes. Moreover, this model encourages English language teachers to discover and interact with Chinese cultures to provide more cultural knowledge to students. Therefore, it fills the gap in the literature around the development of intercultural competence with Chinese students between 'native' and 'non-native' English teachers; it is also in relation to the impetus of this study, that is, to encourage students and English language teachers to know and respect each other's cultures. Therefore, Byram's (1997) model has been selected for this study.

There are two alternative theories which are lead to assess intercultural competence in an educational setting. However, they have not been selected for this study after

consideration, and the reasons are listed as follows. First of all, Standard Cultural Tests (1995) are usually used to consist of multiple-choice questions to evaluate the ability of intercultural competence of teachers which suggests that they are easy to administer and correct (Hashem, 1995). However, cultural tests cannot provide evidence for someone's ability in intercultural competence by only testing generalized and stereotypical cultural knowledge (Dervin, 2006). This theory is not suitable for this study because of the following reasons: the purpose of this study is not to evaluate the ability in intercultural competence of teachers but students' perceptions of the development of intercultural competence by English language teachers in the classroom that cannot be measured by tests; in addition, this study is based on qualitative research methods, however, Standard Cultural tests are based on quantitative methods; there is no evidence that the use of this theory guarantees participants have a clear understanding of intercultural competence by only testing cultural knowledge. Therefore, this model by Hashem (1995) has not been selected for this study.

Another relevant theory of intercultural communication competence is provided by Chen and Starosta (1996) which is used to explore an individual's ability of intercultural competence focusing on three components: affective (intercultural sensitivity), cognitive (intercultural awareness), and behaviour (intercultural adroitness). Intercultural sensitivity refers to an 'active desire to motivate themselves to understand, appreciate and accept differences among cultures' (Chen & Starosta, 1998:231). Chen & Starosta (1998:9) defined intercultural awareness as 'the understanding of cultural conventions that affect how we think and behave'. The final component of this theory, intercultural adroitness, is described as 'the ability to get the job done and attain communication goals in intercultural interaction' (Chen & Starosta, 1996:307). This theory is based on qualitative methods and provides standards for effective interculturalists. However, the reason why this theory has not been selected for this study is that this theory is not based on an educational context; the components of intercultural competence given by this theory are not as clear as Byram's (1997), and therefore, this theory is not related effectively to this study. In addition, this theory focuses on how an individual can effectively perform as an interculturalist, instead of focusing on how participants perceive the development of intercultural competence by their language teacher which does not match the focus of this study. Thus, this theory is

not considered as suitable for the theoretical framework for this study. Therefore, Byram's (1997) intercultural competence model has been selected as the theoretical framework for this study after considering and discussing it with two other related theories. Moreover, Byram (2006) further elaborates on his intercultural competence theory as 'competences which enable them to mediate the values, beliefs and the cultures of themselves and others and to 'stand on the bridge' or indeed 'be the bridge' between people of different languages and cultures' (p.12). This ability of language teachers to understand and respect cultures of themselves and their students is considered as one of the important aims of intercultural language teaching (Council of Europe, 2001). Thus, this theory relates to the purpose of this study: to explore the development of intercultural competence between English language teachers and their students, in order to further consider how to develop intercultural language teaching in the Chinese context.

4.3 Research Methodology

4.3.1 Introduction

In order to answer the research questions in this study, it is important to investigate the research approaches and offer credible findings to other researchers which require the researcher to share her own views of what constitutes truth and knowledge (Chillisa & Kawulich, 2009). In this study, the reason for choosing this method for the current research, as well as the related research questions will be introduced in this chapter, and the research method will be based on the interpretive phenomenological theory put forward by Heidegger (1962). In addition, the method chosen for data collection for this study will be semi-structured in-depth interviews and focus group interviews based on qualitative research methodology. Samples will be described and purposively and equally selected from English major and non-English major Chinese university students, and the data analysis approach will be interpretive phenomenological analysis procedure by Allen et al (1989).

4.3.2 Research Questions and Aims

English has become recognized as a global language in most of the countries in the world (Crystal, 1997). Fishman (1996, P: 628) concluded that the condition of the globalization of English is:

‘The world of large scale commerce, industry, technology, and banking, like the world of certain human sciences and professions, is an international world and it is linguistically dominated by English almost everywhere, regardless of how well established and well-protected local cultures, languages, and identities may otherwise be’.

Due to the globalisation of English in China, the emphasis on learning the English language has continued until the current days, and China has become the country with the largest English learning population in the world. About 13 million Chinese students are learning English at universities in China (Taylor, 2002). According to Arrighi (2007), in the English language education field, it is important to explore Chinese learners’ perceptions of the status of the English language in China because of the globalization of the English language in China and the world today. In addition, how Chinese students as English learners view the state of English seems to be of utmost importance to English language teachers (Block & Pan, 2011). Therefore, as intercultural competence has developed within English language education, this research aims to explore Chinese university students’ perceptions of the development of their motivation and intercultural competence by their English language teachers in the classroom. Based on that, the research questions and aims are designed by the researcher which are listed as follows.

The research questions have been framed based on the research aims and objectives:

- In what ways do University students perceive intercultural competence and the role of their University teachers in contributing to its development in English classes at Chinese universities?
- To what extent is intercultural competence developed between English teachers (both ‘native’ and non ‘native’) and Chinese university students?

- In what ways do students think intercultural competence could be developed more effectively in English departments at Chinese universities?
- To what extent do English major and non-English major students differ in their motivation to learn English and in their perceptions of how their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom of their Chinese university?

The purpose of this study is to explore the English major and non-English major students' perceptions of the development of intercultural competence by 'native' and 'non-native' English teachers in the classroom at Chinese universities. For this purpose, the following aims to support the research questions are advanced:

- To examine and discover Chinese university students' perceptions of the intercultural competence of 'native' English-speaking teachers and 'non-native' English teachers in the Chinese university.
- To identify and explore how both 'native' and 'non-native' English teachers develop intercultural competence in English classes based on students' perceptions in the Chinese university.
- To explore in what ways students will be able to develop their understanding of intercultural competence based on students' perceptions in the Chinese university.
- To compare and discuss the difference in students' motivation to learn English and their perceptions of how their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom of their Chinese university.

4.4 Research Paradigm

Once the topic of the research has been designed, how to investigate the approach and to offer credible findings to other researchers plays a crucial role in a study. It requires the researcher to deliver truth and knowledge in the study (Chillisa & Kawulich, 2009). This idea which enabled the researcher to develop the way of thinking, assumptions about society and community is called paradigm (Schwandt, 2001). A paradigm is defined as 'a shared world view that represents the beliefs and values in a discipline and

that guides how problems are solved' (Schwandt, 2001). According to Patton (2002), a paradigm is regarded as a tool for describing a world view that is informed by philosophical assumptions and belief of nature of social reality, the ways of acquiring knowledge about the research and ethics and value systems. In addition, Fox (2013) described a research paradigm as an established model which is accepted by the majority of people in a research community.

There are three major types of educational research paradigms, which are quantitative research, qualitative research, and mixed research (Johnson & Christensen, 2012). In quantitative research, researchers focus on facts and causes of behaviours by analysing the numeric data in the mathematical process and the final result of the research which is summarized in statistical terminologies (Charles, 1995). In qualitative research, a naturalistic approach is used by researchers to understand a phenomenon that is based on different context-specific settings (Patton, 2002). Qualitative researchers focus on seeking understanding, and extrapolation to similar situations, instead of seeking determination, prediction, and generalization of findings in quantitative research approaches (Hoepfl, 1997).

In this study, the researcher aims to explore Chinese university students' perceptions of the development of intercultural competence by their English language teachers in the classroom in the Chinese context. In order to collect accurate and credible data, focus groups and semi-structured in-depth interviews are selected in this study as data collecting tools to gather and analyse textual information from the process of oral conversations and shared experience between the researcher and participants. In this circumstance, data collected for this research will be based on participants' perceptions and suggestions which cannot be easily measured and analysed by numeric data. Based on that, this present study selected qualitative research paradigms instead of quantitative or mixed research paradigms.

4.5 Epistemological and Ontological Stances

Research philosophy involves important assumptions such as epistemology and ontology, which are related to how researchers observe or view the social world. In addition, epistemology and ontology are significantly important in the research field as the process of selecting the research methods for this study is based on epistemology

and ontology stances (Bahari, 2010). Easterby-Smith et al. (2002) emphasized that the quality of the research will be seriously affected if the researcher fails to consider philosophical issues in his/her research.

This study aims to explore Chinese university students' perceptions of the development of their motivation and intercultural competence by English language teachers in the classroom. The data in the study will be collected from interpretive research methods such as interviews and focus groups, in order to understand students' opinions, experiences and inner thoughts. According to Ahmed (2008:2), researchers have to assume the world which they investigate is populated by human beings who have their own thoughts, interpretations and meanings. In order to explore participants' thoughts and perceptions, this study is designed based on interpretive research methods.

Ontology is defined as 'the study of being' which is concerned with 'what kind of world we are investigating, with the nature of existence, with the structure of reality as such' (Crotty, 2003:10). In addition, ontological assumptions are applied in research in order to respond to the question of the nature of reality (Guba & Lincoln, 1989). As discussed in the research paradigm section of this study, a qualitative approach has been selected for this study. Qualitative researchers usually claim knowledge based on constructivist perspectives (Creswell, 2003). Constructivism refers to the belief that social phenomena is created from social actors who are concerned with their existence (Bahari, 2010). Based on the constructivist view of reality, the participants are given opportunities to share their perceptions and experience about a specific issue which will demonstrate the participants' view of reality, and their perceptions and experiences will be interpreted by the researcher's analysis (Lather, 1992). The construction of meaning is transmitted within an essentially social context which is discussed in the interviews and the constructionists' views, as there is no true or valid interpretation by researchers (Ahmed, 2008). This present study will explore the students' perceptions and opinions of the development of their motivation and intercultural competence by their English language teachers, as well as their perceptions of how their teachers develop intercultural competence and English language skills. The data for this study will be collected and analysed based on their responses to the interviews; therefore, the researcher believes this study is based on constructivist ontology.

Bryman (2004:11) defined epistemology as 'a theory of knowledge and concern of what is considered as acceptable knowledge in a particular discipline'. An epistemological assumption is associated with the nature of knowledge and the methods where the knowledge can be acquired (Bahari, 2010). Interpretivist researchers play the role as 'social actors' where they can interpret the social roles in accordance with the meaning of the social roles of others (Saunders et al. 2007). In addition, based on the views of interpretivists, facts and values are not different in the research, and findings of the study are influenced by the perspectives and values of researchers themselves (Bryman, 2004). However, objectivist research models are often referred to as quantitative research, and they fail to disclose epistemological assumptions due to the fact that objectivist researchers are typically trained in data collection methods and analysis techniques without paying attention to underlying philosophical foundations of findings (Pascale, 2011:5). Therefore, interpretivist researchers select qualitative data collection tools instead of quantitative tools, as it enables them to generate more descriptive data to provide valuable findings (Smith, 2006). This present study fits the focus of the interpretivist stance by interpreting the participants' perspectives on a specific context and gathering descriptive data through qualitative research tools which will be introduced in this paper.

4.6 Research Methods

There are related research methods such as case studies, narratives, phenomenology and grounded theory which could be addressed in social research (Creswell, 2018). This present study adopted interpretive phenomenology which is also referred to as hermeneutics phenomenology as the research method in this study, as the reason is that this study aims to investigate students' perceptions of the development of their motivation and intercultural competence of English language teachers in classes at Chinese universities which relies on the students' perceptions and opinions. This aim is based on the use of interpretivist tradition that the views of participants of the situation will be studied in the research (Creswell, 2003). Similarly, this study relates to the aim of a phenomenological approach outlined by Baker (1992) which aims to explore the perceptions, experiential moments and understanding of the participants from their points of view which helps the researchers to understand the world through the eyes of participants.

Descriptive phenomenology and interpretive phenomenology are therefore both relevant to this study. However, interpretive phenomenology has been selected for this study, because interpretive phenomenology is concerned with interpretation of individual's experience, and with how they have lived through these experiences, in order to understand things which happened in a certain context (Embree, 1997). Woianr and Swanson (2007) suggested that the interpretive phenomenology theory by Heidegger (1962) goes beyond knowledge of core concepts of phenomenology theory, as it aims to look for meanings embedded in common life experience, and suits studies which are in relation to understand human experience. In addition, Spiegelberg (1976) defines interpretive phenomenology as a method for bringing out what is normally hidden in human experience and human relations. However, in some ways, descriptive phenomenology is similar to interpretive phenomenology as both methods are used for researching human lived experience, but descriptive phenomenology focuses more on exploration of phenomena through direct interaction between the participants and investigators to set aside preconceptions through the research procedures (Tymieniecka, 2003). Thus, the key distinctions of descriptive phenomenology and interpretive phenomenology which are relevant to this study are discussed as follows: descriptive phenomenology emphasizes on describing universal essences and believing the consciousness is what human share, while, interpretive phenomenology aims to explore and understand the phenomena in contexts with the belief that what human share are through the context of cultures and language (Swanson & Wojnar, 2007). This current study aims to understand how Chinese university students perceive the performance and development of intercultural competence by their English language teachers in a specific Chinese context which cannot be considered as a universal phenomenon, therefore, instead of describing universal essences by using a descriptive phenomenology method, interpretive phenomenology is considered to be more related to this study.

In an interpretive phenomenological study, relevant theory is not used to generate hypotheses to be tested; instead, a theoretical approach will be addressed when the researchers attempt to focus on the inquiry of the study, and in order to make decisions about samples, subjects and research questions (Lopez & Willis, 2004). This present study aims to explore students' perceptions of the development of their motivation and

intercultural competence by their English language teachers which is not considered as research which aims to test hypotheses. In addition, in the process of data collection in an interpretive study, participants are encouraged to describe interactions and relations to others, as well as their experiences of time to place and lived experience in the specific context and socialization (Smith, 1987). This suits the focus of this current study, as this study also focus on students' perceptions of their English language teachers, and their experience of being taught the related knowledge of intercultural competence by their English language teachers. Therefore, this study can be considered as an interpretive phenomenological study.

4.7 Sampling

The sample selection and data collection procedure of this study were undertaken at one Chinese university, as the researcher aims to explore English language education, students' motivation and the development of intercultural competence by English language teachers in the higher educational curriculums in China. One Chinese university in Changchun has been selected for this research. The reason for choosing this university is because it is an average comprehensive university in China which has an average ranking among all the universities in China. As it was discussed in the Chinese context chapter in this study, Chinese students are required to pass the entrance examinations called 'Gaokao' to higher education institutions (Richard, 1979). The higher scores the students get, the higher ranking universities they are able to enter. The reason why the researcher selected samples from this average ranking university is that the students from this university are at average national levels which can be representative of the majority of university students in China. According to Cohen et al. (2002), a sample selected for research studies should be based on participants' capability and efficiency to follow the research process which could bring sufficient data for researchers to understand a specific phenomenon. Therefore, the researcher believes that participants from average ranking universities could bring more reliable and efficient data for this study.

In addition, qualitative researchers usually do not select samples randomly, in order to choose participants who are able to answer and understand research questions more clearly (Bryman, 2016). The present study employed purposive sampling as a sampling

technique. The main objective of purposive sampling is to produce a sample that can be logically assumed to be representative of a certain group of population (Lavrakas, 2008). Apart from knowledge and experience, availability and willingness to participate in the research procedure, and the ability to express opinions and experiences in an accurate and proper manner of the potential participants are important for the sample selection (Spradley, 1979). Therefore, samples for this present study were purposively selected from English major and non-English major students at one Chinese University who are willing to participate in this study.

To approach the participants of this research, the researcher contacted a teacher who works as a head teacher at the English department of this Chinese university, and this teacher was willing to help recruit the participants. During the process of selecting the participants, this teacher picked ten international trade major students, from non-English majors and ten English major students. These participants all showed their availability and willingness to participate in this study. In addition, the teacher prepared a classroom for the researcher to do the interviews. In order to encourage the participants to answer questions freely, the teacher left the classroom without observing the whole interview process.

4.8 Research tools

This study applied two research tools for data collection which were focus groups and semi-structured in-depth interviews. All the interview questions (see Appendix 1) were developed from the Research Questions and Aims of this study which focus on students' perceptions of their motivation to learn the English language and their teachers' development of intercultural competence in the classroom at a Chinese university.

Research question one "In what ways do university students perceive intercultural competence and the role of their University teachers in contributing to its development in English classes at Chinese universities?" helped to develop section two of the interview questions which focused on the development of intercultural competence and the role of English language teachers.

Research question two "To what extent is intercultural competence developed between English teachers (both 'native' and non 'native') and Chinese university students?"

helped the researcher to form section three of the interview questions which focused on the difference between English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers at developing intercultural competence in the classroom.

Research question three "In what ways do students think intercultural competence could be developed more effectively in English language departments at Chinese universities?" helped the researcher to develop section four of the interview questions which focused on students' suggestion for developing intercultural competence in the classroom.

Research question four "To what extent do English major and non-English major students differ in their motivation to learn English and in their perceptions of how their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom of their Chinese university?" helped the researcher to form section one and section three of the interview questions which focusing on the relations between students' motivation and their perceptions of how their English language teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom (see Appendix 1).

In addition, interview questions which referred to intercultural competence in this study were designed according to Byram's (1997) intercultural competence model; all five components of this model which are : knowledge, intercultural attitude, skills of discovery and interaction, skills of interpreting and relating, and critical cultural awareness, were addressed and explained clearly in the interview questions to help participants understand the questions, that participants could provide full answers and reliable data for this study. In section two of the interview questions, 'Knowledge' refers to question one and two; 'Intercultural attitude' refers to question three and four; 'Skills of discovery and interaction' refers to question five and six; 'Skills of interpreting and relating' refers to question seven and eight; 'Critical cultural awareness' refers to question nine and ten (see Appendix 1).

The process of data collection lasted ten hours in total. The researcher conducted interviews separately with four focus groups with two groups of five English major students and another two groups of five non-English major students at one Chinese university. Each focus group lasted around forty-five minutes. After each focus group,

while the participants were given a fifteen-minute break, the researcher read through the notes from the focus groups and selected the participants who provided the most relevant and interesting answers during the focus groups to take part in the semi-structured interviews. There were six participants who were selected from the focus groups to take part in the semi-structured interviews: three were English major students, and another three were non-English major students to ensure a balanced response in the semi-structured interviews. Each of the semi-structured interview was conducted separately, that is, one after the other, and each lasted around one hour. The design and the reasons for selecting these two tools to collect data for this study are discussed in this section.

In addition, all the interviews for this study were conducted in Mandarin. According to Jiang (2014), Chinese students sometimes have difficulties accomplishing what is considered to be authentic English speaking. In this study, the researcher wanted to support the participants who may not have the level of English fluency to respond in full to the interview questions. Therefore, the researcher used their and her first language, Mandarin, to ask the interview questions to help the participants to understand the questions, thus enabled them to provide full and reliable answers in a more relaxed and comfortable situation. All the data collected in Mandarin were translated into English by this researcher who is a fluent English and Mandarin speaker.

4.8.1 Focus Groups

The first research tool for data collection which was used in this study is focus groups. In order to explore a primary understanding of how English major and non-English major students' perceptions of the development of their motivation and intercultural competence by their 'native' and 'non-native' English teachers in the classroom at one Chinese university, twenty participants were organized in four groups, each group consists of five participants. The participants for the first and second focus groups are English major students who are from the Chinese university where this study was undertaken, and the other ten participants for the third and fourth groups are non-English majors students from the same Chinese university. They were asked a few general questions based on the research questions of this present study at the

beginning to ease the distance and build up a closer interaction between the researcher and the participants (Then et al.,2014).

The ideal size of each focus group recommended in the literature varies from four to fourteen (Dilorio et al., 1994). Five participants, which is an average number, have been chosen for each focus groups in this study because a large group might prevent individuals from participating and sharing information, while a small group might not provide enough diversity within the group to gather more useful information (Then. Et al, 2014:16). Therefore, the size of five participants for each focus group is ideal for this study.

A focus group interview is regarded as a qualitative data collection tool (McClaffery, 2004), and its notion is within the framework of phenomenology (Wilkinson, 1998) which is in accordance with the interpretive phenomenology method selected for this current study. Carey (1994:226) defined the focus group interview as ‘using a semi-structured group session, moderated by a group leader, held in an informal setting, with the purpose of collecting information on a designated topic’. Focus groups are generally used to gather in-depth knowledge about attitudes, perceptions, beliefs and opinions of individuals based on specific topics (Then et al., 2014:16). The aim of this research is to explore students’ perceptions, where the research tool and focus groups can be properly addressed. Focus group interviews concentrate on the individuals in the groups, in order to observe how the participants interact, and allow them to develop their own ideas of the questions within the context of the event (Liamputtong, 2011). During the focus group interviews, the information obtained is not only concerned with the actual words the participants said, but also the non-verbal communications, which allows the researcher to observe individual’s views, and the changes occurred when these views relate to other participants at the group progresses (Then, 2000).

The main advantage of using focus groups as research tools is that the interaction among individuals in the group can be used to generate data (Kitzinger, 1996). For participants, the experience of a focus group is found to be more enjoyable than either self-administered open-ended surveys or structured group interviews which are with less spontaneous interaction (Bristol & Fern, 1996). For researchers, it is easier to generate more reliable data by focus group interviews because individuals in groups are

found to speak or answer questions in a different way as they do in other situations (Agar & MacDonald, 1995). In addition, focus group participants can relate their experiences and reactions among peers whom they prefer to share a more common frame of reference (Kidd & Parshall, 2000).

The reason why focus groups are used as the first research tool in this study is that the researcher can observe a large amount of interaction on a topic in a limited period of time compared to participant observation (Morgan, 1997). In addition, the focus group method can facilitate greater anonymity and help individuals disclose more freely in comparison to individual interviews (Beck, Trombetta & Share, 1986), as well as decreasing the bias of individual interviews when the participants may try to impress the interviewer or give acceptable response (Vaughn, Schumm & Sinagub, 1996). Focus groups provide more common and reliable data from the participants, and it is generated as the basis of further research (Dilshad & Latif, 2013). In this study, using focus groups to collect data enables the researcher to gather more reliable information about students' perceptions, as it allows the participants to respond to the interview questions in a more comfortable way when they stay with their peers, and it allows the researcher to generate information from their discussions and interactions. Therefore, the focus group interview has been selected as the first data collecting tool for this study.

4.8.2 Semi-structured in-depth interviews

Then, semi-structured interviews were applied as the second research tool in this study to generate more in-depth information from the participants. According to Adams (2015), semi-structured interviews can be useful to add depth to other approaches in the research field. In this study, in order to gather in-depth information based on the data collected from focus groups, six participants were selected from the original twenty participants from each focus group interview, based on their involvement during the focus groups interviews; three of the participants were English major students, the others were non-English major students. Further in-depth questions were asked during the interview in order to explore more detailed information about their perceptions of the development of intercultural competence by their English language teachers in the classroom.

Interviews are regarded as discussions between an interviewer and another individual which are aiming to gather information on a certain set of topics (Harrel et al., 2009). According to Segal, et al. (2006:122), structured interviews can be divided into two types: fully structured and semi-structured. In a fully structured interview, questions are asked verbatim to the participants, and the wording of probes is used to follow up on initial questions which are specified. In a semi-structured interview, the initial questions are specified and typically asked verbatim to the participants, but the researcher has substantial latitude to follow up on responses. In comparison to fully structured interviews, semi-structured interviews employ a blend of closed-ended and open-ended questions, accompanied by follow-up on why or how questions. During the process of semi-structured interviews, the responses of participants can meander around topics, rather than adhering slavishly to verbatim questions (Adams, 2015). Semi-structured interviews have always been conducted to provide an initial guide and unstructured questions and topics; this kind of interview is selected when the researcher wants to delve deeply into a topic and to understand thoroughly the answers provided by the interviewees. In addition, semi-structured interviews enable the interviewees to explain their thoughts and opinions freely (Horton & Macve, 2004). In this study, the researcher aims to analyse the data collected from focus group interviews thoroughly. In addition, in order to explore participants' perceptions of the development of their motivation and intercultural competence by their English language teachers, and their suggestions of improving English learning experience, both open-ended and close-ended questions were required. Therefore, a semi-structured interview is the most appropriate choice as the second research tool for this study.

4.9 Data Analysis

There are various types of qualitative data which include interviews, photographs, and documents (Saldaña, 2013). In this study, data was collected and analysed from the interviews with the participants. In order to analyse the data collected from interview transcripts accurately and effectively, Griffiee (2005) suggested that the researcher should not only capture the essence of what had been said from the participants, but also analyse these related data which was either present in the text or supported by the meaning of the text (Lune & Berg, 2017). Therefore, in this study, the researcher selected manual tools to code and analyse the data instead of relying on software

programmes, in order to identify themes correctly by analysing interview transcripts and the related data supported by the transcripts. As Patton (2015) considered that using manual tools to code and analyse the data is more productive and reliable than using software programmes.

According to Saldaña (2013), data coding in qualitative research fields is considered as a word or a group of words that are able to summarize the core, comprehensive, related and distinctive qualities of a set of data. Data coding is found to be helpful for researchers to develop an in-depth understanding of the data, as well as to discover useful remarks during the coding process to form and create themes (Bernard, 2011). Therefore, the researcher decided to code the data collected from the interviews, as it is helpful for the researcher to develop the eventual themes and subthemes of the data set and further analysis.

In this section, the data collected from the participants at the Chinese university will be discussed. As the Research Methodology section explains, this study is considered as an interpretive phenomenological study in the qualitative research field. Therefore, in order to identify and analyse patterns around qualitative data (Smith & Osborn, 2008), interpretive phenomenological analysis was chosen for this study. Smith and Osborn (2008) stated six stages of interpretive phenomenological analysis, which are: reading a transcript and making initial comments; generating initial themes based on the comments; creating a list of initial themes; clustering the themes and ordering them into connected areas; creating a list of superordinate themes and sub-themes; moving on to the next transcript. In this study, these six stages were used to analyse the qualitative data obtained from focus groups interviews and semi-structured in-depth interviews with the participants at the Chinese university. Thus, the interview transcripts the researcher organized were coded to create the themes and further analysis.

4.9.1 Analysing data from the focus groups

In order to transcribe the data for further analysis, the researcher informed the participants before their interviews that the interview transcripts would be stored as locked files with only access to the researcher and her supervisors. In addition, notes and comments were made during the interviews to help the researcher to facilitate and

create initial themes in order to analyse the data thematically. As Maguire and Delahunt (2017) stated, extracting themes from the data set is important in the thematic analysis. After reading the transcripts and the notes of the data collected from focus groups interviews according to the stages discussed by Smith and Osborn (2008), five superordinate themes emerged referring to the research aims and questions of this study, which were: English language learning motivation; development of intercultural competence in English language classes; preference between English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers; intercultural competence training of English language teachers; and suggestions for developing intercultural competence. All the themes arose from the data referred to participants' own perceptions. After clustering the superordinate themes, subthemes were created based on the responses of the participants to the interview questions. At this stage, the researcher faced the challenge to form and create themes by comparing the initial data to find similarities and dissimilarities, in order to develop these themes for discussion in the findings which were collected from the participants. Moreover, in interpretive studies, data needs to be deeply analysed and interpreted (Byram, 2012). Therefore, in order to facilitate a deep understanding of the data, the transcripts of the data were carefully produced and considered, the quotations from participants which were relevant to the superordinate themes and subthemes, were selected from the transcripts, and were organized in grids according to themes for further analysis (See Appendix 2). Saldaña (2013) considered that in order to obtain accurate and essential analysis from the data, a qualitative researcher was required to concentrate on the data coding process with potentially numerous attempts to get coding right. Thus, collating all the information on grids was helpful to the researcher to analyse the data. The data collected from two types of groups: English major students and non-English major students were organized separately, in order to analyse and compare any difference in their perceptions of English language learning motivation and the development of intercultural competence by their English language teachers clearly and accurately.

4.9.2 Analysing data from the semi-structured interviews

In the next stage of data analysis in this study, the transcripts of the participants from semi-structured interviews were produced. As the aim of this study is to explore students' perceptions of the development of their motivation and intercultural

competence by their English language teachers in the classroom, the data collected from semi-structured interviews focused more on the questions related to intercultural competence. Therefore, the superordinate themes were created as explained previously, which are: development of intercultural competence in English language classes; the knowledge of intercultural competence of English language teachers; preference between English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers; intercultural competence training of English language teachers; and suggestions for developing intercultural competence. All the data and themes collected from the semi-structured interviews referred to participants and discussed their own perceptions. In addition, subthemes were created according to the responses of the participants to the interview questions which were connected with the superordinate themes. Moreover, quotations from each participant were listed on grids in relation to each theme (see Appendix 2) in order to help the researcher clearly see each theme and related quotation from participants. The findings of the data collected and analyzed in this study which are related to the research aims and questions will be discussed in the findings chapter.

4.10 Reliability

According to Stenbacka (2001), reliability is a concept used to evaluate the quality of a qualitative research with the purpose of generating understanding. In addition, Long & Johnson (2000) defined reliability as the consistency within the employed analytical procedures. However, to evaluate the reliability of a study in a qualitative approach, Smith & Noble (2015) presented several strategies for qualitative researchers to ensure the 'trustworthiness' of the findings such as accounting personal biases, establishing comparison cases, engaging with other researchers and data triangulation. In other words, reliability is ensured by accounting for personal biases, acknowledging biases in sampling and ongoing critical reflection of methods to ensure sufficient depth and relevance of data collection and analysis. In this study, all the participants were picked by the same teacher who works at the English language department at the Chinese university for the focus group interviews. To ensure the data free biases, all the participants in this research, English major and non-English major students at the Chinese university are all from the same cultural and educational background, under studying the same language policy. In addition, all the participants were selected as they have shown their willingness to participate in this study, in this way, the participants

were able to answer the interview questions freely to offer more accurate and reliable data for this study. Therefore, the researcher believes that she can ensure the reliability of the data and findings of this study by easing any potential biases during the whole research process.

4.11 Transferability

Lani (2017) described transferability as synonymous with generalizability in qualitative research. Transferability is established in order to provide evidence that the results and findings of the research could be applicable to other contexts, situations and populations. However, according to Guba & Lincoln (1985), it seems not possible for researchers to prove the research findings will be applicable, but it is a researchers' responsibility to provide the data base which could make transferability judgements possible on potential applicants. In addition, Guba & Lincoln (1985) recommended a technique to establish transferability in the qualitative research which is able to provide 'thick description' of the phenomenon. Thick description means that researchers can provide a detailed account of the experiences and information during data collection, for example, researchers discuss and consider the information of where the interviews occurred and other aspects of detailed information during the data collection process, in this way, it enables the researcher to offer a fuller understanding of the research setting. In this study, all the research settings will be listed in detail such as participants' educational and cultural background, participants' reactions during the interviews and all their responses to interview questions to ensure the transferability of this research.

4.12 Ethical Considerations

The purpose of this study is to explore the English major and non-English major students' perceptions of the development of their motivation and intercultural competence by their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers in the classroom in a Chinese university instead of examining the ability of intercultural competence of their English language teachers. In this circumstance, this research topic is not considered ethically sensitive as it does not include any physical or psychological pressure for potential participants to take part in this research and share their opinions.

Ethical considerations were paramount through all the stages of the research process, including creating the research design, approaching the Chinese university to conduct interviews with the students, as well as analysing the data collected from the interviews. Initially, the researcher submitted the Ethical Approval Application to the relevant department at the University of the West of Scotland with the explanation of the research design and ethical considerations. Once the researcher received the ethical approval, the English language department of one Chinese university was approached to acquire permission for conducting interviews.

According to Bryman (2007), the following elements of ethical considerations of a piece of research should be mentioned: choice, formality and discretion; anonymity; and safe storage of data. Firstly, an email will be sent to the potential participants via giving them opportunity to take part in the research to make sure it is a voluntary choice without any kind of physical or psychological force on them; then formal language is used by the researcher during the process of focus group interviews and semi-structured interviews.

In addition, ethical issues are important to consider in any research, in order to provide consistency, as well as to ensure no improper offensive or discriminatory language during the whole data collecting process. In this way, the participants are protected from any possible risks or harm. Before the interviews took place, informed consents were sent to all potential participants which included the purpose of this study and an overview of interview questions. They had the right to choose to accept or refuse to participate in this research as their participation in this study was informed as totally voluntary. Moreover, the names of the participants in this research were not used in the written transcripts of the interview, nor in the final report for the project, nor in any other publications arising from the research to protect personal information of the participants. The names of the participants were anonymised and referred to by code instead, for example, Participant 1, Participant 2. Electronic files and documents were password protected and paper documents were securely stored in a locked draw which only the researcher and her supervisors have access to; then the acknowledgement of studies from other authors used to support in this research was listed in the UWS Harvard referencing system.

4.13 Positionality

As the researcher is a former student of the Chinese University where this research was undertaken, the researcher can be considered as an 'insider researcher'. According to Naples (2003:46), insider research has been defined as 'the study of one's own social group or society'. A similar definition is provided by Loxley and Seery (2008), which is, insider research is undertaken by the members of the same group, for example, people who share same cultural, biological or occupational characteristics are from the same group. In addition, insider research is discussed in contrast to outsider research. Merton (1972) defined the research which is undertaken by those who are not occupied with a priori knowledge of the community under study, or who are not a member of the group, is an outside researcher.

Positionality is determined by where the researcher stands in relation to the participants which can influence and shift the process of conducting research (Greene, 2014). According to Chavez (2008:475), insider positionality refers to 'the aspects of an insider researcher's self or identity which is aligned or shared with participants'. However, this definition is not clear enough to determine what degree of social connection merits this classification. Chaves (2008) further discussed that insider researchers may be considered as two types, total insiders and partial insiders; total insiders refer to researchers who share multiple identities or profound experiences with the community which is undertaken their research; partial insiders refers to researchers who share a sole identity with a certain extent of distance from the community they are studying. In this study, the researcher can be regarded as a partial insider, even though the researcher and the participants share the same cultural background, the researcher has a sense of both cultures after studying in the UK for more than three years. Therefore, she can be referred as having multiple identities, as a Chinese student, as an UK student, as a researcher, which might bring an extent of difference between the researcher and participants.

However, there has been a debate around the 'insider/outsider' positionality which really influences the process of the research. The outsider's perspective was considered optimal for its 'objectivity' and 'accuracy' in the research field; on the other hand, insider researchers believe that they are able to possess deeper insights about their

participants, but they might hold a biased position which will complicate their ability to observe and interpret (Chavez, 2008). However, Naples (1996:140) claimed that 'insiderness or outsiderness is not a fixed or static position, rather they are ever-shifting and permeable social locations that are differentially experienced and expressed by community members'. Naples (1996) suggested that both insiders and outsiders have to contend with similar methodological issues around positionality, a researcher should possess a sense of self and situated knowledge as a result of the researchers' position in the social order. In other words, neither insider nor outsider researchers have an advantage on objectivity.

The reason why the researcher chose to conduct this study at the Chinese university she studied at before as an insider, is not only that the researcher was able to get easier access to organize interviews at this university with students than other Chinese universities, but also it might benefit this research. For example, insider researchers have a pre-existing knowledge of the context of the research (Bell, 2005) which helps the researchers to ask meaningful questions, read non-verbal cues during the interviews, as well as to project a more truthful understanding of the culture under study (Merriam, et al, 2001); in addition, interaction between insider researchers and participants is more natural as the insiders are familiar with the social setting and know how to approach individuals instead of perhaps stereotyping and passing judgment on them (Aguiler, 1981).

However, Delyser (2001) argued that as there is greater familiarity between insiders and participants, this can lead to a loss of objectivity, as well as the risk of making assumptions based on insider researchers' prior knowledge and experience. It is crucial to maintain objectivity in this research project. According to Babbie (2010), the observer of the research must not be the source of the data, nor must they influence the data; and the reliability will become lower when the observer adopts a subjective approach (Wilson, 2010). Although the researcher and participants of this research have similar experience of studying at the same university, in order to adopt a more appropriate objective research approach, the process of data collection will also be confirmed by the supervisor of this research. This technique was also confirmed to be useful by other insider researchers (Delyzer, 2001; Miller, 1997; Chaves, 2008) which

helps participants overlook the familiarity with their researcher and provide more details when answering questions.

However, the researcher's perception of her 'insider' position shifted after the data collection with the participants from the Chinese university. As the researcher was a former student of the Chinese university which was the locus for this study, she imagined, in line with her experience as a Chinese student, that the participant responses would be slightly different. However, the findings of this study which will be discussed in the next chapter are quite different from the researcher's expectations. It appears that students' perceptions of the English language education in Chinese universities might have changed since the researcher left China, that is, over the past six years. In this circumstance, the researcher considers herself more as a researcher from a Western university, that is, her positionally is somewhere between an 'outsider' PhD researcher from the UK instead of a wholly 'insider' researcher who studied at the Chinese university.

To sum up, although caution has to be taken when the researcher is considered as an 'insider' researcher, organizing interviews at the university where the researcher used to be a former student, the research methods generated insights which are trustworthy. In addition, the researcher believes that as an insider researcher, it also enables her to offer detailed and objective information based on the understanding of the same culture and context as the participants. Therefore, this study still contains objectivity and in-depth analysis of the data.

4.14 Conclusion

In this study, in order to ensure consistency and comprehensiveness, the most appropriate research design and research methods were selected carefully to link with the research questions. Moreover, the objectives of this study were addressed in two qualitative tools. First, focus groups interviews with English major and non-English major students were used to develop the semi-structured interviews; second, semi-structured interviews with selected English major and non-English major students from all the participants of focus groups interviews were used to explore the findings thoroughly. In addition, the research questions were designed as the result of both the literature review and the theoretical framework of this study.

In this chapter, the rationale for the selected Byram's (1997) intercultural competence model as the theoretical framework in this study was explained as this model provided relevant knowledge to the focus of this study, and all the components in this theory can be fully addressed in interview questions. In addition, the qualitative research methods were presented in order to explore and analyse student's perceptions, a detailed account of comparisons with additional research methods were discussed. Then, the researcher used purposive sampling technique to select participants for this study in order to collect more accurate and reliable data for this study, as well as to ensure the participants can be representative of the Chinese university student groups. In addition, two stages of data collecting tools: focus groups interviews and semi-structured interviews were selected for this study in order to collect in-depth data about students' perceptions of the development of their motivation and intercultural competence by their English language teachers. All the data collected from the interviews of this research was coded and analysed via interpretive phenomenological analysis. Moreover, the issues around the researcher's position as an 'insider' researcher and ethical considerations were discussed in this chapter.

In the next chapter, a detailed discussion of the research findings will be presented.

Chapter 5: Findings

5.1 Introduction

This chapter will discuss and analyse the key findings of research into 'English major and non-English major students' perceptions of their motivation to learn the English language and the development of the intercultural competence by their English language teachers in the classroom in a Chinese university. The discussion and analysis has arisen from the examination of the data which can be separated into themes which emerged from the data collected: Motivation to learn English; Students' perception of development of intercultural competence in English classes; Students' Preference for English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers; Students' perception of English teachers' knowledge of intercultural competence; Students' perception of Intercultural competence training of English teachers; and Students' Suggestions for developing intercultural competence.

5.2 Motivation to learn English

Kim (2009) states that L2 motivation is created when L2 learners realise the importance of the target language learning, and the outcome of learning this target language would connect with their life conditions. Also, L2 motivation is the integration of appropriate L2 learning goals, the participation in actual or imagined target language communities. Accordingly, motivated students would be more eager and enthusiastic to devote their time to language learning. Moreover, having a specific goal and desire to study a foreign language can help students put their best efforts and maintain their motivation (Muftah & Rafik-Galea, 2013).

According to Csizer & Dornyei (2005:20), students' behaviours while they are motivated to learn the foreign language are related to two criteria measures: the students' language choice for future second language studies and the amount of effort the students intend to exert on learning a second language. In a study on high school students learning French as a second language in Canada, motivation and attitude are found relevant to the achievement of French; the findings showered that motivation is regarded as willingness to be like valued members of the language community (Kaplan,

2005 & Baker, 2011). In addition, a new language-learning motivation was proposed by Yashima (2002:57) which was defined as: 'international posture, which includes an interest in foreign or international affairs, willingness to go overseas to study or work, readiness to interact with intercultural partners and a non-ethnocentric attitude toward different cultures'. In the context of Chinese university students, these two theories have affected and revealed the English learning goals of students. According to Gao & Zhao et al. (2007), Chinese students learn the English language to develop their own ability and social values in order to be recognized as 'valued members' in the community in the future, which could be as specific as 'better employment' or as general as acquiring 'a sense of achievement'. In contrast, Chinese university students were also found to be motivated to experience and immigrate to Western cultures by learning the English language.

In this study, the discussion of motivation will be considered mainly as two types: instrumental motivation and integrative motivation by the theories of Dornyei (1990) and Gardner (1985). Instrumental motivation relates to the practical and utilitarian advantages of learning a foreign language by second language learners such as a desire for better employment and a higher salary (Dornyei, 1990). For Chinese students, getting a good grade or passing an examination is an overriding motivation to learn the English language. The examination of CET-4 plays an important role for Chinese university students as it is a baseline to graduate from a university and a stepping-stone for future work (Wang, 2008). For example, passing CET-4 is clearly an instrumental integration in practice: the Chinese students have to excel in listening, reading and writing skills of English in order to progress to graduation. However, English language teachers found it is difficult to motivate students to learn English as students hardly have a chance to practise English in class because most teachers spend more time on teaching grammar and language knowledge instead of communication skills (Zeng & Murphy, 2007).

In contrast, integrative motivation expresses the desire of students to learn a foreign language to be more integrated into the target language culture (Gardner, 1985). After reviewing Gardner's (1985) theory about integrative motivation, Cook (2001) stated that, integrative motivation reflects whether the students identify themselves with the

target culture, in other words, the more the students admire the target culture, the more the students will be more motivated in second language learning. Even though integrative motivation has played a rapidly diminishing role in L2 motivational research, current active motivation researchers are suggested to include the concept of 'integrative motivation' in their research paradigms (Dornyei & Ushioda, 2011). For Chinese students, a strong desire to go abroad or integrate into English-speaking communities has not been found in previous research reviewed for this thesis. Based on the Chinese cultural context, it seems impossible for most Chinese students to go abroad or to have more chances to communicate with foreign friends (Wang, 2008). As there are limited chances for students to meet foreign friends apart from English 'native' teachers, and not every parent in China is able to afford their children to study abroad due to the high priced tuition fees.

In this section, these two types of English learning motivations in relation to the data collected from English major and non-English major students in a Chinese university will be analysed and discussed. During the interviews, the participants were asked how they enjoy and develop their English language to discover their motivation to learn the language. The data from the participant interviews reveals that both English major and non-English major students have instrumental motivation, and English major students are found to have integrative and potential integrative motivation. This is evident from further discussion of the data below.

5.2.1 Instrumental Motivation

Previous surveys conducted by Gao (2004) and Zeng & Murphy (2007) as well as Dornyei & You (2014) show that the English learning motivation of Chinese students is instrumental rather integrative because of the following reasons: English language teachers focus more on grammar teaching instead of developing students' communicative skills; this has caused limited opportunities for students to practise speaking skills of English, and students feel less involved while studying the English language. Chinese university students learn the English language to pass exams, graduate successfully from the university and gain more opportunities for better jobs in the future. In addition, according to the research by Taguchi et al. (2009), Chinese

students are found to be instrumentally motivated to learn the English language due to the fact that many Chinese students are keen on raising their English proficiency test scores as English proficiency is strongly related to successful job-hunting in China where it contains a massive number of foreign companies. The knowledge of the English language is a requirement in most Chinese and international companies in China. As Dornyei & You (2014: 516) stated: 'Chinese learners are primarily instrumentally motivated. While instrumental factors (both promotion and prevention) do play an important part in motivating learning'. According to the discussions around previous studies, Chinese students are found to be mainly instrumentally motivated to learn English.

This study confirms the findings of earlier research, referred to the discussion above, as both English and non-English major students in the context of this study have been found to be instrumentally motivated to learn the English language. According to the data collected from English major students' focus groups, from Group 1 and Group 2, they responded and discussed their English learning motivation as follows: Participant 1 responds:

'I want to learn and develop my English because I want to work as an English teacher in the future'

and Participant 2 adds

'I want to develop my English because I think a good English proficiency is helpful to find a proper job in China';

these responses accord with the goal of instrumental motivation as described by Dornyei (2011) and Gardner(1985): that students learn the English language to be more competitive in the labour market. Moreover, Participant 4 from the semi-structured interviews further notes that:

'I am required to learn English as an English major to pass English tests not only CET-4 and CET-6, but also TEM-8 (Test for English Majors-Band 8) to graduate from a Chinese university'

It is obvious this student is instrumentally motivated to learn English to pass these particular exams to progress graduation.

In addition, the data collected from focus groups with non-English major students, from participant Group 3 and Group 4, discussed their English learning motivation as, in the words of Participant 11:

‘I am not very interested in learning English as English has been a part of my life which I cannot get rid of. According to Participant 11, he/she is not interested in learning English, but just learning the language to progress and graduate successfully from the university.

Participant 15 notes that:

‘I need to learn English to pass the exams and be more competitive in the future job market ‘.

In addition, participant 18 further discusses in the semi-structured interview:

‘I found that it is difficult to learn English deeply as we only use English to pass exams and for a better job opportunity’.

These findings relate to the instrumental motivation theory noted by Gardner (1985) who considers passing exams and an intention to progress to better employment are main factors causing instrumental motivation as noted in the responses from these participants.

The findings of this study also reveal that non-English major students seem to be more negatively disposed towards English language learning than English major students. As non-English major students have to learn the English language from primary school to higher education which counts for more than ten years (Xu, 2009), they seem to be a little tired of learning the English language as a compulsory subject in which they are not particularly interested as participant 11 notes in the interviews. In addition, for non-English major students in Chinese universities, they would like to spend more time on learning the knowledge of their own major study, apart from learning English for the first two years at university. As Participant 16 notes:

‘Apart from learning English to pass CET-4, I have to spend more time on studying business courses such as Accounting and Finance to pass the final exams at the end of each trimester as well’.

The findings of this study are found to be related to Yan's (2015) study on non-English major students' motivation to learn the English language, and the findings revealed that they were demotivated because of their past unhappy experience of learning the English language as well as their low language proficiency makes it difficult for them to understand the contents of English language courses at the higher educational level as participant 11 notes, above.

Chinese non-English major students are found to be more instrumentally motivated to learn the English language as discussed above, mainly for the praise of their teacher and parents, passing the exams and gaining the qualifications to graduate from universities (Wang,2008). However, in comparison with another relevant research in the Japanese context, as Japan shares a similar cultural background as China, Japanese college students are found to be more motivated to learn the English language, as they have the interest and desire to go abroad or travel overseas (Mori& Gobel, 2006). The findings of this research reveal that Chinese university students did not show strong desire to go abroad or to integrate into English-speaking communities referring to the responses of the participants from focus groups 1 and 2; some of the participants indicated that they were barely interested in learning English because they struggled to understand the knowledge of the English language, and they were under the pressure from passing English language exams as participant 18 refers to, above. Wang (2008) noted that the differences in motivation to learn the English language between Japanese and Chinese students may be caused by the fact that, it is impossible for most students to go abroad or to make foreign friends in China as there are fewer foreigners staying in China than in Japan, and not every Chinese family can afford the fees to support their children to go abroad.

5.2.2 Integrative Motivation

According to Dornyei & You (2014), when students progress through a more advanced English language education, such as English major students, they are more aware of their language skills to prepare them to be competitive in their future career. The labour markets in China require students to acquire the knowledge of advanced English language to get a better job, and this requirement affects students' motivation to learn

the English language in China. In addition, language learning motivation can also be affected by their choice of career. According to the data collected for this study, English learning motivation differs between English major and non-English major students. The findings of this study reveal that there are differences in students' motivation to learn the English language between English major students and non-English major students in a Chinese university. It appears, from the data, that non-English major students only have instrumental motivation which is required to pass their exams and be more competitive in the future job market, as discussed above.

During the interview with the focus group, most participants from non-English major groups did not show strong interest in learning the English language, as Participant 20 answered:

‘Sometimes I feel stressed when I am learning English, because examinations such as CET-4 are kind of difficult to pass’.

Participants from non-English majors are found to have no interest to learn the English language as discussed during the semi-structured interviews. As Participant 7 answers:

‘To be honest, I am not very interested in learning English.’

and Participant 19 notes:

‘I used to enjoy learning English when I was very young, but when I grew up, I found it is difficult to learn English’.

The findings show that non-English major students who have lower English language proficiency than English major students feel more stressed when they are learning the English language, as they seem not interested to learn the English language to connect with the Western culture, as English major students do. Similarly, the findings are in relation to the survey conducted by Zhou (2011) where non-English major students are found to lack motivation to learn the English language at Chinese universities; because of that, most of the English language teachers at Chinese universities fail to pay enough attention and develop a systematic way of improving students' motivation to learn the language.

5.2.3 Comparison between the motivation of the two groups of students

However, for English major students, the data collected and analysed from Group 2 (English major students) shows that these students mainly have integrative motivation to learn the English language which enables them to be more integrated into the target language culture as participant 8 answers:

‘I want to learn and develop my English to get more chances to know different cultures and broaden the horizon of life’.

The findings show that English major students seem to have positive attitudes to being integrated in English language communities. Students who choose English as a major subject at university have strong interest in the English language and a desire to develop their knowledge of the Western culture. However, some participants in this study who are English major students are found to have potential integrative motivation, as at the current stage, they are not motivated enough to learn the English language, but they believe that they will be able to be more motivated if they have more opportunities to practise English, as participant 3 comments:

‘I think I will enjoy learning English more if I can get more chances to use English apart from English classes’.

Some participants, such as those above, in this study are found to be eager to understand and explore the culture of the English language; the reason might be that students in China are able to watch Western movies and listen to their songs which are available through the English medium (Cheung, 2001). However, the majority of the participants in this study use the English language as an instrumental tool as they have limited opportunities to learn and use the language as participant 3 notes above. Most Chinese students can hardly talk to English ‘native’ speakers apart from English language classes, as the Chinese language is majorly used in their everyday life (Rao, 2002). Thus, it is perhaps more difficult for Chinese students to have integrative motivation as even English major students use authentic English so rarely in class, as participant 3 notes, above. Therefore, instrumental motivation is considered to be the principal type of motivation of English language learners in China which might result from the fact that the English language education system in China seems still under reformation, traditional exam-oriented teaching has not lost its dominance (Chen, Warden & Chang, 2005). Even though Chinese university students desire to explore

English culture and develop English language knowledge, they have to learn English to pass examinations at the same time.

It appears to be that, both English major and non-English major students in a Chinese university have instrumental motivation towards learning the English language. However, English major students also found to have integrative and potential integrative motivation to learning the English language. There is an obvious difference in students' motivation to learn the English language between English major and non-English major students. In general, English major students express more desire to learn the language, in other words, they are found to have integrative motivation to learn the English language; on the other hand, non-English major students only use English as an instrumental tool to pass the exams, and to have better employment opportunities.

5.3 Students' perceptions of the development of Intercultural Competence in English classes

According to Taylor (1994), intercultural competence refers to a transformative process through which the individuals develop their adaptive capacity, that is, they adapt their perspectives to effectively understand the demands of another culture. Byram (2002) also defined intercultural competence as the ability to change the individual's knowledge, attitudes and behaviours in order to be open and flexible to other cultures. In addition, Fantini (2009) found a variety of terms could be used as tools to assess intercultural competence which are multiculturalism, cross-cultural adaptation, intercultural sensitivity, cultural intelligence, international communication, transcultural communication, global competence, cross-cultural awareness, and global citizenship. The ability of intercultural competence of a foreign language teacher is recognized as an important component of their professional identities which allows them the opportunity to teach the language to a cultural level instead of only teaching grammar points and writing skills (Sercu, Bandura & Castro, 2005). English language teachers' perceptions of intercultural competence and their subsequently willingness to interculturalize the English language and to promote students' acquisition of intercultural competence in English classes are crucial to English language education, as developing the intercultural competence in the English language classroom could offer

students a better understanding of language knowledge, and help them to gain more competitive job options in a global market place (Han & Song, 2011). In the Chinese context, most of the English language teachers are found with vague perceptions of intercultural competence and the relationship between intercultural competence and English language teaching (Song, 2008,2009; Xu, 2000,2008; Zhang, 2007). Chong (2015) summarized a Chinese-perspective intercultural competence model by eight other Chinese scholars between 1998 and 2013; this has three major components: cognitive ability, emotional management and communication skills constitute the Chinese version of intercultural competence models. However, this model is not selected for this study, as this paper aims to explore students' perceptions of how their English language teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom which is focusing on cultural aspects instead of evaluating cognitive and communication skills of English language teachers. Moreover, some Chinese teachers showed strong doubt toward the possibility of acquiring intercultural skills and developing intercultural competence, and teaching English language in an integrated way at university. The findings of Han and Song's study (2011) revealed that due to the limited teaching contents of intercultural education and inadequacy of cultural elements in the textbooks, even though these teachers are willing to develop students' intercultural competence at English classes, a large proportion of time to teach culture will be needed which will interrupt the regular process of English language teaching.

In this section, both English major and non-English major students' perceptions of how their English teachers (English native and non-native teachers) develop intercultural competence will be analysed and discussed. The research questions are based on Byram's (1997) model of intercultural competence which contains five dimensions: *savoirs*, *savoir apprendre*, *savoir comprendre/faire*, *savoir être* and *savoir s'engager*. In English, these five dimensions refer to: knowledge, intercultural attitude, skill of discovery and interaction, skills of interpreting and relating and critical cultural awareness. Byram (2014) argued that this 1997 model of intercultural competence was designed for the Council of Europe in developing the concept of intercultural competence (Byram & Zarate, 1996) which had not included reference to the political in the Council of Europe context. However, this model is appropriate for the Chinese political context. Byram (2014) noticed that the increasing numbers of language

teachers in China have realized the importance of intercultural competence in the recent five to ten years which emphasizes the existence of this study to explore how English teachers possess the knowledge of intercultural competence at classes based on the perceptions of students. However, Byram (2014) again argued this model included discussion of how the development of intercultural competence can be assessed, but lacked the specification of language learning or language awareness objectives. To overcome the shortage of 1997 models in this study, research questions were asked with a specific aim of how Chinese students received cultural information and knowledge from their English language teachers.

5.3.1 Intercultural Attitude

savoir-e[^]tre (intercultural attitude) is described as 'curiosity and open-ness, readiness to suspend disbelief about other cultures and belief about one's own' (Byram, 1997:57). The participants were asked in the interviews whether they think their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers are curious about other cultures as well as their own. In this study, the findings reveal that both English major and non-English major students positively believe that their English language teachers have willingness and curiosity toward other cultures; they are curious of cultural events, movies and the experience of living abroad.

5.3.1.1 English Major

English major students from the focus groups believe their English 'native' teachers have a positive attitude toward Chinese cultures. For example, Participant 3 responses:

'I think my English 'native' teacher desires to learn about Chinese culture. He will ask us about cultural knowledge, but he will not ask deeply as we don't have enough time to talk about it in class'.

Participant 7 notes that:

'He is very curious about Chinese culture as he starts to learn the Chinese language and he loves watching Chinese movies'.

In addition, Participant 6 from the semi-structured interviews adds that:

'I can tell he loves Chinese culture, he even read Chinese ancient novel: The Pilgrimage to the West which is amazing!'.

According to the findings from these participants, the majority of English major students in the Chinese University believe their English 'native' teachers have acquired a positive attitude toward Chinese cultures. Only one student, Participant 3 discusses above that 'I think my English 'native' teacher desires to learn the Chinese culture', but notes that his teacher 'will not ask deeply about cultural knowledge', showing a little uncertainty about their English 'native' teachers' openness and willingness towards the Chinese culture, as there is not enough time for their English 'native' teachers to talk about what they see as 'irrelevant' cultural knowledge in English classes. One of the reasons why English language teachers cannot share and teach enough cultural knowledge in English classes might be that, as You (2010:208) stated:

'A typical college English curriculum in China works under the guidance of the College English Syllabus and is evaluated almost exclusively by the results of students' scores on the CET. In such a curriculum, students' individual needs for English are hardly acknowledged; many teachers are predominantly concerned about teaching language knowledge and test-taking skills, instead of language skills for communication purposes'.

Due to the exam-oriented teaching system in China, some students might have limited chances to develop their understanding of the Western culture and their communicative skills of the English language.

English major students from the focus groups believe their English 'non-native' teachers have a positive attitude toward the Western cultures. As Participant 3 notes:

'my Chinese teacher always reads English books and she told us Western cultures are very interesting. She also suggested that we learn about Western cultures.

Moreover, Participant 7 comments:

'my Chinese teacher is into ancient Greek and Roman mythologies and always introduces them to us in English classes.'

It is interesting in this study to explore Chinese students' perceptions of the Western culture as Participant 7 regards ancient Greek and Roman mythologies as his/her understanding of the Western culture. However, culture is not a simple, easily definable concept. It is difficult to pinpoint an exact definition of such a broad concept. Mastsumo

(1996:16) defined culture as ‘the set of attitudes, values, beliefs, and behaviours shared by a group of people’. Even though ancient Greek mythology may not fully represent Western culture, English ‘non-native’ teachers in China are still found to have enthusiasm to share Western stories with their students.

In addition, Participant 6 responds in the semi-structured interviews:

‘especially my Chinese teachers who have experience studying abroad are likely with share more about Western culture to us. I think they understand more about Western culture than other teachers who don’t have experience abroad’.

English major students seem to be satisfied with their Chinese teachers’ intercultural attitude, but they are still found to prefer the Western culture and stories taught by English language teachers who have experience of studying or living abroad as participant 6 states, above.

5.3.1.2 Non-English Major

Non-English major students also consider their English ‘native’ teachers have a positive attitude toward Chinese cultures. As Participant 12 and 13 discuss in the focus groups:

‘He always asks and discusses with us when he meets something he doesn’t really understand. Also, he is curious and interested at some events my university hosts such as military training for students which I know is only happened in China’.

In addition, Participant 20 notes in the semi-structured interviews:

‘My English native teacher is really interested in Chinese food. He knows better than us where he can find wonderful food. Sometimes he shares Chinese food with us after class’. This confirms that the participants in this study believe their English ‘native’ teachers have a clear understanding of Western cultures.

For non-English major students in Chinese universities, their English learning task is not as difficult as English major students, as they are just required to improve English speaking skills by their ‘English’ native teachers. Referring to the participants from non-English major students group in this study, English ‘native’ teachers seem to be more curious and interested to talk about their daily life in China compared to the data

collected from English major students, as the participants from English major groups consider English 'native' teachers did not talk much about their life in China or discuss cultural topics in-depth in English language classes.

However, non-English major students in this study believe their English 'non-native' teachers also have a positive attitude towards Western cultures. Participant 12 from the focus groups notes that:

'Yes, my Chinese teacher sometimes discusses some events that happened in Western countries with us'.

However, the response from Participant 20 in the semi-structured interviews is very interesting as she comments:

'I think my Chinese teacher is curious about Western culture, but she did not teach much in class, instead, she suggested that we travel abroad to find out by ourselves'.

The findings are in relation to Byram's (1997) theory, in which he set up a dichotomy between the tourist and the sojourner due to the development of intercultural competence. The tourist refers to a traveler who comes to foreign communities to set out to meet foreign people, culture and artefacts which would enrich the individuals' current way of life and experience by encountering otherness. Moreover, the sojourner refers to those who produce effects on a society which challenge its unquestioned and unconscious beliefs, behaviours and meanings, and whose own beliefs, behaviors and meanings are in turn challenged and expected to change' (Byram, 1997:1). Therefore, in this study English 'non-native' teachers are found to be curious of Western cultures, however, their understanding of the Western culture is more based on a 'surface' level, as noted by participant 20, above, they encourage their students to travel abroad to Western cultures instead of introducing Western cultural knowledge.

5.3.2 Skill of discovery and interaction

savoir comprendre/faire is described as the 'skill of discovery and interaction: ability to acquire new knowledge of a culture and cultural practices and the ability to operate

knowledge, attitudes and skills under the constraints of real time communication and interaction' (Byram, 1997: 61).

In this section, participants were asked the research questions: 'whether intercultural competence is directly taught in English classes' and 'how the students receive and understand intercultural competence from their English teachers' to explore whether in the students' perceptions, their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers in Chinese universities have the ability to acquire new knowledge of both Chinese and English-speaking cultures and to develop this during English classes.

5.3.2.1 English Major

All the participants from English major groups believe that both of their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers do not possess enough skills of discovery and interaction as their teachers do not teach intercultural competence directly in English classes, they only teach and introduce relevant cultural knowledge which is connected with the content of textbooks. As Participant 1 in the focus groups notes:

'My Chinese teacher mentioned how to speak English in proper English thinking and explain the language used in English movies. But English 'native' teacher hardly mentions it, he teaches us some English words which are only used in his home country'.

In addition, Participant 2 considers:

'Even though I am not directly taught, my Chinese teacher shared her experience in Europe, recommended some famous Chinese and English movies and told us mythologies of ancient Rome. English 'native' teacher compared festivals in China and Western countries, introduced American religions, and also his understanding of Chinese books.

Moreover, Participant 3 strongly comments in the semi-structured interviews that:

'Both the Chinese and English 'native' teachers didn't teach it directly in class. However, our Chinese teacher who had experience living abroad shared her

opinions on different cultures and stories when she was abroad. But English 'native' teacher hardly mentions the culture in class'.

According to the data collected from English major students in this study, they consider that the knowledge of intercultural competence is not directly taught by either English 'native' or 'non-native' teachers. Moreover, the findings above, from participants 1, 2 and 3 reveal that English 'non-native' teachers share relevant cultural knowledge to their students based on their own experience abroad whereas English 'native' teachers did not mention much concerning cultural knowledge in English classes. The participants in this study perceive that their English 'native' teachers only have mentioned the differences in festivals between China and Western countries. For English 'native' teachers, Intercultural language teaching takes the need to communicate in the first place and try to teach cultural knowledge in a way which develops both intercultural communicative skills and language skills (Liddicoat, 2004). Therefore, whatever teaching methodology is adopted in English classes, cultural knowledge should at least be included (Liu, Zhang & Yin, 2014). However, the findings reveal that English major students receive intercultural knowledge by indirect means such as reading or watching movies, as participant 1 notes during the interviews that 'my teacher mentioned how to speak English in proper English thinking when we were watching an English movie', then, more effective language learning methods should be conducted by their English language teachers to develop students' understanding of the culture behind the language (Zhang, 2007). However, in the Chinese college context, designing classroom activities appropriate for cultural experience and learning which are suitable for Chinese students is still a great challenge for English language teachers at Chinese universities (Liu & Laohawiriyanon, 2013).

5.3.2.2 Non-English Major

All the participants from non-English major groups in this study believe their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers seem not to possess enough skill of discovery and interaction as the teachers do not teach intercultural competence directly in English classes, but they teach and introduce relevant cultural knowledge which is connected with the content of textbooks. As Participant 4 from the focus groups notes:

'I am not directly taught intercultural competence in English classes. My Chinese teacher shared her experience as a visiting scholar abroad with us in class. And English 'native' teacher introduced the difference between Western and Chinese festivals, life and fashion styles to us in class'.

Participant 5 adds in the semi-structured interviews that:

'Both of my Chinese and English 'native' teacher did not really talk about what was intercultural competence in class, but they told us the difference of life styles, festivals, customs between Chinese and Western cultures'.

The data collected from non-English major students are found to be similar to the data collected from the participants from English major groups, as they all perceive that English 'non-native' teachers share relevant cultural knowledge based on their own experience abroad in the classroom. However, English 'native' teachers do not introduce much cultural knowledge at English classes, as they only explain the difference of festivals between China and Western countries. For example, Participant 6 notes his/her opinion of the reason why intercultural competence is not taught at English classes in the semi-structured interviews:

'Our Chinese teacher focuses more on improving our listening and reading skills in class, and English 'native' teacher focus on developing our speaking and presentation skills. They did not talk much about intercultural competence in class as they needed to finish their teaching tasks. But sometimes my English 'native' teacher introduced Western festivals and compares them with Chinese festivals'.

Hu (2003:297) considers the English language teaching style in China is largely teacher-fronted in the classroom, as teachers usually take up most of the class time to introduce and explain the knowledge by themselves without interacting with their students. English language teachers in China typically have the power to control over the content and pace of lessons. They frequently explain grammar rules to their students and provide exemplary sentences to illustrate the grammar rules they have taught, this is echoed by participant 6, above. Thus, this language teaching style in China might cause less time for teachers to develop intercultural competence at English classes, as the

language teachers require more time to concentrate on grammar teaching, and to manage a large number of students in the classroom.

5.3.3 Skills of interpreting and relating

Skill of interpreting and relating is known as ‘the ability to interpret a document or event from another culture, to explain it and relate it to documents or events from one’s own’ (Byram, 1997:61).

In this section, participants were asked whether they think their English ‘native’ or ‘non-native’ teachers are able to interpret an event from the Chinese culture, and compare or relate it to events in the Western culture, in order to explore whether English ‘native’ and ‘non-native’ teachers at Chinese universities have the skills of interpreting, and relating to develop intercultural competence during English classes, according to participants’ perceptions.

5.3.3.1 English Major

Most of the participants from the English major group in this study believe that their English ‘non-native’ teachers (Chinese teachers) have the skills of interpreting and relating to teach intercultural competence, however, they still consider that their English ‘non-native’ teachers do not share enough knowledge of Western cultures at English classes. As in the focus groups, Participant 1 notes:

‘I think my teacher does have the ability to interpret and relate Western documents and events to us, but not often. As the festivals in China and Western countries are not really connected and related, sometimes it is hard to compare to be honest. The most common thing my teacher mentioned in English classes is the comparison between Chinese Spring Festival and Christmas’.

In addition, Participant 2 comments in the focus groups:

‘Our Chinese teacher mentioned the difference and comparison between Chinese festivals and Western festivals at English classes’.

The response from Participant 3 in the semi-structured interviews is interesting to the researcher, as this participant considers:

‘my Chinese teacher has the ability but she did not teach much in class. I think the reason might be that celebrating Western festivals is prohibited in some Chinese universities at the moment’.

According to Zhao (2017), Chinese universities have banned Christmas celebrations in an effort to protect young people from what is considered as the ‘corrosive’ influence of Western cultures. Chinese students are encouraged to be confident of their own cultural identity, but not be entangled with negativity to learn other cultures. However, cultural learning cannot be separated from language learning (Steely, 1984). Thus, English language teachers are still encouraged to teach knowledge of the target language culture and develop intercultural competence in the classroom which is not aim to prevent students from ‘corrosive’ influence of Western cultures, but to widen students’ knowledge and experience, as discussed by participant 1, 2 and 3, above.

Most of the participants from the English major group believe their English ‘native’ teachers have not acquired the skills of interpreting and relating to teach intercultural competence. As Participant 2 notes in the focus groups:

‘I am not sure if my English native teacher has the skills of interpreting and relating his culture to Chinese culture as he never mentioned any relevant knowledge at English classes’.

English ‘native’ teachers seem not to have certain intercultural and language knowledge which the participants in the English major group would like them to have. Participant 6 in this study considers that the reason may be that the teaching requirement for English ‘native’ teachers is not as strict as for English ‘non-native’ teachers. In some circumstances, English ‘native’ teachers have been employed with an associate degree or a high school diploma. In China, some provinces allow high school graduates or university graduates to teach, but not in Shanghai and Beijing (Qiang & Wolff, 2003). In this case, some English ‘native’ teachers might have higher degrees than high school diplomas, but they have not learned and been trained to teach the English language especially intercultural knowledge in their home country. Therefore, some English ‘native’ teachers might not provide language knowledge as ‘professionally’ as English

major students require. In other words, as English major students are not only required to develop their skills of speaking basic English, but also to understand the knowledge of English literature and culture thoroughly .

Participant 3 considers in the focus groups that:

‘My English native teacher have not mentioned that so far in English classes.’

However, Participant 1 has quite a positive attitude toward English ‘native’ teachers compared to other participants, he/she comments in the semi-structured interviews that:

‘I think my English native teacher has the ability to interpret and relate Western culture to Chinese culture, but he did not mention much in class. What I remember is that he compared Chinese Spring Festival with Christmas, or he just mentioned Western festivals without comparing them with Chinese festivals’.

According to the findings of this study, English major students positively believe their English ‘non-native’ teachers have better skills of interpreting and relating than their English ‘native’ teachers.

5.3.3.2 Non-English Major

However, participants from non-English major group believe their English ‘native’ teachers have the skills of interpreting and relating Chinese cultural events to Western cultural events to develop intercultural competence at English classes. According to He & Miller (2011), non-English major Chinese students, especially those with comparatively proficient English, do desire to be taught English by ‘native’ speakers. This finding seems to be opposite to the data collected and analysed from English major students. As Participant 4 notes in the focus groups:

‘Yes, I think my English native teacher has the ability to compare Chinese Spring Festival with Western Christmas’.

In addition, Participant 5 comments that:

‘My English native teacher has not only mentioned the difference between Chinese Spring Festival and Christmas, but also asked us for more details of Chinese culture which he does not understand’.

However, Participant 6 from the semi-structured interviews considers :

‘My English native teacher has the ability to interpret and relate Chinese cultural events to his home cultural events, but what we are taught at English classes is more about the eating habits of Chinese and Western people during their festivals which is not deep enough’.

To summarize, non-English major students believe their English ‘native’ teachers have the skills of interpreting and relating to culture, but the content of the cultural events they teach in English classes is limited, as the participants only remember the differences between Chinese Spring Festival and Christmas taught by their English ‘native’ teachers in the classroom.

Most Non-English major students also positively believe that their English ‘non-native’ teachers (Chinese teachers) have the skills of interpreting and relating Chinese cultural events to Western cultural events to develop intercultural competence at English classes. As Participant 4 comments in the focus groups:

‘My Chinese teacher did not only mention the difference between Chinese and Western festivals, but also taught us the different attitudes of Chinese people and Western people to deal with an international event’.

Similarly, Participant 5 notes that:

‘I remember my Chinese teacher told us the difference between Chinese people and Western people to react to the same thing which is quite interesting’.

However, Participant 6 considers further in the semi-structured interviews that:

‘my Chinese teacher can easily tell us the story behind every event and festival in China, but when she compared and related to Western events, she just briefly introduced Western festivals without stories and details’.

Thus, the findings reveal that most non-English major students believe their English ‘non-native’ teachers have the skills of relating and interpreting. According to the

participants, Chinese teachers seem to share more knowledge about Western events rather than just introducing the differences between the Chinese Spring Festival and Western Christmas. Even though the participants from non-English major groups admire the Chinese cultural knowledge taught by their English 'non-native' teachers, they still consider that their English 'non-native' teachers seem to have limited ability to compare and relate Chinese culture to Western culture as the relevant knowledge is not taught thoroughly in the classroom.

5.3.4 Critical Cultural Awareness

Critical cultural awareness is defined as 'the ability to evaluate, critically and on the basis of explicit criteria, perspectives, practices and products in one's own and other cultures and countries' (Byram, 1997 :63). There is a conscious need for critical cultural awareness to provide a communicative framework in which the local, the national, the global and his/her social identity when individuals come into contact between languages and cultures (Mendes & Moreira, 2005).

In this section, participants were asked whether they think their English 'native' or 'non-native' English teachers are able to evaluate, critically, perspectives and practices in their own and in English-speaking cultures, in order to discover whether their English 'native' or 'non-native' teachers at Chinese universities have been supported to acquire the knowledge and practice of cultural awareness in order to develop intercultural competence in English classes.

5.3.4.1 English Major

All the participants from English major group believe their English 'non-native' teachers (Chinese teachers) have critical cultural awareness to develop intercultural competence at English classes. As Participant 1 from the focus groups notes:

'I think my Chinese teacher has a positive attitude toward Western culture. She read many English books about Western culture. Also she has critical cultural awareness as she mentioned the difference of living habits, manners of dealing with people between Chinese and Western people without any disparagement or

flattering comments at English classes. But I can tell she prefers her own culture, I think there is nothing wrong with it’.

Participant 2 comments that:

‘my Chinese teacher enjoys watching Western and Chinese news and she always shares her comments with us at English classes. She would point out where she thought is not appropriate in both Chinese and Western news. In addition, she discussed with us about life styles, economics and many other areas of Western countries when something is relevant in the textbooks.

Furthermore, Participant 3 considers English ‘non-native’ teachers seem to have a critical evaluation of both Chinese and Western countries based on their knowledge and experience in the semi-structured interviews, as he/she notes that:

‘my Chinese teacher shared with us what kind of knowledge and experience she has learned after she studied in Western countries. Also she shared her comment on both Chinese and Western cultures, such as what we should learn from Western countries, where she thought Western countries need to be improved as well’.

All the participants from English major group consider that their English ‘native’ teachers have critical cultural awareness to develop intercultural competence, but those teachers did not teach or introduce the relevant knowledge in English classes. As

Participant 2 from focus group 1 notes:

‘I think he has the ability to critically evaluate Chinese and his own culture even though he did not directly mention the criteria for a good culture or a bad culture in English classes. And he is willing to ask and discuss with us about something he does not understand of Chinese culture’.

In addition, Participant 2 and Participant 3 both indicate that in the semi-structured interviews:

‘I suppose my English native teacher has the ability to evaluate critically Chinese and Western culture, but he did not mention it in English classes. I do not feel he has misleading assumption of Chinese culture either’.

The findings reveal that English major students think positively that their English 'native' teachers have the ability of critical cultural awareness, even though those teachers did not share any relevant comments at English classes. However, at least, these English 'native' teachers did not let their students feel uncomfortable when relevant Chinese culture is taught in their English classes, and those teachers are found to be willing to develop their understanding of the Chinese culture.

5.3.4.2 Non-English Major

Most participants from non-English major group believe their English 'non-native' teachers (Chinese teachers) have the ability of critical cultural awareness to develop intercultural competence in the classroom, however, some of the participants consider that they are not sure whether their English 'non-native' teachers can possess this kind of ability, as the teachers seem to focus more on finishing teaching tasks rather than sharing and introducing their understanding of both the Chinese and Western cultures.

Participant 4 from focus group 3 comments that:

'I think my Chinese teacher respects Western culture and she encourages us to learn more about Western culture as well. However, my Chinese teacher has limited understanding of Western culture, unlike English native teachers, they can share more stories and knowledge of their cultural background to us'.

Participant 5 from focus groups 4 notes:

'I am sure my Chinese teacher respects Western culture and sometimes we shared and discussed our opinions about something that happened in China or Western counties as well'.

However, Participant 6 is not sure whether their English 'non-native' teachers have the ability of critical cultural awareness, as he/she notes in the semi-structured interviews:

'My Chinese teacher told us the advanced aspects of Western culture in English classes but never shared bad aspects. It is hard for me to tell whether she has the ability of critical cultural awareness because she hardly shared her comments of

Chinese and Western culture with us, but focuses more on the contents of textbooks and finishing her teaching tasks’.

According to Hu (2003), English language teaching style in China is teacher-centered, however, English language teachers in China should be aware of their students’ suggestions and comments to improve their learning experience of the English language.

All the participants from non-English major group believe their English ‘native’ teachers have the ability of critical cultural awareness to develop intercultural competence in the classroom. As Participant 4 and 5 note in the focus groups that:

‘Our English native teacher can objectively share knowledge of Western culture with us, and he did not show any preference of his own cultural background. In addition, he is willing to ask and discuss with us about something he does not understand of Chinese culture’.

In addition, Participant 6 further considers in the semi-structured interviews that:

‘I am sure my English native teacher has the ability to be critical of cultural awareness. I remember once he mentioned mobile payment in class, he said it is so convenient to use mobile payment in China, but there is still much to be improved in Western countries. Also he is very curious about Chinese culture, he went to many famous tourist points in China, and followed Chinese people’s eating habits which is quite interesting’.

The findings show that non-English major students positively believe their English ‘native’ teachers’ have the ability of critical cultural awareness. One participant mentioned in the interview that they discussed the differences of the mobile payment methods in China and in Western countries with their English ‘native’ teachers; that can be seen as a piece of explicit evidence of how English ‘native’ teachers could show their abilities in critical cultural awareness if they refer to this in English classes. As in China, payment by mobile has become the most popular trend at the moment which has brought convenience to people in the society. Based on the answer of Participant 6, their English ‘native’ teachers believes that mobile payment still needs to be improved in the Western countries. Moreover, those teachers are found to be used to the life style

in China, as they enjoy following how Chinese people eat, dress, and spend their spare time in China.

5.4 Students' perceptions of development of Intercultural Competence by English 'native' teachers

5.4.1 English Major

To summarize, most of the English major students think their English 'native' teachers have a positive intercultural attitude toward Chinese cultures. Only a few of the participants show a little uncertainty as they do not receive enough relevant cultural knowledge from their English 'native' teachers in English classes. In addition, all the participants from English major groups believe their English 'native' teachers seem not possess enough skills of discovery and interaction as those teachers do not teach intercultural competence directly in English classes, they seem to only introduce and teach relevant cultural knowledge which is connected with the contents in textbooks. Moreover, most of the participants from English major group consider their English 'native' teachers do not have the skills of interpreting and relating Chinese culture to their own culture. All the participants from English major group believe that their English 'native' teachers have critical cultural awareness to develop intercultural competence in the classroom, but it is not taught or shown by their teachers at English classes. Therefore, according to the data collected from English major students in this study, their English 'native' teachers are considered to have critical awareness and willingness to learn about Chinese culture, but their development of intercultural competence at English classes still needs to be improved, as English major students hope to be taught more relevant cultural knowledge from their English 'native' teachers.

5.4.2 Non-English Major

Non-English major students believe that their English 'native' teachers have positive intercultural attitudes toward Chinese cultures. These teachers seem to be more curious and interested to talk about their daily life in China. All the participants from non-English major groups think their English 'native' teachers seem not to possess enough

skills of discovery and interaction as the teachers do not teach intercultural competence directly to English classes, they only introduce and teach relevant cultural knowledge which is connected with the contents of textbooks. In addition, non-English major students believe their English 'native' teachers have the skills of interpreting and relating Chinese cultural events to Western cultural events to develop intercultural competence at English classes. Then, all the participants from the non-English major group believe their English 'native' teachers have the ability of critical cultural awareness to develop intercultural competence in the classroom. Compared to the findings collected from English major students, non-English major students seem to be more confident of the development of intercultural competence by their English 'native' teachers in the classroom. In the perceptions of non-English major students, English 'native' teachers' skills of discovering knowledge of other cultures could be improved.

5.5 Students' perceptions of development of Intercultural Competence by English 'non-native' teachers

5.5.1 English Major

English major students seem to be satisfied with the development of the intercultural competence by their English 'non-native' teachers in the classroom, however, they are found to prefer to be taught the Western culture and stories by those teachers who have had with experience studying abroad. All the participants from English major groups consider their English 'non-native' teachers seem not to possess enough skills of discovery and interaction as those teachers do not teach the knowledge intercultural competence directly in English classes, they only introduce relevant cultural knowledge which is connected with the contents in textbooks. In addition, most of the participants from English major group think their English 'non-native' teachers have the skills of interpreting and relating to teach intercultural competence, but those teachers are suggested by their students to discuss and share more knowledge about the events from another culture at English classes. Moreover, all the participants from English major group consider their English 'non-native' teachers have critical cultural awareness which enables them to develop intercultural competence at English classes. To summarize, non-English major students think their English 'non-native' teachers have the ability to develop intercultural competence in English classes as they have positive

intercultural attitudes, critical cultural awareness and skills of interpreting and relating Western culture to Chinese culture. However, non-English major students consider that their English 'non-native' teachers should share more cultural knowledge instead of only focusing on contents of textbooks at English classes.

5.5.2 Non- English Major

Non-English major students believe their English 'non-native' teachers have positive intercultural attitudes toward Western cultures, however, which is more based on a 'tourist' level. All the participants from non-English major groups think their English 'non-native' teachers seem not to possess enough skills of discovery and interaction as the teachers do not teach the knowledge of intercultural competence directly at English classes, they only discuss relevant cultural knowledge which is connected with the contents in textbooks. Most of Non-English major students also believe their English 'non-native' teachers have the skills of interpreting and relating Chinese cultural events to Western cultural events, but they think their teachers seem to have limited ability to compare and relate Chinese culture to Western culture as the relevant knowledge is taught thoroughly by them. Then, most participants from non-English major group believe that their English 'non-native' teachers have the ability in critical cultural awareness to develop intercultural competence in the classroom, but some of them are not sure whether their English 'non-native' teachers can possess this kind of ability as the teachers focus more on finishing teaching tasks rather than sharing their knowledge of Chinese and Western cultures to their students. In summary, in the perceptions of non-English major students, English 'non-native' teachers seem not to develop intercultural competence effectively in English classes. Those teachers are found to focus more on finishing teaching tasks instead of sharing cultural knowledge thoroughly with their students.

5.6 Students' Preference for English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers

In this section, participants from both groups were asked about their preference for English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers during the interview in order to explore the difference between the preferences of the two groups of participants. However, the

findings from both groups are completely the opposite to those expressed in previous research. Peng (2006) states that English major students seem to enjoy their course better when they interact with English language 'native' speakers. In addition, according to early research by Liang (2002); 20 non-English major students' attitudes towards their English 'native' speaker teachers and 'non-native' speaker teachers in China. The findings reveal that even though students think the English accent plays an important role in English language teaching, this factor seems not to influence their positive attitudes towards their English 'non-native' teachers. The students believe that professional features such as 'being interesting', 'being prepared' and 'being qualified' in teachers are more necessary than a good accent. an American or British accent seems not be the critical reason that Chinese students desire English courses taught by 'native' speakers. Moreover, Chinese students are found to prefer to interact with English language teachers who have professional knowledge and colourful characters. In this study, English major students prefer the English courses taught by their English 'non-native' teachers as they think those teachers seem more knowledgeable in terms of culture than English 'native' teachers; in contrast, non-English major students in this study prefer the English courses taught by their English 'native' teachers, as they believe English 'native' teachers understand Western culture fully than their English 'non-native' teachers. Further discussion is noted as follows:

5.6.1 English Major

During the focus groups interviews, Participant 1 commented that it was easy to understand the knowledge taught and delivered by their English 'non-native' teachers as they shared the same cultural background which is quite important. Littlemore (2003) considers that a students' cultural background is likely to affect the ways in which he/she is able to use clues in the surrounding context to understand information and metaphors. Students are perhaps more likely to notice and understand information that corresponds to their cultural expectations, as he/she notes:

'Our Chinese teacher knows about both Chinese and Western cultural knowledge and can easily tell us the difference and how to use English properly as they know how to help us understand. But our English 'native' teacher is not very familiar

with Chinese culture so sometimes when he introduces Western stories, it is a little difficult to relate to my own life’.

In addition, both Participant 2 and Participant 3 from the semi-structured interviews believe their English ‘non-native’ teachers possess more cultural knowledge than their English ‘native’ teachers, as those English ‘non-native’ teachers have experience of studying abroad, so it seems to be that they understand both Western and Chinese culture well. As Participant 2 notes:

‘My Chinese teacher has abundant knowledge of Western and Chinese culture as she shared mythologies of ancient Rome with us in class. Even though our English ‘native’ teacher has a positive attitude towards learning Chinese culture, sometimes he needs to ask us questions to know more about it’.

Participant 3 explains:

‘It is obvious that Chinese teachers who have more experience studying abroad, share more cultural knowledge with us in class. As a student, I can learn more new things from this kind of teacher.’

According to the data collected from English major students in this study, English ‘non-native’ teachers are found to have had experience studying abroad for few years which seems very helpful for those students in understanding both Chinese and Western culture by someone who shares the same cultural background as well as understand the Western culture.

5.6.2 Non-English Major

However, in this study, non-English major students are found to hold different perceptions of their English ‘native’ teachers compared to the data collected from English major students. Non-English major students are found to prefer English ‘native’ teachers than their English ‘non-native’ teachers as the participants believe their English ‘native’ teachers have thorough understanding of the Western culture. As Participant 4 notes in the focus groups that:

‘I think my English ‘native’ teacher knows more about Western culture than a Chinese teacher so they can introduce cultural knowledge deeply to us. In addition, he shared his experience in China and his own understanding of Chinese culture with us as well’.

The findings also reveal that non-English major students are willing to learn the knowledge of the Western culture as well as the understanding of Chinese culture delivered by their English ‘native’ teachers which can result, for them, in more enjoyable courses than English courses by their English ‘non-native’ teachers. For example, Participant 5 discusses in the semi-structured interviews that:

‘Even though my Chinese teacher has a short-term experience studying abroad, our English ‘native’ teacher still knows more about Western culture than her. As students, we are more curious to learn about Western culture as we know Chinese culture quite well’.

The English teaching materials and methodologies seem different between English major and non-English major teachers. According to English major students in this study, nearly all of their English ‘non-native’ teachers have experience of studying abroad for a few years. However, some of English ‘non-native’ teachers who teach non-English major students have trained in Western countries but only for a short-term time which seems not enough to build up a solid understanding of Western culture. Also, Participant 6 notes in the semi-structured interviews that:

‘My Chinese teacher knows deeply about ancient Chinese cultures so she always mentioned that to us in class, but I am more curious to learn about Western culture which my English ‘native’ teacher helped me understand more about.

Thus it can be seen, Chinese students seem to be more curious to learn about Western cultures as they are familiar with their own cultural background already. However, English ‘non-native’ teachers are found only to introduce the Western cultural knowledge in English classes compared to their English ‘native’ teachers. Therefore, non-English major students at a Chinese university seem to prefer English ‘native’ teachers more than ‘non-native’ teachers as those students believe their English ‘native’ teachers have a deeper understanding of Western cultures, and they are more willing

and curious to learn the knowledge of the Western culture from their English 'native' teachers .

5.7 Students' perceptions of English language teachers' knowledge of intercultural competence

Byram defines knowledge of intercultural competence as knowledge of social groups and their products and practices in one's own and in one's interlocutor's country, and of the general processes of societal and individual interaction' (Byram, 1997: 58). In English classrooms, teachers must be prepared with thorough knowledge of the English language, and spend time guiding students to reflect on their preconceived ideas or perceptions before entering into studies of other cultures (Moeller & Nugent, 2014).

In this section, participants were asked whether they think their English 'native' or 'non-native' teachers have knowledge of social groups and practices in both cultures, that is, in English-speaking culture and in Chinese culture, to illustrate whether English 'native' or 'non-native' teachers at Chinese universities have a critical cultural awareness to develop intercultural competence in English classes.

Previously, Han (2011) conducted a survey among 30 English language English teachers in Chinese universities to discover how they conceptualize intercultural competence and relate it to their teaching practice. The findings reveal that although many English language teachers in China could make a distinction between the intercultural approach and the communicative approach to English language teaching, their knowledge of intercultural competence and its relevance to English language teaching is ambiguous, in other words, the intercultural dimension in their English language teaching needs to be enhanced. Some Chinese teachers do not have a clear understanding of the importance of acquiring intercultural skills at university or teaching the target language culture in an integrated way. In addition, the findings also show that there is limited teaching content of intercultural knowledge for the teachers which leads to the lack of teachers' knowledge of the specific aspects of the target language as well as the inadequacy of cultural elements in the teaching materials. However, in this study, most English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers are found to acquire the knowledge of

intercultural competence based on the students' perceptions. Further details of this discussion are listed below.

5.7.1 English Major

Most of the participants from the English major group think their English 'non-native' teachers (Chinese teachers) have knowledge of intercultural competence, but some students are not sure whether those teachers have a deep understanding of the intercultural competence as they seem to focus more on teaching from textbooks in English classes without teaching cultural knowledge to students. As Participant 3 from focus group 2 notes:

'I think my grammar teacher has the knowledge of intercultural competence based on her experience abroad, but other English teachers focus more on the knowledge of textbooks'.

The participants positively believe that their English 'non-native' teachers have the knowledge of intercultural competence as they have experience studying abroad and willingness to learn and share the Western culture with students. As Participant 1 discusses in the semi-structured interviews:

'Our Chinese teacher has at least 6-month studying abroad experience, so I think they have quite good understanding of Western culture, and they know how to compare Chinese and Western cultures in different ways'.

Participant 2 also notes that:

'Our Chinese teacher has cultural knowledge of Chinese and Western festivals, and they desire to discover more about Western culture when she can get a chance to go abroad'.

However, most of the English major students in this study are not sure whether their English 'native' teachers have knowledge of intercultural competence as they seem to only have a 'surface' understanding of the Chinese culture, and those teachers are found to focus on improving speaking skills of students rather than widening their cultural knowledge in English classes. As Participant 1 from focus group 1 notes:

‘our English ‘native’ teacher knows deeply about Western culture, but he only knows plain knowledge of Chinese culture’.

In addition, Participant 3 comments in the focus groups that:

‘my English ‘native’ teacher focus more on improving our English speaking skills in English classes.

However, some English major students in this study believe their English ‘native’ teachers have the ability to acquire the knowledge of intercultural competence as they have an obvious interest in understanding the Chinese culture, and a deep understanding of the Western culture. As Participant 2 discusses in the semi-structured interviews that:

‘our English ‘native’ teacher know deeply about Western culture as he starts learning Chinese language and shows a massive interest in Chinese culture’.

5.7.2 Non-English Major

For non-English major students, most of the participants consider that their English ‘non-native’ teachers (Chinese teachers) have a certain level of intercultural knowledge as they have experienced training abroad and have willingness to discuss cultural knowledge with students in and after class in the focus groups. As Participant 4 notes:

‘I think my Chinese teacher has the knowledge of intercultural competence as they teach cultural knowledge in class and discuss with us after class to let us understand more different cultures’.

Participant 5 answers:

‘I think my Chinese teacher has some knowledge of intercultural competence as she has experience studying abroad’.

However, a few participants are uncertain of their English ‘non-native’ teachers’ intercultural knowledge, as the teachers do not discuss enough cultural knowledge at English classes in the students’ perceptions. For example, Participant discusses in the semi-structured interviews that:

‘I don’t know if my Chinese teacher has the knowledge of intercultural competence or not as she didn’t mention much in class’.

It is quite interesting to find out that students who have been taught by the same English language teacher have totally different perceptions of their English ‘non-native’ teachers. For example, Participant 4 considers that the cultural knowledge is shared and taught by their English ‘non-native’ teachers in and after class, while Participant 6 thinks that the cultural knowledge is hardly mentioned or taught by their teachers. This difference might be caused by the amount of time the student focused on listening to their teachers during the English classes as well as their language learning motivation.

However, all the participants from the non-English major group strongly believe their English ‘native’ teachers have knowledge of intercultural competence. Some participants think their English ‘native’ teachers are willing to discuss cultural knowledge with them as Participant 4 comments in the focus groups:

‘I think both my Chinese and English ‘native’ teacher have the knowledge of intercultural competence as they teach cultural knowledge in class and discuss with us after class to let us understand more different cultures’.

Besides, those students believe their English ‘native’ teachers acquire the ability to understand the Chinese culture as they have been in China for years. For example, Participant 5 notes in the focus groups:

‘My English ‘native’ teacher has experience living in China for more than six years. So it is easy to pick up the knowledge of intercultural competence if you have time to experience another culture’.

The findings also reveal that English ‘native’ teachers’ willingness and interest to learn and understand the Chinese culture is regarded as the standard of whether their English language teachers have knowledge of intercultural competence in participants’ perceptions. As Participant 6 discusses in the semi-structured interviews that:

‘I think my English ‘native’ teacher has the knowledge, because he understands a lot of Western culture and he is very interested to know about Chinese culture and can tell us the difference as well’.

Both English major and non-English major students have similar perceptions of their English 'non-native' teachers (Chinese teachers) about their knowledge of intercultural competence, as most of them positively believe that their English 'non-native' teachers have intercultural knowledge, as they are found to be willing to explore and share cultural knowledge with students as well as their experience of studying abroad. However, their perceptions of the intercultural knowledge of their English 'native' teachers are quite different. English major students believe their English 'native' teachers have basic Chinese cultural knowledge, and only focus on developing speaking skills in English classes; non-English major students consider their English 'native' teachers have a high level of intercultural knowledge as a result of the teachers' willingness to discuss and learn Chinese culture as well as their long-term experience of living in China. The difference in the attitudes toward English 'native' teachers between English major and non-English major students might be caused by the different levels of English language course required by both groups of students. The English teaching task for English 'native' teachers to teach English major students is more complex compared to teaching non-English major students. Therefore, English 'native' teachers might not have enough time to discuss other cultural topics to English major students in the classroom. In addition, non-English major students seem to enjoy English language courses taught by English 'native' teachers, because the only mission for English 'native' teachers is to improve students' speaking skills; there are found to be more interesting topics around cultures to discuss at English classes between teachers and non-English major students, instead of just focusing on textbooks.

5.8 Students' perceptions of training in Intercultural Competence of English language teachers

In this section, participants were asked whether they think their English 'native' or 'non-native' teachers have been trained to teach intercultural competence, in order to explore whether English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers at Chinese universities have been trained to develop intercultural competence based on student participants' perceptions of English classes.

5.8.1 English Major

For English major students, nearly all of the participants believe their English ‘non-native’ teachers are trained to teach intercultural competence at English classes. However, some students have no idea whether their teachers are trained as they do not see intercultural competence is developed between in the classroom. For example, Participant 1 notes in the focus groups:

‘I don’t think my Chinese teacher is trained as she/he did not mention much in class but they might be introduced to relevant knowledge during other trainings’.

In addition, some other participants strongly believe their English ‘non-native’ teachers have relevant knowledge of intercultural competence even though they might not be trained according to the students’ perceptions. As Participant 2 mentions:

‘I have no idea if my Chinese teacher is trained in specific knowledge of intercultural competence or not. But I think they might have learned relevant knowledge from other teaching trainings’.

However, a few of the participants consider their English ‘non-native’ teachers have had no training in teaching intercultural competence due to the reason that those teachers are found to focus more on the content of textbooks, and developing basic skills in the English language instead of developing their ability in intercultural competence. As Participant 3 considers in the semi-structured interviews:

‘I don’t think my Chinese teacher is trained to teach intercultural competence, as they focus more on teaching through textbooks, grammar knowledge and improving our spoken skills’.

Participants from English major groups seem to have similar perceptions of intercultural competence training of their English ‘native’ teachers and their ‘non-native’ teachers. The majority of them from the focus groups indicate that they are not sure whether their English ‘native’ teachers are trained to teach intercultural competence in English classes. Some participants consider their English ‘native’ teachers have basic knowledge of intercultural competence as they have experience of living in China, even though they might not be trained to teach intercultural competence in the classroom. As Participant 1 notes:

‘As for English ‘native’ teachers, most of them have lived in China for six or seven years, even though they are not trained, they might have a basic understanding of intercultural competence’.

Participant 2 considers:

‘I have no idea if my Chinese teacher is trained in specific knowledge of intercultural competence or not. But I think they might have learned relevant knowledge from other teaching trainings’.

However, a few of the participants consider that their English ‘non-native’ teachers have had no training of teaching intercultural competence due to the reason that their English ‘non-native’ teachers are found to focus more on the content of textbooks and developing basic skills of English language instead of focusing on the development of intercultural competence in the classroom. As Participant 3 notes in the semi-structured interviews:

‘I don’t think my Chinese teacher is trained to teach intercultural competence, as they focus more on teaching through textbooks, grammar knowledge and improving our spoken skills’.

5.8.2 Non-English Major

However, compared to the data collected from English major students, the findings of students’ perceptions of intercultural training of their English language teachers from non-English major groups seem to be more positive. Even though the participants from non-English major groups are not totally sure whether their English ‘native’ or ‘non-native’ teachers have been trained to teach intercultural competence, most of them seem positively to believe that both of their English language teachers have the ability to teach intercultural competence in English classes. As Participant 4 notes in the focus groups that:

‘I know my English teachers have different trainings but I’m not sure whether intercultural competence is trained or not. Sometimes they mention cultural knowledge in class so they might have been trained’.

This participant assumes his/her English language teachers might have been trained to teach intercultural competence, as English language teachers have taught relevant topics around intercultural competence in English classes. Other participants also consider their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers have been trained to teach intercultural competence, as Participant 5 discusses in the focus groups that:

'I think they might have been trained in the knowledge of intercultural competence when my English teachers studied abroad as visiting scholars. I am not very sure as they didn't mention in class'.

This participant assumes his/her English teachers have been trained to teach intercultural competence based on the teachers' experiences of studying abroad as visiting scholars, however, those English language teachers did not discuss the details of where they had been trained and taught when they were in Western countries.

Participant 6 considers that:

'My Chinese teacher has experience studying in the UK as a visiting scholar so she might be trained about intercultural competence at that time. But I am not very sure'.

When asked about the training in intercultural competence of English 'native' teachers, participants who are of non-English major students think their teachers might have been trained as they assume those teachers have trained how to teach the English language in a Chinese university curriculum. In addition, most of their English 'native' teachers have been in China for many years as they might develop the knowledge by themselves. As Participant 6 notes in the semi-structured interviews:

'I think my English native teacher might have been trained to teach the knowledge of intercultural competence as he has been in China for six years already, he might know or be told the way to teach English to Chinese students, also he knows basic knowledge of Chinese culture.'

5.9 Students' Suggestions for Developing Intercultural Competence

In this section, participants were asked what support they wanted from their university to help them develop intercultural competence in English classes to explore how

English major and non-English major students develop the ability of intercultural competence with the support of their English language teachers and English language departments at their university.

5.9.1 English Major

The participants from the English major focus groups show a strong desire to develop intercultural competence, and they are willing to have more opportunities to practise speaking English with English 'native' speakers and other English major students. As Participant 1 notes:

'I hope my university will hold more after-class activities such as an English presentation competition and an English corner. Also, I think my teachers could try to set up a website which allows us to talk face-to face talk to English 'native' speakers'.

In addition, English major students are curious about how English major students from other universities receive and develop intercultural competence in English classes as they desire to share experience with other English major students to find an effective way to improve their English language proficiency and their ability in intercultural competence. As Participant 2 comments that:

'I hope my university can give us more chances to share experiences with English major students from other universities to find out if they have any tips for learning English and ideas of intercultural competence as well'.

Apart from sharing experiences with English major students from other universities, participants hope their university could offer them opportunities to study abroad as exchange students to learn and experience different cultures by themselves. Participant 3 further discusses in the semi-structured interviews that:

'I would like to have more chances to study abroad as an exchange student to improve my English, and hope the English department in my university can support us to celebrate Western festivals. In addition, it will be better if we can share experiences with English major students from other universities'.

5.9.2 Non- English Major

The participants from non-English major focus groups hope that the English language departments at their university will offer more chances for them to study or visit abroad as exchange students or visitors for a short period. As Participant 5 notes:

‘I hope our English department will organise more chances for us to study abroad as international exchange students or intercultural volunteers’.

Apart from asking for opportunities to study abroad as exchange students, non-English major students consider that it would be better if the library stock more relevant English language books about Western cultures which are available for them to read. As Participant 4 considers in the semi-structured interviews that:

‘I hope there will be more English books about Western cultures in our library for us to read. Also If the English department organise activities such as international exchange students and international volunteers will be very helpful for us to know different cultures’.

In addition, non-English major students consider that they are not given as many chances by their English language teachers to use and speak English as English major students. Therefore, the participants from non-English major groups suggest their university to offer more opportunities for them to practice speaking English. As Participant 6 notes in the semi-structured interviews that:

‘I just want to attend more activities which can help me to get more chances to speak and use English’.

5.10 The place of literature in this discussion

In this section, the comparisons between this study and other relevant research are discussed referring to the findings of this study. In addition, discussions are divided into themes which have been previously introduced and discussed with reference to the participant data in the finding chapter.

5.10.1 Motivation to Learn English

In this study, both English major and non-English major students are found to be instrumentally motivated to learn the English language as those students are required to pass English exams to proceed to successful graduation from university, and they desire to be competitive in the future job market where English language proficiency is regarded as a crucial requirement. This finding confirms the discussions from previous studies, according to Taguchi et al. (2009) and Dornyei & Yu (2014), Chinese students are found to be instrumentally motivated to learn the English language due to the fact that many Chinese students are keen on raising their English language proficiency test scores as English language proficiency is strongly related to successful job-hunting in China which is regarded as a global marketplace. In addition, non-English major students are found to be more negative and more instrumentally motivated to learn the English language than English major students as non-English major students seem a little tired of learning the English language since they started English learning from primary school. In addition, non-English major students are required by the university to spend more time and attention on their own major subjects such as Accounting and Finance.

Non-English major students in this study are found to only have instrumental motivation to study the English language which is in agreement with Zhou's (2012:1319) study which notes several general problems of non-English major students learning the English language in China which are: Lack of purpose for learning. The purpose of the majority of students in learning the English language is just for grades and future work; lack of experience. Those students are not given enough practice as they communicate rarely in real-life English communication contexts. They always feel they are not fully ready to use English authentically; lack of confidence. When they are asked to communicate in the target language they are lacking in self-confidence and doubting their own capacity for using the English language to communicate'. As the participants from non-English major groups in this study consider that they hardly have opportunity to use and practise English as they are required to pass English exams to proceed graduation and better job options in the future.

However, English major students in this study are found to have integrative and potential integrative motivation to learn the English language as they would like to explore different cultures by using the English language as a medium. In addition, they wish to have more opportunities to speak and practise English outside classes to develop their English language proficiency. According to Li and Pan (2009), instrumental motivation plays an extremely important role in English language learning for English major students; the reasons are similar with the findings of this study, as those students learn the English language to be competitive in their future employment. In addition, English major students' integrative motivation is discussed by participants from English major groups who notes that : 'I learn English because I am interested in the social relationship and culture of English speaking people'; 'Since the European and American countries have their unique ways of thinking, I learn English for a better knowledge of them'; 'I learn English to have my personal experience of their foreign culture' (Li & Pan, 2009:125). These findings concur with the findings in this study, in that English major students desire to experience Western cultures and have more opportunities to communicate with English 'native' speakers. However, they seem not to be interested in learning the English language in the ways that English 'native' teachers teach in this study.

5.10.2 Students' perceptions of development of Intercultural Competence in English Class

To refer to Byram's (1997) model of intercultural competence, students' perceptions of the knowledge of intercultural competence of their English teachers is discussed in this section with reference to the other four terms: Intercultural attitude, Skills of discovery and interaction, Skills of interpreting and relating as well as Critical cultural awareness.

5.10.2.1 Students' perceptions of development of Intercultural Competence by English 'native' teachers

Most of the English major students believe their English 'native' teachers have a positive intercultural attitude toward Chinese cultures. Only a few of them shows some uncertainty as their English 'native' teachers seem not to make an effort in discussing relevant cultural knowledge with students in English classes. All the participants from English major groups think their English 'native' teachers seem not to possess enough

skills of discovery and interaction as the teachers do not teach intercultural competence directly in English classes, they only introduce relevant cultural knowledge to students which is connected with the contents of textbooks. Most of the participants from the English major group think their English 'native' teachers do not have skills of interpreting and relating Chinese culture to their own culture. All the participants from English major group consider their English 'native' teachers have critical cultural awareness in developing intercultural competence, but they do not discuss it in English classes. Most of the English major students are not sure whether their English 'native' teachers have the knowledge of intercultural competence as they are found to only have basic knowledge of Chinese cultures, and they focus more on improving speaking skills of students rather than widening their cultural knowledge at English classes. Therefore, based on English major students' perceptions, English 'native' teachers have critical awareness and willingness to learn about Chinese culture, but the development of intercultural competence at English classes still needs to be improved as those teachers do not teach enough cultural knowledge to English major students in the classroom.

Non-English major students think their English 'native' teachers have a positive intercultural attitude toward Chinese cultures. English 'native' teachers seem to be more curious and interested to talk about their daily life with their students in China in comparison. All the participants from non-English major groups believe their English 'native' teachers seem not to possess enough skills of discovery and interaction as those teachers do not teach intercultural competence directly in English classes, but they introduce relevant cultural knowledge which is connected with the contents in textbooks. Non-English major students have positive attitudes toward English 'native' teachers and think they have the skills of interpreting and relating Chinese cultural events to Western cultural events to develop intercultural competence in English classes. All the participants from the non-English major group consider that their English 'native' teachers have the ability of critical cultural awareness to develop intercultural competence in the classroom. All the participants from non-English major group positively believe their English 'native' teachers have the knowledge of intercultural competence. Some students think their English 'native' teachers are willing to discuss cultural knowledge with them in English classes. Compared to the findings of English major students, non-English major students seem more confident about the

development of intercultural competence by their English 'native' teachers. In the perceptions of non-English major students, only skills of discovery and interaction of English 'native' teachers are required to be improved.

5.10.2.2 Students' perceptions of development of Intercultural Competence by English 'non-native' teachers

English major students are found to be satisfied with their English 'non-native' teachers' intercultural attitude, but they prefer and trust more of the Western culture and stories taught by those teachers who have had experience studying abroad. All the participants from English major groups think their English 'non-native' teachers seem not to possess enough skills of discovery and interaction as the teachers do not teach intercultural competence directly in English classes, as they only mention relevant cultural knowledge which is connected with the contents of textbooks in the classroom. Most of the participants from English major group think their English 'non-native' teachers have the skills of interpreting and relating to teach intercultural competence, but they do not teach the events from another culture often at English classes. All the participants from English major group consider their English 'non-native' teachers have critical cultural awareness to develop intercultural competence at English classes. To summarize, non-English major students think their English 'non-native' teachers have the ability to develop intercultural competence in English classes as they have positive intercultural attitudes, critical cultural awareness and skills of interpreting and relating Western culture to Chinese culture. Most of the participants from English major group consider those teachers have the knowledge of intercultural competence, but some students are not sure about their teachers' knowledge level as they seem to focus more on teaching textbooks in English classes without mentioning cultural knowledge to students. However, it is suggested, by English major students, that English 'non-native' teachers should share more cultural knowledge instead of only focusing on contents of textbooks at English classes.

Non-English major students think their English 'non-native' teachers have positive intercultural attitudes toward Western cultures which is more based on a 'tourist' level. All the participants from non-English major groups believe their English 'non-native' teachers seem not to possess enough skills of discovery and interaction as the teachers

do not teach intercultural competence directly at English classes, as they only introduce relevant cultural knowledge which is connected with the contents in textbooks. Most of the non-English major students also have positive attitudes toward English 'non-native' teachers and think they have the skills of interpreting and relating Chinese cultural events to Western cultural events, however, they think their teachers seem to have limited ability to compare and relate Chinese culture to Western culture as they are not taught about the relation between the Chinese culture and the Western culture thoroughly. Most participants from the non-English major group consider their English 'non-native' teachers have the ability of critical cultural awareness to develop intercultural competence, but some of them think they are not sure whether those teachers possess this kind of ability as they are found to focus more on finishing teaching tasks rather than sharing their comments on Chinese and Western cultures. For non-English major students, most of the participants think their English 'non-native' teachers have a certain level of intercultural knowledge as they have experience training abroad and are willing to discuss cultural knowledge with students in and after class. In summary, in the perceptions of non-English major students, English 'non-native' teachers seem not to develop intercultural competence effectively during English classes. They focus more on finishing teaching tasks as well as only sharing basic cultural knowledge with students.

To summarize, according to the perceptions of both English major and non-English major students, intercultural competence is not successfully developed in classes by their English language teachers (both native and non-native teachers), as their teachers do not discuss and share enough cultural knowledge with the students. Instead, some teachers focus more on teaching through the textbooks and grammar knowledge in English classes. Compared to the research conducted by Han & Song (2011), English language teachers in Chinese universities are not found to be effectively developing intercultural competence at English classes which is similar to the findings of this study. According to Han & Song (2011), limited teaching content of intercultural education is found at English classes as the results of teachers' unfamiliarity with specific aspects of the target cultures as well as the inadequacy of cultural elements in the teaching materials. The participants in this study agree that their English language teachers seldom refer to cultural knowledge and events at classes. In addition, students in this

study note that English language teachers focused more on teaching through the textbooks; the reason is found in the statements of English teachers in Han&Song's (2011:190) study, which is: 'Even if these English teachers are willing to develop students' intercultural competence in the classroom, and most claimed to have devoted a large proportion of time to cultural teaching, the intercultural dimension in their English language teaching needs to be enhanced'.

5.10.3 Students' Preference for English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers

In this study, the findings reveal that English major students prefer their English 'non-native' teachers as they believe those teachers seem to be more knowledgeable about cultures than their English 'native' teachers; non-English major students prefer English 'native' teachers as they believe those teachers have thorough knowledge of the Western culture. According to He and Miller (2011), non-English major students in Chinese universities are found to prefer English 'native' teachers than 'non-native' teachers, but the reasons are slightly different referring to this study: in He and Miller's (2011) study, Chinese students believe English courses at university should be taught solely by English 'native' teachers rather than 'non-native' teachers; in addition, the majority of the students prefer to sound like a English 'native' speaker even though they agree that some English 'non-native' speaking teachers can also speak 'standard English'. In this study, non-English major students prefer English 'native' teachers as the students desire develop their understanding of Western cultures.

However, according to Peng (2006), English major students seem to enjoy their English courses better when they interact with English 'native' speakers. This is opposite to the findings in this study, as English major students in this study believe English 'non-native' teachers have more knowledge and experience of teaching the language than English 'native' teachers. In addition, the speaking skills of English 'non-native' teachers in this context are considered to be as good as English 'native' teachers.

Liang (2002) conducted a survey of 20 non-English major students' attitudes towards their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers; the findings show that even though students think the English accent plays an important role in English teaching, this factor

seems not to influence their positive attitudes towards English 'non-native' teachers. However, in this study, non-English major students are found to be a little tired of learning the English language from their English 'non-native' teachers as those teachers are found to focus more on teaching through textbooks and grammar knowledge instead of introducing cultural knowledge in English classes; the students feel less stressed when they are taught by English 'native' teachers, as they want to learn Western cultural knowledge shared by their English 'native' teachers.

5.11 Conclusion

The findings of this study reveal that non-English major students only have instrumental motivation towards learning the English language, however, English major students show more potential integrative and integrative motivation besides instrumental motivation; according to the perceptions of both English major and non-English major students, intercultural competence is not successfully developed in classes by their English language teachers (both native and non-native teachers) as their teachers do not discuss and share enough cultural knowledge to the students. Instead, some teachers focus more on teaching through the textbooks and grammar knowledge at English classes. English major students prefer their English 'non-native' teachers as they think those teachers have more knowledgeable of both Chinese and Western cultures than English 'native' teachers; non-English major students prefer English 'native' teachers as they believe those teachers understand the Western culture thoroughly. English major student groups state that their English language teachers might have been trained to teach intercultural competence as the majority of them indicate that they are not sure whether their English 'native' teachers are trained to teach intercultural competence in English classes; even though non-English major groups are not totally sure whether their English language teachers have been trained to teach the knowledge of intercultural competence, most of them seem positively to believe their teachers have the ability to teach intercultural competence in English classes. English major students have a strong desire to develop intercultural competence and have suggested the university to organize more opportunities to practise speaking English with English 'native' speakers and English major students from other universities; non-English major students wish the English language

departments at their university to offer more opportunities for them to study or visit abroad as exchange students for a short period.

Chapter 6: Conclusions

6.1 Introduction

This chapter aims to evaluate and discuss findings from Chapter 5 which relate to the research questions and the aims of this study. Each research question will be considered in terms of the findings. Whether or not the research questions are answered and how they are answered will also be discussed. In addition, this section will set out a summary of the research so far and consider implications of the findings, potential limitations of the current research, recommendations and consider if any future research should be done. Moreover, the academic and personal growth of the researcher during the period as a PhD student will also be referred.

6.1.1 Chapter Summaries

This study set out to explore English major and non-English major students' perceptions of their motivation to learn the English language and the development of the intercultural competence by their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers in a Chinese university. The type of intercultural competence in English language education has been widely discussed in the literature. However, the difference between English learning motivation between English and non-English major students and their perceptions of their English language teachers have been overlooked in previous studies. Therefore, the researcher aims to understand how those English language teachers could best support students' requirements of intercultural learning in the Chinese context as discussed in Chapter 1. Chapter 2 discussed the reasons for the popularity of English language education in China, and the challenges it has brought to both English language teachers and their students. In addition, the policies which were established by the Chinese government to improve intercultural learning in English language education were introduced and discussed. Chapter 3 discussed the literature around intercultural competence, native speakerism, English learners' motivation and language identity which underpinned this study. This chapter also analysed previous studies of students' English learning motivation and their perceptions of English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers in the Chinese context.

Chapter 4 set out the qualitative interpretative research design which arose from Byram's (1997) intercultural competence model as the theoretical framework, and planned to use focus groups and semi-structured in-depth interviews to employ the methodology for this study as this approach enabled the researcher to collect rich and in-depth data. Furthermore, the reasons for choosing Byram's (1997) intercultural competence model as the theoretical framework were that this model contains a clear definition of each component of intercultural competence which is in relation to the focus of this research, and help the participants to understand the meaning of intercultural competence, and it provides a clear guidance would be given to the participants to answer questions during interviews. Chapter 5 set out the full discussion and analysis of the key findings from the data collected from the participants in this study which included Chinese university students' motivation to learn English, those students' perceptions of how their English teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom, and their suggestions to improve English learning experience in Chinese universities.

The research questions which relate to the title are the following:

- In what ways do University students perceive intercultural competence and the role of their University teachers in contributing to its development in English classes at Chinese universities?
- To what extent is intercultural competence developed between English teachers (both 'native' and non 'native') and Chinese university students?
- In what ways do students think intercultural competence could be developed more effectively in English departments at Chinese universities?
- To what extent do English major and non-English major students differ in their motivation to learn English and in their perceptions of how their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom of their Chinese university?

The aims which support the research questions are:

- To examine and discover Chinese university students' perceptions of 'native' English-speaking teachers and 'non-native' English teachers in the Chinese university .
- To identify and explore how both 'native' and 'non-native' English teachers develop intercultural competence in English classes based on students' perceptions in the Chinese university.
- To explore in what ways students will be able to develop their understanding of intercultural competence based on students' perceptions in the Chinese university.
- To compare and discuss the difference in students' motivation to learn English and their perceptions of how their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom of their Chinese university.

Each of the research questions for this study will be considered in turn. Whether or not and how they are answered by the findings will be discussed in Chapter 5.

6.2.1 In what ways do university students perceive intercultural competence and the role of their University teachers in contributing to its development in English classes at Chinese universities?

This research question is set out to explore In what ways do university students perceive intercultural competence and how do they perceive their university teachers' contribution the development of intercultural competence in English classes. This question was answered through the interview question which was in two parts. (Please see Appendix 1).

To discover the ways in which university students perceive the development of the intercultural competence by their English language teachers, the participants were asked whether they were taught intercultural competence directly in English classes and in what ways have they received any understanding of intercultural competence from their English language teachers for both focus groups and semi-structured in depth interviews. The findings show that all the participants from both English major

and non-English major groups perceive that the concept of intercultural competence was not taught directly in English classes; and the students have developed the understanding of intercultural competence from their English language teachers as the teachers introduced the reference to Western cultural background and events into the classes. They did this by relating the articles in the textbooks to Western cultures and engaging students in discussion by comparing the differences between the Chinese and Western culture.

In addition, in order to discover how students perceive their English language teachers' contribution to the development of intercultural competence in English classrooms, the participants were asked whether their English language teachers show their knowledge of intercultural competence in English classes and whether their English language teachers have been trained to teach intercultural competence in their opinions. The findings reveal that all the participants believe their English language teachers have not been trained to teach intercultural competence in English classes. The participants from English major groups noted that their English language teachers do not show the knowledge of intercultural competence to the students directly, they only mention something relevant they know already, as they think the teaching task for their English language teachers is mainly to help them pass the exams. The participants from non-English major groups think English 'native' teachers sometimes show their knowledge of intercultural competence by comparing the difference between Chinese and Western cultures, however, the students do not perceive their English 'non-native' teachers have enough capacity in teaching and developing intercultural competence in the classroom as those teachers appear to focus more on teaching through textbooks.

Therefore, the researcher believes this research question is answered by the findings. In the Chinese university where this research is undertaken, the students perceive that the knowledge of intercultural competence is not directly taught from their English language teachers as they consider that their English language teachers have not been trained to teach the knowledge of intercultural competence in English classes. However, sometimes those teachers introduce Western cultural events and compare the difference between the Chinese and Western culture in English classes. English 'non-native' teachers are recognized as mainly teaching through textbooks to help the

students to pass the exams rather than teaching more cultural knowledge in English classes. In summary, this question is answered through the interview questions and discussion from the findings.

6.2.2 To what extent is intercultural competence developed between English teachers (both 'native' and non 'native') and Chinese university students?

To answer this research question, the participants were asked five sub-questions during the interviews based on the five components of Byram (1997)'s intercultural competence model to discuss how intercultural competence has developed between English language teachers and students in the Chinese university. Each question was answered and discussed in the findings with details and given examples by the participants. Questions are listed in the appendix (see Appendix 1).

This particular finding shows that the participants from English major and non-English major groups perceive their English 'non-native' teachers to have intercultural knowledge because their 'non-native' teachers show willingness to explore, to share and discuss cultural knowledge with the students in the classroom. In addition, the findings reveal that English 'non-native' teachers who have had the experience of studying abroad are willing to share their stories of what happened when they were in Western countries with the students. The participants are motivated and encouraged by those teachers to experience the Western culture by themselves when they have opportunities to travel or study abroad. However, these groups of English major students believe their English 'native' teachers only have basic knowledge of Chinese culture and focus more on developing students' speaking skills in English classes; the participants from the non-English major groups believe their English 'native' teachers have a higher level of intercultural knowledge than their 'non-native' teachers as a result of the 'native' teachers' willingness to discuss and explore Chinese culture, as well as their long-term experience of living in China which provided them with a deeper understanding of the Chinese culture.

In addition, the findings show that these groups of English major students believe their English 'native' teachers have not acquired the skills of understanding the Chinese culture and relating it to their own culture. However, they believe their English 'non-native' teachers have acquired the skills of understanding and developing the knowledge of the Western culture, and relating it to Chinese cultures in discussions with students in the classrooms. However, they believe that the students are not given enough opportunities to discuss the events from other cultures. These groups of non-English major students have positive attitudes toward both English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers as they believe their 'native' teachers have the skills of interpreting and relating Chinese cultural events to Western cultural events. Therefore, they believe their English 'non-native' teachers have limited ability to compare and relate Chinese and Western cultures as they have had no evidence of this throughout the classes that have been taught by their English language teachers.

In addition, the findings reveal that the participants from both English and non-English major groups think both their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers are not able to acquire new cultural knowledge as those teachers only mention relevant cultural knowledge which is connected with the contents of textbooks to their students in the classroom.

In relation to the findings of this study, the participants from both English major and non-English major groups believe their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers are able to evaluate critically and use this experience to enhance their classroom practice about Chinese and Western cultures. However, English major students assume their English 'native' teachers do not have enough understanding of critical awareness of other cultures as the teachers have not referred to this relevant knowledge in English classes; on the other hand, non-English major students show a similar concern about 'non-native' teachers, as in their perceptions, those teachers appear to focus more on completing teaching tasks rather than sharing their knowledge and understanding of Chinese and Western cultures and encouraging discussion of this with the students in the classroom.

Moreover, the findings reveal that these students believe their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers are curious and have positive attitudes towards other cultures. To non-English major students, their English 'native' teachers appear to have a significant interest in talking about their own experience in China and discussing Chinese cultures with students in and after classes.

Therefore, the researcher believes this research question is answered by the findings from the perceptions of English and non-English major students which can be related to five aspects of Byram's (1997) intercultural competence model.

6.2.3 In what ways do students think intercultural competence could be developed more effectively in English language departments at Chinese universities?

To answer this research question, the participants were asked what were the benefits of developing intercultural competence in their opinion and what support they wanted to get from the English language department of the university to help them to develop intercultural competence. The findings clearly show that the participants believe that an ability to discuss and engage with intercultural competence can help them to develop confidence to talk to people from different countries, as well as to gain more opportunities in the future job market. In addition, the participants agree that they would like to attend more events and after-class activities which are organized by the English language department to speak to English 'native' speakers and to be able to have discussions of intercultural competence with students from other universities.

More specifically, English major students in this study are found that they have strong desire to develop their ability of intercultural competence. In addition, they would like to be given more opportunities to practise authentic English with English 'native' speakers, as they did not have enough support to help them practise and develop their English speaking skills in the classrooms, according to their responses in the interviews. In addition, English major students at the Chinese university would like their university to offer them opportunities to interact and communicate with English major students from other Chinese universities to share English language learning experience and the knowledge of intercultural competence. Moreover, they wish to get the support from

their university to allow them to study abroad as exchange students to learn and experience different cultures by themselves and develop their skills of intercultural competence in the authentic context.

The suggestions from non-English major participants in the Findings, in relation to the development of intercultural competence more effectively in Chinese universities, are similar to English major students' in this study. Non-English major students would also like to be supported by their university to study abroad as exchange students to develop their skills of intercultural competence by themselves, even though for a short period of time. In addition, non-English major students in this study are found that they have strong desire to be given more opportunities to practise authentic English and develop their English speaking skills, as the participants in this study consider that they were not given as many opportunities as English major students to develop their English language skills in class. Therefore, they would like to be given more opportunities in and outside the classrooms to practise their English speaking skills. Moreover, non-English major students in this study would like their university library to stock more relevant and updated English language books relating to Western cultures. Therefore, the students would be able to develop their knowledge and understanding of Western cultures in order to develop their skills of intercultural competence outside the classrooms.

The findings of this research question are clearly answered. Potential implications and suggestions for the English department of Chinese universities based on the findings of this study will be further discussed in the section 6.6.

6.2.4 To what extent do English major and non-English major students differ in their motivation to learn English and in their perceptions of how their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom of their Chinese university?

To answer this research questions, the participants were asked their motivation to learn and develop their English language skills in the interviews, the findings of students' perceptions and comparisons of intercultural competence between English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers are listed in Appendix 2. The findings clearly show

that English major students appear to enjoy learning and developing their English language skills more than non-English major students. Referring to their responses in the interviews, all these students are instrumentally motivated to learn the English language, in order to pass exams and find a better job in the future. However, English major students are also found that they have integrative motivation to learn English, in order to get more opportunities to practise English, and to understand people from different cultural backgrounds by using English as the media to communicate with them. On the other hand, participants who are non-English major students respond that learning the English language is difficult and not enjoyable for them.

To discuss English major and non-English major students' different perceptions of intercultural competence of their English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers, the findings show that English major students believe that English 'non-native' teachers can better develop intercultural competence than their English 'native' teachers in the classroom because they believe their English 'non-native' teachers have better understanding of both home and Western cultures because of their experience of studying abroad. However, non-English major students believe that English 'native' teachers can better develop intercultural competence than their English 'non-native' teachers in the classroom. Referring to the participants who are non-English major students in the interviews, they consider that their English 'non-native' teachers focus more on finishing teaching tasks, however, their English 'native' teachers would share more cultural knowledge in the classroom which makes their learning experience more enjoyable. Therefore, they assume that their English 'native' teachers can better develop intercultural competence than their 'non-native' teachers in the classroom.

Thus, the researcher believes this research question is answered by the findings. It has been found that English major students who are more motivated to learn and develop their English language skills believe that their English 'non-native' teachers can better develop intercultural competence than their English 'native' teachers because the students believe that their 'non-native' teachers have a better understanding of both home and Western cultures. However, non-English major students who seem to not enjoy learning the English language, and only develop their English language skills to pass exams are found that they prefer the way their English 'native' teachers deliver

intercultural competence in the classroom, as their 'native' teachers share cultural knowledge with them which make their English learning experience more enjoyable.

According to the findings, the researcher believes that students' motivation to learn and develop their English language is associated with their perceptions of how their English language teachers develop intercultural competence in the classroom. Students who are more motivated to learn the English language consider their English language teachers' professional skills of intercultural competence and their experience abroad are more important in the classroom; students who are less motivated to learn the English language consider teachers who can deliver enjoyable and relaxing learning experience can better develop intercultural competence in the classroom.

6.3 Limitations of this study

This research adopts an interpretive approach to analyze the data, which enables the researcher to gather in-depth information. However, there are several limitations the researcher considers in this study. It would be ideal to examine the research in more than one university in China. The researcher only examined one university because the PhD is rather a short study, this is therefore it is considered as a limitation of the size of this study. In addition, as discussed in Chapter 4, the researcher was a former student of the Chinese university where this study is undertaken, thus the researcher can be referred to as an "insider" researcher. The 'insider' position of the researcher is considered as a limitation, because the researcher is familiar with the context which might have let her interpret the results inaccurately. However, the researcher overcame this by ensuring that she represented each participant accurately. Furthermore, the researcher was unable to meet the participants in person to clarify their responses for the interviews within the restrictions of the COVID 19 pandemic. This might make it difficult for the researcher to re-interview the students which might cause the data to be analysed inaccurately. However, in order to overcome these limitations, the researcher has discussed and considered these with the participants to ensure that the participants were given clear interview questions, and the participants' voices were represented accurately in the findings chapter. The details of each limitation are listed below.

6.3.1 The size of this study

The small size of this study is considered as a limitation because the researcher only examined one university in China. Ideally the views of many more universities and students from different cities could be explored as the English language teaching system might differ in areas. However, the researcher has collected rich and in-depth data from this one university, and there was not enough time for the researcher to stay in China to collect the data from another university due to the restrictions of her personal life. In addition, this research focuses on the perceptions of students to discover their motivation to learn the English language and the development of intercultural competence by their English language teachers in the classroom, in order to guide the English educators in China to improve intercultural teaching. Collecting data from only one university might not be able to represent a common phenomenon in China. The researcher has tried to overcome this limitation by clearly analysing the findings of research questions which were underpinned by the interview questions which encouraged the participants to relate their responses to each research question. In addition, the researchers noted down the responses of participants which needed to be clarified during the interviews, and asked the participants for further information to clarify their responses via social media. Therefore, the researcher has tried to ensure the accuracy and depth of the data to overcome any limitation in the length of the study.

6.3.2 The 'insider' position of the researcher

As it was discussed in the methodology chapter, the researcher can be considered as an 'insider researcher' as the researcher being a former student of the Chinese university where this research was undertaken. However, sometimes the perspective of the "insider" is not recognized optimal for its 'objectivity' and 'accuracy' in the research field (Delyser, 2001). In addition, as discussed in the Methodology chapter, the researcher believes that her positionality as an 'insider' researcher shifted after the data collection. The responses given by the participants in the interviews were different to the researcher's previous expectations of their answers. The researcher expected that English language education might have changed in China over six years, perhaps because of the comparative youth of the students to the researcher, and the expansion

of social media and China's importance globally. Therefore, the researcher considers herself, in the perception of the participants, as well as her own, to be more of an 'outsider' researcher from a Western university rather an 'insider' researcher.

In addition, to maintain the 'objectivity' of this research, the researcher focused on the responses of the participants during the interviews without referring to her own opinions or making assumptions based on prior experience. The analysis of data was overviewed by the researcher's supervisors to ensure the objectivity of this research.

6.3.3 Working within the restrictions of the COVID Pandemic

Data collection for this research happened before the COVID pandemic, but the researcher did not have enough time to stay in China to contact the participants in person to clarify their answers after the interviews. To overcome this, after getting the permission from the participants, the researcher added them on Wechat, the Chinese social media which is similar to Facebook, in order to re-interview the students to clarify their responses to the interviews. In this way, the researcher overcame the issue of distance to contact the participants, which was made more difficult because of the COVID pandemic.

In addition, it was the first time for the researcher to experience the COVID Pandemic and national lockdowns. The temporary closure of the campus and libraries at UWS made it harder for the researcher to get access to academic articles. Instead, the researcher managed to get online articles from different academic websites with the help of the supervisors and other PhD students.

In addition, facing this situation caused by the COVID pandemic, without social contact with the close ones, it was not easy to stay positive and productive after staying at home for a few months. To overcome this, the researcher set up a daily schedule to ensure the studying routine is set up as normal. To prevent mental illness, the researcher contacted her family and friends through social media, and spent time developing new hobbies. The COVID pandemic has brought tremendous changes to lives, but on the other hand, it

enabled the researcher to have more time to review her study and think thoroughly about the potential impacts of this research.

6.3.4 Working with two different languages

As the researcher discussed in the Methodology chapter, it was expected that the participants in this study may not have been able to answer the interview questions fluently and accurately in English. Therefore, in order to collect the participants' actual and full perceptions of their motivation; and their English language teachers' ability to develop intercultural competence, as well as to provide a relaxing environment for the participants to deliver reliable data for this study, the researcher, after discussion with her supervisors, decided to interview the participants in their, and her, first language, Mandarin.

However, after the data collection, the researcher faced a challenge to translate the interview transcripts from Mandarin to English. The researcher's first language is also Mandarin, therefore, there was no difficulty for the researcher to understand the meanings from the data collected for this study. The researcher ensured that she translated as accurately as possible, to deliver the words of the participants to ensure the richness of the data in English. As translation is considered as an interpretive act in qualitative research, the researcher was aware that the actual meaning of the data might get lost in the translation process (Abma, et al., 2010). To overcome this and ensure the trustworthiness of this study and faithfulness to the responses of the participants, the data was translated as appropriately and accurately as possible. In addition, the researcher discussed the translated data with her supervisors, to make sure the data was clear and understandable in the English language setting. Therefore, the researcher believes that any potential loss of meaning from the data in the translation process was avoided.

6.4 Reconsidering the research

If the researcher had been able to review and reconsider the research, she would do a pilot study. However, the data which the researcher has already collected provided rich

information for this study. The researcher made the decision to concentrate on the data she collected in depth, rather than doing a pilot study. If the opportunity arose, the researcher would like to add a pilot study to this research to find the approach which is suitable for this research in order to ensure the efficiency and quality of this study.

The researcher studied the field of TESOL for her Masters degree as an international student in Scotland. The researcher would like to do a pilot study with other Chinese international students in Scotland to discover the ways in which the experience of intercultural study has reflected on them, and what they thought about the situation themselves.

6.5 Academic and personal development during the research

6.5.1 My academic growth

6.5.1.1 Development of my knowledge within the field

The initial idea of the researcher for this study was to discover students' preferences between English 'native-speaking' teachers and 'non-native' teachers in Chinese universities. However, the researcher realized this topic was too wide to enable her to discuss and analyse as students' perceptions and preferences of the development of intercultural teaching of their English language teachers. Then the researcher discovered the theories of intercultural competence with her supervisors' guidance. The researcher has a better understanding of intercultural competence which allowed her to investigate the research title fully by reading the academic articles related to this title and how other researchers examined intercultural competence in similar contexts.

The researcher has read numerous academic articles which are related to English learning motivation of students in China, most of these articles which lead to the result that Chinese students are instrumentally motivated to learn English. In the researcher's perception, learning English is mostly driven by passing exams and gaining qualifications for Chinese students studying in China. The researcher shared a flat with another Chinese girl in the first year in Scotland as an international student, who was

from the same university as the researcher in China. As a non-English major student, the researcher was surprised after this Chinese girl shared the information about the English courses she had in the Chinese university as an English major student. This led the researcher to understand that the English course design and the depth of knowledge are totally different between English and non-English majors. Therefore, the researcher started to consider whether English major and non-English major students would be differently motivated to learn the English language. This idea enabled the researcher to investigate all the areas related to the title of her PhD study.

In addition, the researcher clarified the term English native-speaking teachers to English 'native' teachers after reading the academic articles related to the term 'Native Speakerism' as there was not a clear definition of English 'native' speakers which could inform this study. The researcher read related articles in the Asian contexts and realized that the definitions of English 'native' speakers were quite narrow and conservative. The majority of people recognized the term English 'native' speakers as a white person who is from the US or UK. The researcher was shocked and ashamed. As a former student in the Chinese university, the researcher had experience of being taught by a Chinese teacher whose first language is English, whose teaching styles and methods were different to those of teachers who were born in China. Therefore, the term English 'native' teacher in this context refers to those teachers whose first language is English regardless of the colour of their skin.

6.5.1.2 Extended language skills

The researcher had developed as a Masters student, her language level had developed to an academic level. However, the researcher realized the language skills required to be developed after starting her PhD study. To develop the language skills, the researcher has started to write in a more formal setting and to update her understanding of academic words and terms by extending her reading and attending to other PhD students' presentations. Therefore, the researcher believes her language skills have developed, but it still remains to be improved.

6.5.2 My personal growth

6.5.2.1 Gained confidence

The researcher used to be shy to talk in public, especially not in her first language. However, after engaging with the participants during the interviews, she realized she was confident to start a conversation with people who she was not familiar with. In addition, the researcher presented her study at the transfer event and university colloquia in front of other PhD students and academics. Speaking in public in another language was a skill the researcher had indeed developed.

The researcher and other PhD students plan to attend an academic conference in Manchester at April 2020. This conference was cancelled due to COVID pandemic restrictions, the researcher lost the opportunity to share her own work and discuss with academics and PhD students in the conference. However, the researcher has gained in confidence to speak in public, and certainly would like to discuss and share her work with people from different universities and different parts of the world in upcoming academic conferences in the future.

6.5.2.2 Adapted to English-speaking environment

The researcher faced challenges in understanding lectures when she first came to Scotland as an international student. The researcher had difficulties completing the classroom assessments as she was not familiar with the educational setting in the UK. In addition, the language barrier became an issue for the researcher to express herself in English thinking.

However, the researcher believes that her English criticality has improved and she is more adapted to the English-speaking environment now. She is confident to share and discuss her work with other PhD students, and her speaking skills of English has improved which helps her to avoid the misunderstanding of her talking between her and others. In addition, the part-time employment in Scotland provided the researcher with more opportunities to practise her English speaking and listening skills, which enabled her to develop the skills of English thinking outside the classrooms.

6.6 Implications of research and recommendations

6.6.1 Recommendations for teacher training

Currently, both the findings of this research and other studies (Zhao,2012; Xu, 2017) reveal that there is not enough training offered for English language teachers in China to improve their skills of developing intercultural competence in the classroom. The implication of this is that English language teachers are not trained enough to practise and develop intercultural competence in the classroom. Therefore, the recommendation arise from this implication is that, it is necessary to remind higher educational institutions in China and other parts of the world to develop more awareness of improving intercultural competence in language education (Piller, 2002). Therefore, as the feedback from the participants discussed their perception that there was a lack of discussion of culture in the classroom, more relevant and updated teacher training should be offered to English language teachers. In addition, to improve the effectiveness of the teacher training, it is recommended that the training should be adjusted and updated based on students' feedback on their learning experience. In this study, the researcher found that according to students' perceptions, it is important to improve these teachers' practises in the classroom, particularly in the area of imparting cultural knowledge, as the focus of this study is to discover students' perceptions of the development of intercultural competence of English teachers in the classroom.

6.6.2 Recommendations for university English language departments

There are three recommendations for University English Language Departments in China based on the findings of this study. Each recommendation is based on the implications listed below.

6.6.2.1 English reading material

According to one of the findings of this research, the participants desire access to more updated English material about Western cultures in the university. The implication of this is that the English reading material which refers to the participants stocking in their

university library are outdated and limited. It is recommended that the universities should improve the quantity and quality of English reading material in the libraries. Reading books related to Western cultures enables the students to develop their understanding of intercultural competence and to be more motivated to learn the English language.

6.6.2.2 English speaking practices

The participants did not have enough opportunities to practise authentic English in their responses during the interviews. The implication of this is that Chinese students desire to be offered opportunities to practise and develop their authentic English skills. One of the participants made the recommendation for English language departments that the students would like to attend and to be more involved in English language presentations and other after-class activities which would enable them to practise their speaking skills of English.

In addition, these students desire to have more opportunities to have conversations with English 'native' speakers at the events organized by English language departments. There are international students from English-speaking countries studying in the Chinese university where this research was underpinned. Organizing events for both Chinese students and international students to attend and to communicate with each other will provide opportunities for Chinese students to develop their skills of intercultural communication and a deeper understanding of Western cultures.

6.6.2.3 Provide exchange opportunities

In relation to the research findings, these groups of students would like to be offered opportunities by English language departments to study abroad as exchange students for a short period of time. In this way, the students can develop the ability of intercultural competence by learning and practising cultural knowledge in English-speaking countries. However, it might be difficult for the English language departments to offer every single student to study abroad as exchange students due to the high expense. One of the students suggested that they would like to attend events which are

organized by the English language departments to celebrate Western festivals with English 'native' speakers and international students from other countries. Therefore, if the high expense of supporting students to study abroad is considered as an issue for English departments, in this way, Chinese universities students could still be provided opportunities to experience Western cultural events.

The findings of this study suggest that, these groups of English major students desire to exchange ideas and knowledge with other English major students from different Chinese universities, apart from exchanging experience with students abroad. Therefore, if English language departments in China could be united to organize meetings for English major students from different universities to share and exchange their knowledge of English learning, it would enable the students to widen their approaches to improve their English language proficiency and to learn new strategies to develop their ability to understand intercultural competence from other students.

6.6.3 Recommendations for English 'native' teacher recruitment

Previous research shows that the English 'native' teachers in China vary in their capabilities and experience which leads to the implication that it is difficult for Chinese employers to monitor their quality as discussed by Li (2020). Therefore, to standardize English 'native' teacher recruitment is important. Those English 'native' teachers who acquire a qualification for teaching English and a graduate certification from official universities in Western countries should be considered to be recruited by Chinese universities.

What is more important is that the recruitment of English 'native' teachers should not be limited to those who are white and from inner-circle countries (Ruecker & Ives, 2015). English language teachers should be valued for their language proficiency and teaching skills. A teacher's knowledge and teaching skills should be considered as priorities instead of the colour of skin. Therefore, It is recommended by the researcher that a teacher's race should not be considered in any circumstances for English 'native' teacher recruitment.

6.6.4 Recommendations for the English exam system in China

The current research has discovered that English language assessments are mainly written examinations in the Chinese context (Wright & Zhang, 2017). The implication of this is that there are not enough opportunities for students to practise spoken English. In the Chinese context, students are mainly instrumentally motivated to learn English to pass the exams (Dornyei & You, 2014; Liu, 2007). Including the speaking examinations in the English language assessments would enable students to develop their speaking skills to pass the exams. In addition, one of the findings of this study shows that students desire to develop their skills of spoken English to be able to communicate with English 'native' speakers, apart from aiming to gain the required certificates and passing the exams. Therefore, including speaking exams in the English language assessment in higher educational institutions in China can not only motivate students to improve their speaking skills, but also enable the students to develop their confidence to have conversations in English with people from different countries.

6.7 Suggestions for future research

There have been many possible research designs for this study to be planned and tested in future research. The researcher was unable to organize interviews in other Chinese universities because of the lack of time researching in China and restrictions of the COVID pandemic. To overcome this, future research should be rooted in a deeper analysis of the current research subject, and analyse wider and more updated data. Here the researcher listed three suggestions for the future research.

6.7.1 Widening the scope of the study

Even though the data the researcher has collected from the Chinese university is rich enough for the current study, collecting data from other Chinese universities in different cities to examine whether the findings of the current study will be able to represent the common situations in China is what the researcher would like to do in the future. In addition, the researcher desires to discover whether Chinese university students are motivated by different reasons to learn the English language when they are from different areas in.

6.7.2 Interview teachers

This current study aims to discover students' perceptions of the intercultural competence of English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers. As the findings show in Chapter 5, the majority of the participants think their English language teachers are not trained to be able to teach intercultural knowledge in class. Students' perceptions of how their teachers deliver intercultural competence in the classroom could be seen as an effective way to evaluate English language teachers' ability of intercultural competence. However, to discover English language teachers' perceptions of their own intercultural competence for any future research can add depth to this study by comparing teachers' and students' perceptions. The researcher believes it is essential to find out whether English language teachers are offered relevant training, and if so, whether this training is effective enough for them to deliver the intercultural knowledge to the students.

6.7.3 Replicate this research in different countries

As the researcher discussed in Chapter 2, Chinese students learn English as a foreign language at school. As in some other countries, a foreign language is designed as a compulsory subject for students. For example, students learn French or German at school in Scotland. The researcher would like to replicate the current research in the Scottish context, but not in a higher educational setting, as students in Scotland do not need to learn a foreign language in universities and colleges if they are not studying for degrees in foreign languages. This future research could explore how Scottish students are motivated to learn French or German, and their perceptions of the intercultural competence of foreign French 'native' teachers and 'non-native' teachers. The researcher desires to discover whether the students are similarly or differently motivated to learn a foreign language in different parts of the world, and whether the students share the same or different perceptions towards their 'native' and 'non-native' foreign language teachers. The researcher believes this future research would offer recommendations to foreign language educators in the world to be aware of improving the effectiveness of foreign language teaching in the future.

6.8 Conclusion

This research has provided an insight into the English language education in Chinese universities. Previous studies in this field have focused on comparing teaching skills and students' preferences of both English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers and teachers' self-report of their ability of intercultural competence. In order to fill in the gap, this research acknowledges the differences between English major and non-English major students in Chinese universities, and to discover whether these students' perceptions of intercultural competence of English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers will differ in some aspects.

To review and reevaluate the findings in terms of the research questions, it considered each research question in turn, and it gave evidence of how these research questions were answered. By using Byram's (1997) intercultural competence model as the theoretical framework for this study, research questions were not directly answered by the findings, but by relating each component of this model into questions in the interviews, in order to discover in detail how students' perceive the development of intercultural competence of their English language teachers in the classroom. Therefore, the researcher believes all the research questions are answered by the findings.

In addition, the researcher discussed possible changes of this current study if it could be done differently; a pilot study would be done to examine the feasibility of the research approach. During the period of study as a PhD student, the researcher's knowledge of this research title and language skills have benefited her in both academic and personal life.

According to the findings of this study, it could be suggested that language educators and English language departments in China should consider developing English language teachers' intercultural teaching skills, in order to raise awareness of students' need for English learning and offer them support. This current study is small in scale and has its limitations. For future research, the researcher intends to widen the scope of

this study, improve the research design, and replicate this research in different countries' contexts.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

Interview Protocol

Hello, my name is Yueying Zheng, I am a PhD student at the school of Education at The University of West of Scotland. Thank you very much for accepting to take part in this study. This interview will be conducted to examine **English major and non-English major students' perceptions of intercultural competence of native and non-native English teachers at a Chinese university.**

Based on that, this interview aims at collecting data about your perceptions and experiences of intercultural communication with both native and non-native English teachers at your university. This face-to-face interview may take up to 1 hour so please let me know if you would like to take a break or to withdraw at any time. In order to proceed with the interview process, your signature on the consent form is needed first.

Background information

- Can you please introduce yourself?
- How long have you been studying English?
- Do you enjoy learning and developing your English?
 - Why / Why not?
- Do you study in an English major or non-English major class?

How do you perceive intercultural competence and the role of your University teachers in contributing to its development in English classes at your universities?

- Are you taught intercultural competence directly in English classes?
 - Can you give some examples?
- In what ways have you received any understanding of intercultural competence from your English teachers?
- Do your English teachers show knowledge of intercultural competence in English classes?
 - If so, can you give some examples?
- Do you think your English teachers have been trained to teach intercultural competence?
 - Please give reasons: why or why not?

To what extent is intercultural competence developed between English 'native' and 'non-native' University teachers with Chinese university students?

- Do your native English teachers have knowledge of social groups and practices in their own culture and in Chinese culture?

- If so, can you give examples of how they develop this in English classes?
- Do your non-native English teachers have knowledge of social groups and practices in their own and English-speaking cultures?
 - If so, can you give examples of how they develop this in English classes?
- Are your native English teachers able to interpret an event from your culture, and compare or relate it to events in their own culture?
 - If so, can you give examples of how this is done in English classes?
- Are your non-native English teachers able to interpret an event from their own culture, and compare or relate it to events in the English culture?
 - If so, can you give examples of how this is done in English classes?
- Do you think your native English teachers are able to acquire new knowledge of a culture and cultural practices and can impart and discuss knowledge, attitudes and skills within the constraints of a real 'classroom' context?
 - If so, can you give examples of how this is done in English classes?
- Do you think your non-native English teachers are able to acquire new knowledge of a culture and cultural practices and can impart and discuss knowledge, attitudes and skills within the constraints of a real 'classroom' context?
 - If so, can you give examples of how this is done in English classes?
- Do you think your native English teachers are able to evaluate, critically, perspectives and practices in your own and in English-speaking cultures?
 - If so, can you give examples of how this is done in English classes?
- Do you think your non-native English teachers are able to evaluate, critically, perspectives and practices in your own and in English-speaking cultures?
 - If so, can you give examples of how this is done in English classes?
- Do you think your native English teachers are curious about other cultures as well as their own?
 - If so, can you give examples of how this is done in English classes?
- Do you think your native English teachers are curious about other cultures as well as their own?
 - If so, can you give examples of how this is done in English classes?

In what ways could intercultural competence be developed more effectively in English departments at Chinese universities?

- What, in your opinion, are the benefits of developing intercultural competence?
- What support do you want from your university to develop intercultural competence during English classes?

Thank you very much for your contribution today.

Appendix 2 Focus Groups and in-depth interview results

Focus Groups Results

G1= Focus group participants 1 (English major students)

G2= Focus group participants 2 (English major students)

G3= Focus group participants 3 (Non-English major students)

G4= Focus group participants 4 (Non-English major students)

IC= Intercultural Competence

English major students

Participants	Quotations	Subthemes	Themes
G1	'I want to learn and develop my English because I want to work as an English teacher in the future, but I think I will enjoy learning English more if I can get more chances to use English apart from English class.'	Instrumental and potential Integrative motivations	English Learning Motivation
G2	'I want to learn and develop my English because I think a good English proficiency is not only helpful to find a proper job in China but also easier to get more chances to know different cultures and broaden the horizon of life.'	Instrumental and Integrative motivations	English Learning Motivation
G1	'The knowledge of intercultural competence is not directly taught in class, but our English teacher introduced cultural background and events while we were learning a relevant article on textbooks. And we will have a course about intercultural communication next year.'	Not directly taught but mentioned in class	Development of IC in English Class
G2	'I think we are not directly taught intercultural competence in class, but our teacher introduced western cultural knowledge, and how to transfer Chinese thinking to English thinking to us based on her abroad experiences.'	Not directly taught and based on English teachers' abroad experience	Development of IC in English Class

G1	'Most of our Chinese teachers they have experience of studying abroad, so they always compare some aspects of home and western cultures in class. And our English native-speaking teachers they are curious about Chinese culture, they will compare similar festivals in China and their home country, but they don't know as much as our Chinese teachers.'	'non-native' teachers have better understanding of both home and western cultures than English 'native' teachers based on abroad experience	Preference between English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers
G2	'Our Chinese teachers introduced us western life styles which are different in China, their experience in a western country and some British and American dialects. However, English 'native' teachers did not mention much cultural knowledge in class, but they still introduced western movies during the chat with us.'	English 'native' teachers did not mention as much cultural knowledge as 'non-native' teachers in class	Preference between English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers
G1	'I don't think our English teachers are trained to teach the knowledge of intercultural competence as they did not mention it and teach it directly in class. Some English teachers they teach cultural knowledge because they have known the knowledge already.'	Students think English teachers are not trained for teaching IC in class	IC training of English teachers
G2	'Our English teachers are not trained to teach intercultural competence in class as we think they are tasked to teaching through the textbooks and help us to pass the exams.'	Not trained and English teachers focus more on textbooks	IC training of English teachers
G1	'We don't think making intercultural competence as a course is the best choice for us as we just want to have more chances to communicate with English native speakers and know more about English movies and books. The ability will develop faster if the university help us make English learning as an interest instead of a task.'	Make English learning as an interest	Suggestion for developing IC
G2	'If we can get some opportunities as exchange students to study abroad will be very helpful, as we can build	Exchange students	Suggestion for developing IC

	up the understanding of intercultural competence ourselves. Also, We would like to discuss intercultural competence and communicate with English major students from other universities to find out their opinions.'		
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Non-English major students

Participants	Quotations	Subthemes	Themes
G3	'To be honest, I am not very interested to learn English as English has been a part of my life, I need to learn English to pass the exams and be more competitive in the future job market. But I still hope I can use English more in my daily life.'	Instrumental motivation but want to develop English proficiency	English learning motivation
G4	'I used to enjoy learning English when I was very young, because it is a very cool thing to me to talk to foreigners. But when I grow up, I found it is difficult to learn English deeply as we only use English to pass exams and for a better job opportunity.'	Instrumental motivation and not enjoy learning English	English learning motivation
G3	'Our Chinese teachers they hardly teach cultural knowledge in English class, but focus more on textbook. Sometimes they mentioned their quite short experience living abroad as a visiting scholar. In addition, our English 'native' teachers sometimes introduced the difference of western and Chinese culture in class.'	Not directly taught in class	Development of IC in English class
G4	'Intercultural competence is not directly taught in class but sometimes our English 'native' teachers introduce culture differences between America and China such as festivals, shopping and eating habits in class.'	Not directly taught in class	Development of IC in English class
G3	'Our English 'native' teachers are very curious about Chinese culture; they will ask us if they have something they don't understand. And they didn't only introduce their	English 'Non-native' teachers focus more on textbooks	Preference between English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers

	home culture in class, but also told us their own experience as a foreigner in China. Our Chinese teachers they think we have known some simple aspects of western culture already so they just focus on teaching through the textbooks.'		
G4	'The teaching task for Chinese teachers is teaching through all the knowledge in the textbooks and help us pass the exams, but English 'native' teachers are hired in our department are only to help us improve our spoken English. So no wonder English 'native' teachers they have more time to introduce us cultural knowledge and make the course more enjoyable.'	The course by English 'native' teachers is more enjoyable as their teaching task is easier than 'non-native' teachers	Preference between English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers
G3	'I don't think our English teachers are trained to teach the knowledge of intercultural competence in class. As it is not always that they mention cultural knowledge in class, they only tell us when they want to.'	Students think English teachers are not trained for teaching IC in class	IC training of English teachers
G4	'English teachers are not trained to teach intercultural competence, they teach us the cultural knowledge and western events, stories based on their own knowledge and experience.'	Not trained and cultural knowledge are only based on teachers' own experience	IC training of English teachers
G3	'We would like to have more chances to practice English if we have an 'English corner' in school. And we hope we can get some opportunities to study abroad as short-term exchange students or to go for a summer camp to another country which is organized by our university.'	Exchange students and summer camp	Suggestion for developing IC
G4	'As non-English major students, we can hardly have chances to use and speak English, hopefully our department will organize some meetings or parties to let us communicate with English native speakers and improve our English.'	More chances to communicate with English native speakers	Suggestion for developing IC

Interview Results

P1= Participant 1 (English major)

P2= Participant 2 (English major)

P3= Participant 3 (English major)

P4= Participant 4 (non-English major)

P5= Participant 5 (non-English major)

P6= Participant 6 (non-English major)

IC= Intercultural Competence

Participant	Quotations	Subthemes	Themes
P1	'My Chinese teacher mentioned how to speak English in proper English thinking, how to use English dialects in a proper way when we were watching an English movie. But our English 'native' teacher hardly mention this kind of knowledge, sometimes he teaches us some English words which are only used in his home country.'	Not directly taught but mentioned	Development of IC in English Class
P1	'Our Chinese teacher has at least 6-month studying abroad experience, so I think they have quite good understanding of western culture, and they know how to compare Chinese and western cultures in different ways. However, our English 'native' teacher knows deeply about western culture, but he only knows plain knowledge of Chinese culture.'	Based on teachers' own experience	IC knowledge of English teachers
P1	'Our Chinese teacher knows about both Chinese and western cultural knowledge and can easily tell us the difference and how to use English properly as they know how to let us understand. But our English 'native' teacher is not very familiar with Chinese cultures so sometimes when he introduce western stories, it is a little difficult to relate to my own life.'	Share same cultural background with English 'non-native' teachers	Preference between English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers
P1	'I don't think my Chinese teacher is trained but they might be introduced relevant knowledge	Not trained	IC training of English teachers

	during other trainings. As for English 'native' teachers, most of them have lived in China for six or seven years, even though they are not trained, they might have basic understanding of intercultural competence.'		
P1	'I hope my university will hold more after-class activities such as English presentation competition and English corner, also I think my teachers could try to set up a website which allow us to face-to face talk to English 'native' speakers.'	Online and outline communication with English 'native' speakers	Suggestion for developing IC

Participant	Quotations	Subthemes	Themes
P2	'My Chinese teacher shared her experience in Europe, recommend us some famous Chinese and English movies and told us mythologies of ancient Rome in class. In addition, our English 'native' teacher compared festivals in China and Western countries, introduced American religions, also his understanding of Chinese books in class.'	Not directly taught but mentioned in class	Development of IC in English Class
P2	'Our Chinese teacher has cultural knowledge of Chinese and western festivals, and they desire to discover more about western culture when she can get a chance to go abroad. And our English 'native' teacher know deeply about western culture, as he starts learning Chinese language and shows a massive interest in Chinese culture.'	English teachers have positive attitudes learning IC	IC knowledge of English teachers
P2	'My Chinese teacher has abundant knowledge of western and Chinese culture as she shared mythologies of ancient Rome with us in class. Even though our English 'native' teacher has positive attitude to learn Chinese culture, sometimes he needs to ask us questions to know more about it.'	English 'non-native' teachers seem more knowledgeable in cultures	Preference between English 'native' and 'non-native'teachers
P2	'I have no idea if they are trained specific knowledge of intercultural	Might have been trained	IC training of English teachers

	competence or not. But I think they might have learned relevant knowledge from other teaching trainings.'		
P2	'I hope my university can give us more chances to share experiences with English major students from other universities to find out if they have any tips for learning English and ideas of intercultural competence as well.'	Share experiences with English major students from other universities	Suggestion for developing IC

Participant	Quotations	Subthemes	Themes
P3	'Both Chinese and English 'native' teachers didn't teach intercultural competence directly in class. However, our Chinese teachers who had experience living abroad shared her opinions on different cultures and interesting stories happened to her when she was abroad. But my English 'native' teacher hardly mention about culture in class.'	Not directly taught in class	Development of IC in English Class
P3	'I think my grammar teacher has the knowledge of intercultural competence based on her abroad experience, but other English teachers focus more on the knowledge of textbooks. In addition, my English 'native' teacher focus more on improving English speaking skills of us.'	Most English teachers focus more on teaching through textbooks	IC knowledge of English teachers
P3	'It is obvious that Chinese teachers who have more experience studying abroad, share more cultural knowledge to us in class. As a student, I can learn more new things from this kind of teachers.'	English 'non-native' teachers seem more knowledgeable in cultures	Preference between English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers
P3	'I don't think my English teachers are trained to teach intercultural competence, as they focus more on teaching through textbooks, grammar knowledge and improving our spoken skills.'	Not trained	IC training of English teachers

P3	'I would like to have more chances to study abroad as an exchange student to improve my English, and hope the English department in my university can support us to celebrate western festivals. In addition, it will be better if we can share experiences with English major students from other universities.'	Share experiences with English major students from other universities and exchange students	Suggestion for developing IC
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Participant	Quotations	Subthemes	Themes
P4	'My Chinese teacher shared her experience as visiting scholar abroad to us in class. And English 'native' teacher introduced the difference between western and Chinese festivals, life and fashion styles to us in class.'	Not directly taught but mentioned	Development of IC in English Class
P4	'I think both my Chinese and English 'native' teacher have the knowledge of intercultural competence as they teach cultural knowledge in class and discuss with us after class to let us understand more different cultures.'	Teach cultural knowledge in and after class	IC knowledge of English teachers
P4	'I think my English 'native' teacher knows more about western culture than Chinese teacher so they can introduce cultural knowledge deeply to us. In addition, he shared his experience in China and his own understanding of Chinese culture to us as well.'	English 'native' teachers know deeply about western culture	Preference between English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers
P4	'I know my English teachers have different trainings but not sure whether intercultural competence is trained or not. Sometimes they mention cultural knowledge in class so they might have been trained.'	Might have been trained	IC training of English teachers
P4	'I hope there will be more English books which are about western cultures in our library for us to read. Also If the English department organize activities such as international exchange students and international volunteers will be very	Exchange students and more English books	Suggestion for developing IC

	helpful for us to know different cultures.'		
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Participant	Quotations	Subthemes	Themes
P5	'Both of my Chinese and English 'native' teacher did not really talked about what was intercultural competence in class, but they told us the difference of life styles, festivals, customs between Chinese and western cultures.'	Not directly taught but mentioned	Development of IC in English Class
P5	'I think my Chinese teacher has some knowledge of intercultural competence as she has experience studying abroad. And my English 'native' teacher has experience living in China for more than six years. So it is easy to pick up the knowledge of intercultural competence if you have time to experience another culture.'	Based on teachers' own experience	IC knowledge of English teachers
P5	'Even though my Chinese teacher has a short-term experience studying abroad, our English 'native' teacher still knows more about western culture than her. As students, we are more curious to learn about western culture as we know Chinese culture quite well.'	English 'native' teachers know deeply about western culture	Preference between English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers
P5	'I think they might have been trained the knowledge of intercultural competence when my English teachers studied abroad as visiting scholars. But I am not very sure as they didn't mention in class.'	Might have been trained	IC training of English teachers
P5	'I hope our English department will organize more chances for us to study abroad as international exchange students or intercultural volunteers.'	Exchange students	Suggestion for developing IC

Participant	Quotations	Subthemes	Themes
P6	'Our Chinese teacher focus more on improving our listening and reading skills in class, and English 'native' teacher focus on developing our speaking and presentation skills. They did not talk much about	Not directly taught but mentioned	Development of IC in English Class

	intercultural competence in class as they need to finish their teaching tasks. But sometimes my English 'native' teacher introduced western festivals and compared them with Chinese festivals.'		
P6	'I don't know if my Chinese teacher has the knowledge of intercultural competence or not as she didn't mention much in class. But I think my English 'native' teacher has the knowledge, because he understand deeply of western culture and he is very interested to know about Chinese culture and can tell us the difference as well.'	English 'native' teacher shows massive interest in Chinese culture	IC knowledge of English teachers
P6	' My Chinese teacher knows deeply about Chinese ancient cultures so she always mentioned that to us in class, but I am more curious to learn about western culture which my English 'native' teacher helped me understand more about it.'	English 'native' teachers know deeply about western culture	Preference between English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers
P6	'My Chinese teacher has experience studying in UK as a visiting scholar so she might be trained about intercultural competence at that time. But I am not very sure.'	Might have been trained	IC training of English teachers
P6	'I just want to attend more activities which can help me to get more chances to speak and use English.'	More chances to use English	Suggestion for developing IC

Appendix 3 Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Name of department:

School of Education, University of the West of Scotland

Title of the study: English major and non-English major students' perceptions of intercultural competence of native and non-native English teachers at a Chinese university.

Dear Participant

My name is Yueying Zheng and I am conducting research for a Postgraduate thesis at the University of the West of Scotland. My contact details are as follows:

- Email: [REDACTED]
- Telephone: [REDACTED]

Supervisor's contact details:

- Dr Margaret Allan
- Email: [REDACTED]

Introduction

I would like to invite you to take part in a research project. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve for you. Please take the time to read the following information carefully and ask questions about anything you do not understand. Talk to others about the study if you wish.

What is the purpose of the study?

This research aims to find out students' perceptions of intercultural competence of both native and non-native English teachers in a Chinese university. The reason I chose to conduct this research is based on my own experience as a student at a Chinese university. I would like to find out whether there has been any change in the teaching of intercultural competence in the Chinese university context. In addition, there is an increasing demand for English native-speaking teachers in China, so it will be interesting to examine this; and as a researcher, I want to explore what Chinese university students require in terms of support to develop intercultural competence in English classes, and what kind of support they want to get from English departments at Chinese universities.

Why have I been invited to take part in the study?

You have been invited to this study because the sample selection and data collection procedure of this study will be undertaken from English major and non-English major students at a Chinese university. The university which has been selected for this research is Changchun University of Technology because it is an 'average' university in China. Selecting

samples of participants from this university, from among the large student group in China, will ensure the credibility of the study. 20 participants from your university will take part in this study.

Do I have to take part?

No, you do not have to participate. There will be no adverse consequences if you decide not to participate or withdraw at a later stage. You can withdraw your participation at any time. You can request for your data to be withdrawn until publication of the data without giving a reason and without prejudice.

If you withdraw from the study, this will mean the following for your participation and data: all data identifiable to you would be withdrawn from the study; no further data would be collected or any other research procedures would be carried out in relation to you.

What will my involvement require?

If you agree to take part, we will then ask you to sign a consent form. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and a copy of your signed consent form. The research will last three years but your involvement would only be for the interviews. During this time, you will be asked to attend focus group interviews, and some of you will be randomly picked up for further semi-structured in-depth interviews.

What will I have to do?

You are only required to be honest to answer any questions during the interviews.

What will happen to data that I provide?

The name of participants of this research will not be used in the written transcripts of the interview, nor in the final report for the project, nor in any other publications arising from the research. The names of the participants were referred to by code instead (i.e. Participant 1, Participant 2, Participant 3.....). Electronic files and documents will be password protected and paper documents would be securely stored in a locked draw.

What if there is a problem?

Any complaint or concern about any aspect of the way you have been dealt with during the course of the study will be addressed; please contact Yueying Zheng Principal Investigator on [REDACTED]. In the first instance, you can also contact my supervisor Dr Margaret Allan at [REDACTED].

Will my taking part in the study be kept confidential?

Yes. Your details will be held in complete confidence and we will follow ethical and legal practice in relation to all study procedures.

Who is organizing and funding the research?

This research is organized by University of the West of Scotland, and funded by the researcher herself Yueying Zheng.

Who has reviewed the project?

This research has been examined by the University Research Ethics Committee, to protect your interests.

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet.

Appendix 4 Participant Letter

School of Education, University of the West of Scotland

Title of study: English major and non-English major students' perceptions of intercultural competence of English 'native' and 'non-native' English teachers at a Chinese university.

Dear Participant

My name is Yueying Zheng and I am a PhD student in the school of Education, University of West of Scotland, UK. I would like to invite you to take part in my study, which aims to explore English major and non-English major students' perceptions of intercultural competence of native and non-native English teachers at a Chinese university.

Through conducting the interviews and focus group discussions, the study seeks to understand the ways in which English major and non-major students perceive intercultural competence and the role of your University teachers in contributing to its development in English classes at your universities.

Before making the decision to take part in this study or not, it is important to understand the aim of this research. Therefore, please take time to read the information sheet, and to think about participating or not in the present study.

With your consent, I will record the research sessions. The information obtained from you will be securely stored, and only my supervisory team and I will have access to the data.

Your names and contact details will be separated from the data you provide and will not be shared with third parties. In reporting the data, your names will be changed and replaced with pseudonyms so that no one can identify you in the study.

You are able to withdraw from the research at any time without providing any explanation to the researcher. You are free to use any language you prefer during the session but will ask that the language you choose should be one that the researcher can also understand and use.

If you have any questions concerning the study, please do not hesitate to contact me via phone or email. My mobile/cell phone number is _____ and my email address is _____

_____. If you have further questions about the study, please contact my lead supervisor, Dr Margaret Allan: _____

Thank you for considering taking part in my study.

Yours sincerely,

Yueying Zheng

PhD Student, University of the West of Scotland, UK

Appendix 5 Consent Form

Consent Form: Participants (interview)

Name of department:

School of Education, University of the West of Scotland (UWS)

Title of the study:

English major and non-English major students' perceptions of intercultural competence of English 'native' and 'non-native' teachers at a Chinese university.

- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above study and the researcher has answered any questions to my satisfaction.
- I understand that taking part is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.
- I understand that I can withdraw my data from the study up to the point of anonymization.
- I understand that any information recorded during the study will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.
- I consent to being a participant in this study.
- I consent to being audio recorded as part of the study

I (PRINT NAME)	Hereby agree to take part in the above study
Signature of Participant:	Date

